

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

**Autonomous Off-Road Vehicles:
Enhancing Perception, Remote Control,
and Environmental Impact Through
Advanced AI Techniques**

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Dedication

The past three years have been filled with both challenges and achievements. Moving abroad to pursue research was difficult, requiring me to build a new life in an unfamiliar place. However, this journey not only expanded my knowledge but also enriched my life with new experiences and friendships, making it all worthwhile. I'm deeply grateful for the support I received, and I dedicate this thesis to those who made it possible.

This thesis is dedicated to:

Mis padres, María Piedad y Conrado, quienes me inculcaron el amor por el aprendizaje y la creencia en el poder de la perseverancia. Su apoyo y ánimo inquebrantables han sido la base de mis logros académicos y vitales. Gracias por estar siempre ahí.

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“Synchronicity is an ever present reality
for those who have eyes to see.”

Carl Jung

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this dissertation is entirely my own work, with the exception of specific references and acknowledgments made to the contributions of others. The content presented herein has not been previously submitted, in whole or in part, for any other degree or qualification at this or any other institution.

Javier Saez-Perez

July 2024

The research work presented in this thesis is the aggregation of publications that have been submitted, peer-reviewed, accepted and published in recognised international journals and international conferences and where the PhD candidate is the first and main author. Hence, the PhD candidate confirms that he has made the major contribution to all publications comprising this thesis. The following is a detailed list of the published research outcomes that constitute this thesis (2 journals and 2 conferences):

- **Outcome 1 (Journal):**

Journal	Sensors
Title	Design, Implementation, and Empirical Validation of a Framework for Remote Car Driving Using a Commercial Mobile Network
Authors	Javier Saez-Perez, Qi Wang, Jose M Alcaraz-Calero and Jose Garcia-Rodriguez
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	3.735
Volume	23
Pages	17
Year of Publication	2023
DOI	10.3390/s23031671
URL	https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/3/1671

- **Outcome 2 (Conference):**

Conference	International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications
Title	Enhancing Point Cloud Resolution for Autonomous Driving with Deep Learning AI Models
Authors	Javier Saez-Perez, Qi Wang, Jose M Alcaraz-Calero and Jose Garcia-Rodriguez
Date of conference	February 2024
Location	Biarritz, France
DOI	10.1109/PerComWorkshops59983.2024.10503354

- **Outcome 3 (Conference):**

Conference	International Symposium on Communication Systems, Networks and Digital Signal Processing
Title	Advancing Off-Road Operations: Comparative Assessment of Object Detection Methodologies
Authors	Javier Saez-Perez, Qi Wang, Jose M Alcaraz-Calero and Jose Garcia Rodriguez
Date of Conference	July 2024
Location	Rome, Italy
DOI	10.1109/CSNDSP60683.2024.10636691

- **Outcome 4 (Journal):**

Journal	IEEE Access
Title	Optimizing AI Transformer Models for CO_2 Emission Prediction in Self-Driving Vehicles with Mobile Edge Computing Support
Authors	Javier Saez-Perez, Pablo Benlloch-Caballero, David Tena-Gago, Qi Wang, Jose M Alcaraz-Calero and Jose Garcia-Rodriguez
Year of publication	2024

In addition, the following software projects have been developed to empirically validate and evaluate the research work presented in this thesis. The author's will is to make them public once we have exploited their results in the context of the fore-coming post-doctoral activities, so that they could be share with the scientific community as open source projects and thus allowing the extension and continuation of this research contribution:

- **Outcome 5 (Software):**

Title	Fusion data collector
Author	Javier Saez-Perez
Description	<p>specialized tool for the collection and synchronization of multi-sensor data in off-road environments. The tool was designed to capture data from two distinct types of sensors: LiDARs and optical cameras. Leveraging the Robot Operating System (ROS), the tool efficiently gathered both point cloud data from the LiDARs and image data from the cameras. A critical feature of the tool is its ability to filter and retain only those data pairs that were captured concurrently. Temporal alignment between LiDAR and camera data is essential, as discrepancies can lead to inaccuracies in downstream processing and significantly degrade the performance of deep learning models trained on such data.</p> <p>This tool played a pivotal role in the creation of a robust and reliable dataset, which was subsequently used for training deep learning algorithms in challenging off-road scenarios. The ability to accurately align multi-sensor data is crucial for the successful application of these algorithms, and this tool represents a significant advancement in the field of autonomous vehicle research.</p>

- **Outcome 6 (Dataset):**

Author	Javier Saez-Perez
Title	UWS Off-road Dataset
Description	The UWS Off-Road Dataset is a unique collection of LiDAR point cloud and image data designed for training and evaluating object detection algorithms in challenging off-road environments. Collected across various terrains in Alicante (Spain) and Paisley (UK), this dataset fills a gap in the research community by providing annotated data specifically for off-road scenarios, focusing on human detection for search and rescue operations. The dataset's high-quality sensor data and diverse environments make it a valuable resource for advancing research in off-road perception, autonomous navigation, and robotics. The dataset presents opportunities for expansion and further research to address the complexities of off-road object detection and enhance the capabilities of autonomous vehicles in diverse terrains.

- **Outcome 7 (Software):**

Software Project	<i>CO₂</i> ViT
Author	Javier Saez-Perez
Description	The <i>CO₂</i> ViT is a novel deep learning architecture designed specifically for predicting <i>CO₂</i> emissions in self-driving vehicles. Adapted from the Vision Transformer (ViT) framework, it utilizes a transformer encoder with 1D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Location-Based Attention to process sequences of vehicle status parameters, capturing temporal dependencies crucial for accurate predictions. Implemented in PyTorch, the model incorporates normalization as a pre-processing step, enhancing its predictive accuracy compared to standardization. The <i>CO₂</i> ViT demonstrates superior performance in both accuracy and inference time compared to previous state-of-the-art models, making it a promising tool for optimizing energy efficiency and promoting sustainability in autonomous vehicles.

- **Outcome 8 (Hardware):**

Hardware	Portable Multi-Sensor Perception System (PMSPS)
Author	Javier Saez-Perez
Description	Portable Multi-Sensor Perception System is a portable, adaptable rig designed to collect synchronized LiDAR point cloud and camera image data for research and development of autonomous systems in off-road environments.

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Abstract

This thesis addresses the critical challenges of deploying Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) in off-road environments, particularly for Search and Rescue (SAR) operations. It proposes a multi-faceted approach that encompasses enhanced perception, improved point cloud resolution, human-in-the-loop autonomy, and environmental sustainability.

A novel dataset, the UWS Off-Road Dataset, was introduced, providing annotated Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) point cloud and image data specifically tailored for off-road scenarios. This dataset fills a critical gap in existing resources, enabling the development and evaluation of robust object detection algorithms for challenging terrains.

Extensive experiments were conducted to evaluate state-of-the-art deep learning models for human detection, including both single-modal (LiDAR-based) and multi-modal (LiDAR and camera fusion) approaches. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of Point Pillars, a point-cloud-based model, in achieving high accuracy in off-road human detection.

To enhance perception capabilities further, novel point cloud upsampling techniques using generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) were investigated. This approach improves the resolution and quality of LiDAR data, leading to more accurate and detailed environmental representations. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed Point Cloud Upsampling using Graph Convolutional Networks (PU-GCN) model in achieving superior performance compared to other upsampling methods.

The thesis also explores human-in-the-loop autonomy by designing and implementing a remote driving framework on a commercial vehicle using 4G connectivity. This real-world validation demonstrates the feasibility of teleoperation as a complementary technology to fully autonomous driving, enabling human intervention in challenging or uncertain situations.

Finally, the thesis investigates the environmental impact of AVs by developing a novel transformer-based model, *CO₂ViT*, for accurate *CO₂* emission prediction. The model is evaluated in both standalone and Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) environments, highlighting its potential for real-time emission monitoring and optimization.

Overall, this thesis contributes to the advancement of autonomous vehicle technology for off-road applications, with a particular focus on enhancing perception, safety, and sustainability. The developed datasets, algorithms, and frameworks offer valuable tools for researchers and practitioners working towards the deployment of robust and environmentally responsible autonomous systems in challenging off-road environments.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Humans have long dreamed of creating machines capable of performing tasks independently. Despite significant advancements across various fields, the automotive industry has yet to achieve fully functional vehicles in all challenging scenarios, which remain largely theoretical or experimental rather than a reality. Advancements in self-driving car technology have accelerated in recent years. These new capabilities hold the potential to dramatically impact transportation on a global scale. These advancements promise substantial improvements in the efficiency, convenience, and safety of our roadways and transportation systems.

While substantial progress has been made, numerous challenges remain at all levels of system functionality. Addressing these concerns is crucial, especially given the wide-ranging potential effects of autonomous technology. Globally, 10 trillion automobile miles [14] are driven annually, presenting countless scenarios in which AVs could fail. Ensuring the reliability and safety of these systems is paramount as we move closer to fully AVs. This is true for both urban and off-road environments. In urban areas, with their complex traffic patterns and dense surroundings, reliable self-driving cars are essential to prevent accidents and ensure smooth traffic flow. Off-road, where unpredictable terrain and unforeseen obstacles are common, reliable autonomous systems are crucial for passenger safety and successful navigation.

Even with these advancements, achieving a fully autonomous vehicle that can handle all driving scenarios without human intervention is likely still far off. This is where teleoperation

emerges as a valuable complementary technology. Teleoperation allows a human driver to remotely control a vehicle, potentially from a location far removed from the car itself. This technology can bridge the gap between the current capabilities of autonomous vehicles and the ideal of a fully self-driving car. In situations where AVs encounter unforeseen challenges or limitations, a remote human operator can take control and safely navigate the vehicle. This can be particularly beneficial in the following ways:

- **Handling unexpected situations:** Even the most advanced AVs may struggle with unexpected situations on the road, such as accidents, adverse weather conditions, or unclear signage. Teleoperation allows a human operator to intervene and guide the vehicle safely through these situations.
- **Navigating complex environments:** Off-road environments or highly congested urban areas can pose significant challenges for AVs. Teleoperation enables a human with superior situational awareness and decision-making capabilities to take control and navigate the vehicle through these complexities.
- **Maintaining safety during critical moments:** In the event of a potential system malfunction or safety hazard, teleoperation allows a human operator to take immediate control and prevent accidents.

The development of teleoperation, alongside continued advancements in autonomous driving, offers a promising path towards a safer and more efficient transportation future. Nonetheless, a significant disparity exists between the abundance of research data and materials available for developing AVs in urban environments and the scarcity of such resources for off-road scenarios. While significant strides have been made in urban autonomous driving, the transferability of these advancements to off-road settings remains largely unexplored. Off-road scenarios introduce unique complexities, such as traversing rugged terrains, navigating through dense vegetation, and detecting dynamic obstacles like fallen trees or wildlife. Addressing these challenges requires specialized research efforts tailored to the distinct demands of off-road environments. The main existing open-source datasets for autonomous

driving predominantly focus on urban driving scenarios, where road markings, traffic signals, and well-defined pathways abound. These datasets fail to capture the intricacies of off-road environments. The absence of data specific to off-road challenges, such as diverse weather conditions, impedes the progress of robust perception algorithms and autonomous navigation systems designed for these scenarios.

This disparity in data resources is particularly critical considering the vast potential of AVs to significantly transform various off-road operations that currently face significant logistical and safety challenges. One such application lies in delivering essential supplies during natural disasters in remote locations. Reaching isolated areas after natural disasters can be time-consuming and hazardous for human responders. Traditional methods of delivering aid often rely on helicopters or off-road vehicles, which can be limited by weather conditions, accessibility, and pilot or driver fatigue. Autonomous vehicles, equipped for off-road navigation and capable of operating for extended periods, could deliver critical aid more rapidly and efficiently. This would significantly enhance disaster response capabilities by ensuring timely delivery of essential supplies to affected populations.

Similarly, agricultural automation in rural environments presents a compelling application for off-road AVs. Labour shortages and the vast scale of rural agriculture pose significant challenges for farmers. AVs, equipped with appropriate sensors and actuators, could automate various tasks currently performed manually. These tasks could include crop monitoring, spraying pesticides and herbicides, and even harvesting crops. Automating these tasks would improve agricultural efficiency and productivity, while also alleviating the pressure on the agricultural workforce.

Additionally, AVs hold promise for facilitating exploration and environmental monitoring in uncharted areas. Currently, exploring and collecting data in remote or hazardous locations is often limited by human capabilities and safety concerns. AVs equipped with specialized sensors could navigate these challenging terrains and collect valuable data. This capability would significantly advance scientific discovery in various fields, such as geology, ecology, and meteorology. Additionally, AVs could be used for environmental monitoring in areas

that are difficult or dangerous for humans to access, such as regions prone to wildfires or volcanic eruptions.

Finally, SAR missions in challenging terrain represent another area where AVs hold potential. However, it is important to acknowledge the advancements made in recent years with other technologies. The emergence of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) has revolutionized SAR operations by providing aerial reconnaissance capabilities. UAV equipped with high-resolution cameras transmit real-time images of the search area, allowing SAR teams to efficiently cover extensive areas of terrain. Furthermore, the application of object detection algorithms on the images captured by UAV allows for automated analysis and identification of potential targets, further streamlining the search process and increasing the likelihood of locating missing individuals. This integration of UAV technology with advanced object detection algorithms represents a significant advancement in SAR operations, offering a cost-effective and scalable solution to the challenges posed by remote wilderness environments. Nonetheless, alternative strategies must be considered to augment SAR operations in challenging scenarios where weather conditions, such as poor visibility or strong winds, impede the use of UAV. Ground robots emerge as a viable solution in such circumstances, offering the capability to access remote and difficult terrains where human intervention may be impractical or unsafe. Despite their potential, there remains a notable scarcity of research exploring the integration of ground robots into SAR operations, particularly in the context of off-road scenarios. Additionally, existing literature on SAR often overlooks the utilization of multi-sensor systems, which have demonstrated efficacy in diverse environments but remain under-explored in off-road settings. Addressing these gaps in research presents an opportunity to enhance SAR capabilities by leveraging the complementary strengths of ground robots, multi-sensor systems, and potentially, autonomous vehicles in the future. This combined approach could improve detection and localization of missing persons in challenging conditions.

This PhD thesis aims to address these gaps by developing advanced autonomous systems for off-road SAR operations. The objectives include creating single- and multi-modal systems for perception-based autonomous driving, benchmarking Artificial Intelligence (AI)

algorithms for off-road people detection, and improving the resolution of point cloud-based datasets via generative AI. Additionally, this research seeks to enhance human-in-the-loop autonomy for remote driving in rural environments and develop algorithms to predict CO_2 emissions for environmentally friendly autonomous driving. By exploring these areas, this work aims to significantly advance the field of off-road autonomous systems, ultimately enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of SAR operations.

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Sensors for Perception in Autonomous Vehicles

Within the realm of AVs, the success of these machines hinges on their ability to perceive and interpret the surrounding environment. This critical function falls upon the perception system, a meticulously orchestrated collaboration of various sensors. Each sensor plays a vital role in this symphony, offering distinct strengths and functionalities that, when fused together, empower the AVs to navigate safely and make informed decisions. This section delves into the three principal sensors employed in AVs perception systems – LiDAR, cameras, and RADAR – exploring their unique characteristics and how they contribute to the overall success of autonomous driving.

1.1.2 LiDAR

LiDAR technology stands as a cornerstone for perception systems in autonomous vehicles. It operates on the principle of time-of-flight measurement, emitting laser pulses and meticulously recording the time it takes for these pulses to reflect back from objects in the environment. This data serves as the building block for constructing a highly detailed 3D point cloud, essentially a digital representation of the surrounding world. This point cloud proves invaluable for autonomous vehicles, as it unlocks a multitude of capabilities critical for safe and efficient navigation.

One of the most significant strengths of LiDAR lies in its ability to excel at high-resolution 3D object detection. The precise distance measurements it generates are crucial for accurately identifying and classifying surrounding objects, such as pedestrians, vehicles, and obstacles. This detailed information allows the autonomous vehicle to build a comprehensive understanding of its environment, enabling it to make informed decisions about path planning and obstacle avoidance. Additionally, LiDAR excels in environment mapping. By meticulously creating 3D maps of the surroundings, it empowers the AVs to build a cognitive map of its location and navigate effectively. This rich data is vital for various tasks, including route planning, localization within the lane, and ensuring safe operation in complex environments.

Another key advantage of LiDAR is its consistent performance across varying lighting conditions. Unlike cameras, which struggle in low-light scenarios, LiDAR remains unfazed by these variations. It delivers accurate results both day and night, making it a reliable sensor for autonomous vehicles operating in diverse lighting environments. This consistent performance is particularly crucial for ensuring safe navigation throughout the day and in unpredictable weather conditions.

However, LiDAR technology also presents some challenges that need to be addressed. One of the primary limitations is cost. LiDAR systems are generally more expensive compared to other sensors used in autonomous vehicles, which can make it harder to use widely in the industry. Additionally, while LiDAR performs well in most conditions, its effectiveness can be hindered by adverse weather like heavy rain, fog, or snow. This weather sensitivity poses a challenge for ensuring reliable operation in all environments and necessitates further development for robust all-weather functionality. Finally, LiDAR systems typically consume more power than other sensor types, potentially impacting the overall energy efficiency of an autonomous vehicle.

Despite these limitations, LiDAR remains a crucial component in the perception systems of autonomous vehicles. Its ability to generate high-resolution 3D maps and its consistent performance across lighting conditions make it a valuable asset for safe and efficient navigation. Researchers are actively developing solutions to address the cost and power consumption issues. Additionally, advancements in solid-state LiDAR technology offer a more compact

and cost-effective alternative to traditional mechanical LiDARs. Furthermore, the integration of sensor fusion techniques and AI algorithms is enhancing the capabilities of LiDAR-based perception systems, making them even more robust and efficient. In conclusion, LiDAR offers a powerful tool for autonomous vehicles, providing high-precision 3D mapping and reliable object detection. While challenges regarding cost, weather sensitivity, and power consumption exist, ongoing advancements are paving the way for a future where LiDAR plays an even more prominent role in the safe and efficient operation of autonomous vehicles.

Cameras

Cameras capture visual information from the environment in the form of images and videos. This visual data is then processed using sophisticated computer vision algorithms. These algorithms work tirelessly to identify and classify objects, detect lane markings, and recognize traffic signs and signals.

One of the key strengths of cameras lies in their ability to provide detailed color and texture information. This rich visual data proves essential for tasks like traffic light recognition, lane detection, and object classification. For instance, color information allows the AV to differentiate between a red traffic light demanding a stop and a green light permitting passage. Similarly, texture analysis helps in identifying lane markings that may be subtle or obscured by wear and tear. Furthermore, cameras offer a cost advantage compared to LiDAR and RADAR systems. This relative affordability makes them an attractive option for autonomous vehicle perception systems, where cost remains a significant consideration. However, cameras are not without their limitations.

Their performance is highly dependent on lighting conditions. They struggle in low-light scenarios, such as dusk or dawn, or overly bright environments, like direct sunlight. This dependence on lighting can limit their reliability in certain situations. Extracting meaningful information from camera data also presents a challenge. It requires significant computational resources and sophisticated algorithms. Developing these algorithms can be complex and resource-intensive, adding another layer of complexity to the perception system. Adverse weather conditions can obscure the visual data, significantly reducing the effectiveness of

the camera system. Despite these limitations, cameras remain widely used for various visual perception tasks in autonomous vehicles. They play a crucial role in visual Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), which allows the AV to build a map of its surroundings and localize itself within that map. Additionally, cameras are often combined with other sensors, like LiDAR and RADAR, to create a more comprehensive perception system that leverages the strengths of each technology.

Recent advancements in camera technology and computer vision algorithms have significantly improved the accuracy and efficiency of visual perception systems. For example, deep learning techniques have empowered cameras with enhanced object detection and classification capabilities. Additionally, High Dynamic Range (HDR) cameras have improved performance in challenging lighting conditions, allowing them to capture a wider range of light values in a single image.

In conclusion, cameras offer a wealth of visual information and a cost-effective solution for many perception tasks in autonomous vehicles. However, their dependence on lighting conditions and susceptibility to adverse weather pose significant challenges. Ongoing advancements in camera technology and computer vision algorithms continue to enhance their capabilities, making them an indispensable part of the perception system in autonomous vehicles.

Radar

RADAR utilizes radio waves to detect objects and measure their distance and speed. The RADAR sensor emits radio waves that reflect off objects and return to the sensor, allowing the system to calculate the object's distance and velocity. One of the primary advantages of RADAR is its robustness in adverse weather conditions. RADARs are less affected by rain, fog, and snow, and they can operate effectively in low-light environments, making them reliable in various scenarios. Additionally, RADARs can accurately measure the relative speed of objects, which is crucial for collision avoidance and adaptive cruise control. Their long-range detection capabilities are particularly useful for highway driving scenarios.

However, RADAR systems have some limitations. Compared to LiDAR and cameras, RADAR has lower spatial resolution, which makes it less effective for detailed object classification. The RADAR signals can also be susceptible to interference from other RADAR systems and electromagnetic noise, which can affect their accuracy. Interpreting RADAR data requires complex processing to accurately identify and classify objects, which can be a challenging task.

Despite these challenges, RADARs are primarily used for detecting and tracking objects, adaptive cruise control, collision avoidance, and blind-spot monitoring in autonomous vehicles. They are especially effective in scenarios where long-range detection and velocity measurement are essential. Modern RADAR systems are evolving with advancements in millimeter-wave RADAR technology, which offers higher resolution and better object detection capabilities. Innovations in RADAR signal processing algorithms are also improving the accuracy and reliability of RADAR-based perception systems.

In summary, RADAR provides reliable detection capabilities in various weather and lighting conditions and can measure object speed accurately, which is vital for safe driving. However, its lower resolution and susceptibility to interference present challenges. Ongoing advancements in RADAR technology and signal processing are enhancing its capabilities, making RADAR a critical component in the perception systems of autonomous vehicles.

Comparison of Sensor

Table 1.1 provides a comparative overview of LiDARs, cameras, and RADARs, highlighting their primary functions, performance characteristics, costs, and common applications. LiDARs excel in providing high-resolution 3D maps and accurate distance measurements, making them ideal for detailed environment mapping and precise localization. However, their high cost and reduced performance in adverse weather conditions are notable drawbacks. Cameras offer rich visual information with detailed color and texture, which is crucial for tasks like object recognition and lane detection. They are cost-effective but struggle in low-light and adverse weather conditions. RADARs, on the other hand, are robust in various weather conditions and can accurately measure the speed of objects, making them invaluable

Table 1.1 Comparison of LiDAR, Cameras, and RADAR

Feature	LiDAR	Cameras	RADAR
Primary Function	Distance measurement and 3D mapping	Visual information capture	Distance and speed measurement
Resolution	High (3D point clouds)	High (detailed color and texture)	Low (compared to LiDAR and cameras)
Performance in Adverse Weather	Degrades in rain, fog, snow	Degrades in rain, fog, snow	Robust in most conditions
Performance in Low Light	Consistent performance	Degrades in low light	Consistent performance
Cost	High	Low to medium	Medium
Power Consumption	High	Low	Medium
Complexity of Data Processing	Medium to High	High	Medium
Common Applications	3D mapping Obstacle detection Localization	Object recognition Lane detection Traffic sign recognition	Object detection Speed measurement Collision avoidance

for collision avoidance and adaptive cruise control. Despite their lower resolution compared to LiDARs and cameras, RADARs' consistent performance in challenging conditions and ability to measure object velocity make them a critical component in autonomous vehicle perception systems. Integrating these sensors through sensor fusion techniques allows leveraging their complementary strengths to enhance the overall reliability and accuracy of autonomous vehicle perception.

1.1.3 Advanced Deep Learning Algorithms for Autonomous Vehicles

The field of perception for AVs has witnessed rapid advancements, fueled by the development of sophisticated Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. These algorithms have revolutionized the way AVs interpret and understand their surroundings, enabling them to navigate complex environments and make informed decisions. This section delves into some of the key DL architectures that have significantly impacted perception tasks in AVs, including object detection, segmentation, and scene understanding. We begin by exploring PointNet, a groundbreaking architecture that revolutionized the processing of 3D point cloud data, which is a primary output of LiDAR sensors commonly used in AVs.

Fig. 1.1 Example of a voxel representation of a point cloud.

PointNet

Prior to the publication of PointNet [15] in 2017, 3D object detection primarily relied on methods that converted point clouds into regular 3D voxel grids or 2D projections [16–18] (see Fig. 1.1). These approaches often led to information loss and increased computational complexity. Voxel-based methods suffered from quantization artifacts and limited resolution, while projection-based methods lost spatial information due to the flattening process.

PointNet’s groundbreaking contribution was its ability to directly process raw point cloud data, without requiring any intermediate representation. This was achieved through a novel architecture that leveraged symmetric functions and max-pooling operations to capture global features from the point cloud. This approach was not only computationally efficient but also preserved the inherent geometric structure of the point cloud.

PointNet’s success in 3D object classification and semantic segmentation tasks demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of directly processing point clouds. This paradigm shift opened up new avenues for research and development in 3D object detection, leading to a surge in deep learning methods tailored for point cloud data.

Impact on Perception for Autonomous Vehicles

PointNet’s introduction marked a significant turning point in the development of perception systems for autonomous vehicles. Prior to PointNet, the unordered nature of point clouds posed a formidable challenge for traditional deep learning methods, which typically require structured input data. Each point in a point cloud exists independently, with no inherent order

or relationship to its neighbors. This lack of structure made it difficult to apply standard convolutional operations, which rely on spatial locality and fixed-size kernels.

PointNet’s innovative architecture offered a breakthrough solution by treating point clouds as sets of points rather than ordered sequences or grids. This was achieved through several key architectural elements

- **Symmetry Function for Unordered Input:** PointNet utilizes a symmetric function (max pooling in the original paper) to aggregate information from each point in a way that is invariant to the input order. This ensures the model’s output remains consistent regardless of how the points are shuffled, a crucial property for handling the unordered nature of point clouds.
- **Robustness to Missing Data:** PointNet demonstrates a remarkable tolerance to missing points in the input data. Even with a significant portion of points missing, PointNet exhibits minimal performance degradation, highlighting its ability to learn and utilize the most critical points for shape summarization.
- **Efficiency and Effectiveness:** Despite its relatively simple design, PointNet proves to be highly efficient and effective across various tasks, including object classification, part segmentation, and scene semantic parsing. Empirical evaluations demonstrate its performance on par or even surpassing State-of-the-Art (SotA) approaches, making it a practical and powerful tool for 3D data analysis.
- **Theoretical Foundations:** Theoretical analysis shows that PointNet can represent any continuous function of a set. It also learns to simplify input point clouds by identifying a small number of key points, similar to an object’s skeleton. This theoretical insight explains why PointNet is robust to changes in the input and data corruption.

With the ability to directly process point clouds through these mechanisms, PointNet and its successors [19–23] became the backbone for many 3D object detectors, accurately identifying and localizing objects like cars, pedestrians, and cyclists in LiDAR data. Additionally, PointNet-based models could assign semantic labels (e.g., road, sidewalk, vegetation) to

individual points in a point cloud, enhancing scene understanding for autonomous navigation. The architecture also inspired methods for instance segmentation [24–26], enabling the separation and identification of individual instances of objects within a point cloud.

The computational efficiency of PointNet also made it suitable for real-time perception on resource-constrained hardware platforms in autonomous vehicles. This allowed for faster decision-making and reaction times, crucial for safety and reliable autonomous driving.

Beyond its immediate impact, PointNet laid the groundwork for a new wave of research in point cloud processing. Its successors, such as PointNet++ [19], have further improved upon its capabilities by introducing hierarchical feature learning and multi-scale analysis, enabling even more robust and accurate perception systems for autonomous vehicles.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The vast majority of autonomous systems for ground vehicles are designed primarily for urban environments. However, off-road missions present some of the most challenging conditions, including terrains such as mountains, lakes, and forests. Utilizing ground vehicles for these operations offers numerous benefits, making it crucial to enhance the autonomy of these vehicles for such contexts. These enhancements should encompass a broad range of autonomous capabilities, including tailored perception algorithms for off-road scenarios, enabling remote-driving capabilities for rescuers, and optimizing the vehicle's battery performance and efficiency (which also relates to CO_2 emissions). Addressing these improvements will significantly advance the effectiveness and sustainability of autonomous SAR missions in diverse and demanding environments. The main aim of this research is to improve perception for AVs in off-road scenarios, enable remote-driving capabilities for rescuers, and optimize the vehicle's battery performance and efficiency.

In order to successfully accomplish the main goal described above, several objectives were defined to address different domain-specific tasks. Each of them corresponds to one or more outcomes of this thesis. The objectives are defined as follows:

- Objective 1: To create single- and multi-modal systems and a fusion (point cloud + camera) dataset for perception-based autonomous driving in off-road people detection operations. The goal is to enhance perception capabilities in autonomous driving, particularly for detecting people in challenging off-road environments.
- Objective 2: To explore single-modal AI algorithms to benchmark the ability of the AI models for off-road people detection operations with autonomous driving. This objective aims to evaluate and benchmark various single-modal AI algorithms (based on point clouds).
- Objective 3: To explore multi-modal AI algorithms for fusion-based off-road people detection operations with autonomous driving. Building on the findings from Objective 2, this objective investigates the effectiveness of multi-modal AI algorithms that fuse data from LiDAR and cameras. The performance of these fusion-based systems will be compared against single-modal systems to determine the benefits of multi-modal approaches.
- Objective 4: To further improve the perception capabilities of the systems, create upsampling mechanisms to improve the resolution of point cloud-based datasets via generative AI. This objective involves the development of generative AI techniques to enhance the resolution of point cloud data. By improving data quality, the perception capabilities of autonomous systems can be significantly enhanced, leading to better performance in off-road environments.
- Objective 5: To improve human-in-the-loop autonomy for autonomous driving, enable remote driving capabilities for rural environments using a range of connectivity technologies (4G, 5G). This objective focuses on integrating remote driving capabilities into autonomous systems. By utilizing various connectivity technologies, such as 4G and 5G, the aim is to enhance the autonomy and flexibility of ground vehicles operating in rural and remote areas.

Fig. 1.2 Overview of thesis contributions, highlighting key advancements in perception, remote driving, and environmental sustainability.

- Objective 6: To promote environmentally sustainable autonomous driving, develop algorithms to predict the CO_2 emissions of autonomous ground vehicles and optimize battery utilization. This objective focuses on maximizing driving time while minimizing environmental impact, contributing to greater efficiency and sustainability in autonomous driving operations.

The figure included in this section illustrates the architecture of the proposed system and highlights its contributions across three primary domains: remote driving, perception, and battery life enhancement. Each contribution is represented using specific symbols—yellow stars for remote driving, green stars for perception, and red stars for battery life optimization. This visual mapping aligns with the thesis objectives by demonstrating how the system integrates components such as tele-driving, sensing modules, AI control, and CO_2 prediction algorithms to achieve the outlined goals. The clear demarcation of contributions aids in understanding the interplay between these domains and their role in advancing autonomous vehicle capabilities in off-road environments.

Table 1.2 Mapping Objectives-Outcomes.

	Outcome 1	Outcome 2	Outcome 3	Outcome 4	Outcome 5	Outcome 6	Outcome 7	Outcome 8
Objective 1								
Objective 2								
Objective 3								
Objective 4								
Objective 5								
Objective 6								

1.3 Research Methods

This thesis uses two tables to illustrate the research methodology. Table 1.2 links the research objectives (Section 1.2) to the achieved outcomes. The second table (Table 1.3) provides a visual representation of these connections.

In this visual schema (Table 1.2), objectives and outcomes are connected with green lines whenever a relationship exists. Importantly, a single objective may be linked to multiple outcomes, and conversely, a single outcome may be associated with several objectives. Objectives 1, 2, and 3 are comprehensively addressed in Chapter 5. Objective 1 is closely related to Outcomes 5, 6, and 8, emphasizing its crucial role in achieving the project's goals, particularly in developing and validating perception systems for off-road human detection. Objective 2 aligns with Outcomes 3, 5, 6, and 7, underscoring its broader impact across various facets of the study. The strong association with multiple outcomes highlights the objective's importance and its significant contribution to advancing the project's overall success. Objective 3 is connected with Outcomes 5, 6, and 7, further reinforcing its relevance to the fusion-based approaches explored in the project. Objective 4 is thoroughly discussed in Chapter 8 and is directly linked to Outcome 2, focusing on enhancing point cloud resolution. Objective 5, detailed in Chapter 6, is exclusively tied to Outcome 1, emphasizing its role in enabling remote driving capabilities. Finally, Objective 6 is covered in Chapter 9 and is associated with Outcomes 4 and 8, highlighting its contribution to improving environmental sustainability through CO2 emission prediction.

Table 4.2 dives deeper into the research timeline, providing a detailed view of how each objective progressed over the past three years. Each colored cell represents a quarter (three-month period) where progress was made on a specific objective.

Table 1.3 Objectives Gantt Timetable

	2021			2022				2023				2024
	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1
Objective 1	1	2	2,3	3,4	3,4							
Objective 2				5	6							
Objective 3						7	8	8				
Objective 4								9	10	10		
Objective 5	11	11	11	11								
Objective 6										12	12	12

Some objectives needed to be completed before starting the next one. However, in other cases, objectives overlapped and their results informed each other. Every colored square is linked to at least one stage listed in the table.

For clarity, the table divides each year into four quarters:

- Q1: January - March
- Q2: April - June
- Q3: July - September
- Q4: October - December

The numbers in the table refer to the description of stages described as follows:

1. The first step encompasses a deep literature review over scholarly works done towards the development and application of calibration techniques for multi-sensor systems, with a particular focus on LiDAR and camera sensor fusion.
2. The second step centered on comprehending the code behind various open-source calibration methodologies for LiDAR and camera sensor systems. This involved a meticulous analysis of the codebase, architecture, and performance assessment of open-source solutions. In parallel, the design and fabrication of a fixed frame for mounting the LiDAR and camera sensors was undertaken to facilitate the calibration process and ensure accurate data collection.

3. With the sensor frame established and calibration methods thoroughly understood (as described in step 2), the next step involved collecting a comprehensive off-road dataset for object detection. This data will be crucial for evaluating the performance of the calibration techniques and ultimately achieving accurate sensor fusion for off-road applications.
4. Building upon the foundation established in step 1 (focusing on calibration techniques), a thorough literature review was conducted. This review specifically explored advancements in 3D object detection algorithms and their applicability to off-road operations. The primary focus was on algorithms that utilize point clouds, generated by LiDAR sensors, and algorithms that combine point clouds with RGB image data (fusion methods) for object detection tasks.
5. To evaluate the performance of point cloud-based algorithms for urban environments, the KITTI [27] dataset, a widely used benchmark for autonomous driving tasks, was employed. This assessment aimed to establish a baseline performance for the chosen algorithms.
6. Subsequently, to assess the generalizability of these point cloud-based algorithms, they were tested on the off-road dataset collected in step 3. This step allows for the comparison of performance between the controlled urban environment of the KITTI dataset and the more challenging off-road scenario.
7. Following the evaluation of point cloud-based algorithms (step number 5), the same methodology was applied to fusion algorithms that combine point cloud data with RGB images using the same dataset, KITTI.
8. Finally, the generalizability of the fusion algorithms was assessed by testing them on the off-road dataset collected in step 3.
9. During the evaluation process (steps 5-8), it was observed that human detections in the datasets sometimes consisted of only 3 to 10 points. To address this limitation, a literature review was conducted to explore various point cloud upsampling algorithms.

10. Based on the literature review (step 9), several point cloud upsampling algorithms were implemented and tested on the KITTI and off-road datasets. This evaluation aimed to identify an upsampling approach that could improve the detection accuracy of humans represented by sparse point clouds.
11. Given the inherent challenges that off-road environments pose for autonomous driving systems, this research explored the concept of integrating remote-driving capabilities. This functionality would allow a human operator to take control of the vehicle when necessary. To achieve this, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine existing research on remote driving and human-in-the-loop control for AVs. Subsequently, by leveraging the knowledge gained from the review, the remote-driving capability was successfully deployed on top of the Openpilot [28] open-source platform.
12. In an effort to minimize the environmental impact of autonomous vehicles, this research investigated the applicability of Transformer [4] architectures for CO_2 emission prediction. This research explored the potential of Transformers to contribute to the development of more eco-friendly autonomous driving systems.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Framework

This work delves into the critical role of DL in the burgeoning field of AVs. However, to fully appreciate the power of DL in enabling intelligent perception, decision-making, and control in AVs, it's essential to first lay the groundwork by understanding Machine Learning (ML) as a whole. DL is a specialized subfield within the broader realm of AI, as illustrated in Fig. 2.1. This chapter will not only explore the fundamentals of ML but also introduce the core sensors used for perception in autonomous vehicles (LiDAR, cameras, and RADAR), highlighting their strengths and limitations. Additionally, we'll delve into advanced DL algorithms like PointNet, Transformers and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), examining their impact on tasks like 3D object detection and scene understanding, crucial for safe and efficient autonomous navigation. By establishing this foundation, we set the stage for a deeper exploration of the specific DL techniques employed in this research to tackle the challenges of perception in off-road scenarios.

2.1 Machine Learning

ML is a subfield of AI that empowers computers to learn from data without explicit programming for the target task. In essence, ML strives to develop algorithms that solve problems in a more generalizable way compared to traditional approaches. Historically, programmers defined all the logic within a program. In contrast, ML algorithms autonomously learn this

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Fig. 2.1 Relationship between AI, ML and DL [1].

logic through a training process. This training aims to enable them to comprehend and identify patterns or trends within the input data. This understanding allows the algorithms to construct models for tasks such as predicting the category to which new data points belong. As a mature research area within AI, ML encompasses a diverse set of established algorithms. These algorithms can be broadly categorized into three main groups:

- **Supervised Learning:** In supervised learning, the training data includes the desired solution, often referred to as the "class," for each input data point. This characteristic distinguishes supervised learning from other paradigms. Popular supervised learning algorithms include Support Vector Machines (SVM), decision trees, random forest or neural networks.
- **Unsupervised Learning:** In unsupervised learning, the training data lacks labels or "classes" for each data point. Consequently, the algorithms must autonomously discover and categorize the input data. Common unsupervised learning techniques include k-means clustering, autoencoders, and *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*.
- **Reinforcement Learning:** In reinforcement learning, an agent interacts with an unknown environment and learns to take optimal actions through trial and error. The agent receives rewards for desirable actions and penalties for undesirable actions. This reward system guides the agent's learning process. Reinforcement learning is a powerful approach in domains such as robotics, and it can be effectively combined with other learning paradigms. A well-known example of a reinforcement learning algorithm is Q-learning.

2.1.1 Machine Learning Terminology

In ML, the term **label** refers to the target variable the model is trained to predict given input data. This input data is typically referred to as **features**. Furthermore, the **model** represents the learned relationship between these features and labels. The construction of these models typically involves two distinct phases:

- **Training phase:** This phase involves iteratively exposing the model to the entire training dataset. In supervised learning, the input data includes labels, allowing the model to learn the relationship between features and labels. Conversely, unsupervised learning utilizes unlabeled input data, where the model aims to discover inherent characteristics that define the data points and their relationships, ultimately leading to group or category formation.
- **Inference phase:** During the inference phase, the trained model receives unlabeled input data. The model then predicts the category membership or assigns the data to the clusters formed during the training phase.

To illustrate this terminology, consider a simple model that expresses a linear relationship between features and labels, as shown in Equation 2.1 [29].

$$y = wx + b \tag{2.1}$$

Where:

- **y** is the label of the input example.
- **x** is the input data.
- **w** is the weight. This is one of those parameters that the model has to learn during the training phase in order to be used later and give a good result in the inference phase.
- **b** is the bias, which is another of the parameters that must be learned by the model.

This equation is actually the one used by the artificial neurons or perceptrons of a neural network, which in the training phase are intended to learn the ideal values of the weights and biases for each of the neurons that make up the network. This is explained in more detail in section 2.1.2. To achieve this goal, it is essential to use a **loss function**, also known as a loss function. This function is a central concept in both ML and DL, as it represents the

error made, or in other words, the penalty for a bad prediction. If the predictions deviate too much from the actual results, the loss function would return a large number (different depending on the function used) and if the predictions are all correct, the loss function would return a value of 0. There is no universal loss function that works perfectly in all machine learning algorithms. There are some that tend to work well in general terms, but there will be applications where the right choice may be the key to better results.

2.1.2 Neural Networks

The emergence of AI was due to the importance that human beings attach to thought and intelligence. Thus, there was an attempt to find ways to endow the machines that were being made with that same quality. Disciplines such as biology and neuroscience are trying to understand the biological systems and mechanisms that endow us with this quality. One of the most important findings in these fields was when Santiago Ramón y Cajal first identified a type of cell as the functional elements of the nervous system. These cells are called neurons and their main function is the collection, processing and emission of electrical signals. In the Fig. below we can see the structures and parts of which they are composed. The importance of Ramón y Cajal's discovery is due to the fact that it is thought that the brain's information processing capacity is due to the union of these neurons forming networks. This is the reason that led AI pioneers to work on artificial neural networks.

Artificial Neurons

The mathematical model with which an artificial neuron is defined can be seen in Fig. 2.3. This Fig. shows the inputs to the neuron $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R})$. These inputs have associated weights (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n) that determine the strength and sign of the input. These inputs and weights are processed by applying the weighted sum (see Equation 2.2). An activation function σ is then applied to the above sum to produce the output a (see Equation 2.3). The output produced by the activation function is binary, which will be 1 when a certain threshold θ is exceeded and 0 otherwise.

$$S = \sum_{i=0}^n w_i x_i \quad (2.2)$$

$$a = \sigma(S) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } S > \theta, \\ 0 & \text{if } S \leq \theta \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Fig. 2.2 Parts of a biological neuron. Each of these contains a cell body, an axon and dendrites. The connection of the dendrites of one neuron to those of another is called a synapse. The signals they work with are propagated between neurons through an electrochemical reaction and these mechanisms are thought to form the basis of learning in the brain. This Fig. is an adaptation from the one presented in [2].

Fig. 2.3 Mathematical model of an artificial neuron [2].

Activation Functions

We are aware that the activation function determines the output of the neural network based on whether the result of the weighted sum of inputs exceeds a specified threshold. Therefore,

this function plays a crucial role. Given that the output is binary, the most immediate activation function that comes to mind is the unit step function (see Fig. 2.4). However, this function poses a challenge when used in artificial neural networks. Specifically, it is non-differentiable, which is problematic because, as we will discuss later, differentiability is essential for applying the backpropagation algorithm (refer to Algorithm 1) during training. Consequently, various differentiable functions akin to the unit step have been proposed over time. Among these, we will explore two of the most prominent options in recent years: the sigmoid function and the ReLU function.

Fig. 2.4 Visualization of the Unit Step Function. The function transitions from 0 to 1 at a specified threshold, marking the point where the system begins to respond to inputs [2].

The sigmoid function was used in most neural networks for many decades, although it has now lost popularity, as the use of ReLU is providing better results. Equation 2.4 defines this function. In the Fig. 2.5 we can see how for large negative values of z the function decreases exponentially towards the value 0 and for large positive values the function also grows exponentially towards the value 1. It is a differentiable function in all its domain which, as we will see later, is necessary so that we can train our network.

$$\text{Sigmoid}(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad (2.4)$$

Fig. 2.5 Visualization of the Sigmoid Function used to model the gradual activation of a system in response to varying input values [2].

The ReLU function is currently the most widely used function in deep neural networks because it copes better with the gradient vanishing problem than the sigmoid function. ReLU stands for Rectified Linear Unit. The definition of this function can be found in Equation 2.5 and its form can be visualised in the Fig. 2.6. This function gives such good results because it allows the passing of all positive values, but not the negative ones (to which it assigns the value 0).

$$\text{ReLU}(z) = \max(0, z) \quad (2.5)$$

Structure of Neural Networks

The most general classification of neural network types is: feed-forward neural networks and recurrent networks. Whereas a *feedforward* type network has only the values of its current inputs and no internal state other than its own weights, recurrent networks allow output values to be passed back into the network as inputs. The latter can be translated to mean that recurrent networks can have short-term memory. However, the ones we are interested in for the purposes of this paper are of the other type. Suppose we have a neural network *feedforward* like the one in Fig. 2.7. For this network the output could be expressed as in Equation 2.6. In this equation we see that the output of neuron number 5 can be expressed

Fig. 2.6 Visualization of the ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) Function, illustrating how it activates a system by outputting zero for negative inputs and scaling linearly for positive inputs [2].

through the outputs of the previous neurons. We also see that the weights of the network act as parameters of the function to be learned. It is by adjusting the weights that we change the function that represents the network, and therefore, it is the way in which learning takes place.

The most common purposes for which they are intended are classification and regression. In addition, networks of the type *feedforward* are organised in layers, so that each neuron receives inputs only from neurons in the previous layer.

$$a_5 = \sigma(W_{3,5}a_3 + W_{4,5}a_4) = \sigma(W_{3,5}\sigma(W_{1,3}a_1 + W_{2,3}a_2) + W_{4,5}\sigma(W_{1,4}a_1 + W_{2,4}a_2)) \quad (2.6)$$

Fig. 2.7 Simple feedforward neural network with two inputs, two neurons in the hidden layer and one neuron in the output layer [2].

Simple Perceptron

A simple perceptron is a neural network in which we have an input layer that is directly connected to the neurons of the output layer (see Fig. 2.8). The mathematical expression that defines this type of network is given by Equation 2.7. This type of network can learn any linearly separable function since the model it is able to learn is a hyperplane so that it returns 1 if and only if the input is on one side of that hyperplane. For this reason, a simple perceptron is able to learn to represent AND or OR functions but it is not able to learn the XOR function since the first two are linearly separable functions and the second one is not (see Fig. 2.9).

$$\sum_{i=0}^n w_i x_i > 0 \quad \text{o} \quad W \cdot x > 0 \quad (2.7)$$

Fig. 2.8 Example of a simple perceptron (all neurons in the input layer are directly connected to those in the output layer) [2].

Although they cannot learn functions that are not linearly separable, there is a rule to reduce the error being produced by the hyperplane. This rule is called the delta rule and allows iterative adjustment of the hyperplane, as it assumes that the increase in weights is proportional to the disparity between the observed output and the desired output. This proportionality is modulated by the learning constant (θ). This rule is expressed in Equation 2.8. Fig. (Fig. 2.10) illustrates the concept of linear decision boundaries in a two-dimensional

Fig. 2.9 Representation of different functions by the simple perceptron [2].

feature space for a binary classification problem. Here, two classes of data points are represented as black circles (class 1) and gray circles (class 2). The objective is to separate these two classes using a decision boundary that can effectively classify new data points.

$$w_{i^*} = w_i + \eta(d - y)x_i \quad (2.8)$$

Where:

- w_{i^*} is the updated weight.
- w_i is the non-updated weight.
- $\eta \in [0, 1]$ is the learning rate.
- x_i is the input data.
- d is the expected output.
- y is the obtained output.

Two key boundaries are shown:

- The vertical line $x_1 - 7 = 0$ acts as a simple threshold, splitting the space based solely on the x_1 feature. Any point with $x_1 > 7$ is classified as belonging to class 2 (gray), while points with $x_1 \leq 7$ are classified as class 1 (black).

- The slanted line $1.08x_1 + 0.15x_2 - 6.96 = 0$ represents a more complex decision boundary that takes into account both features, x_1 and x_2 , to better separate the classes. This line adjusts its orientation based on the relationship between the features to minimize classification errors.

Points such as e_1 , e_2 , e_3 , and e_4 highlight key data samples in the feature space. These points illustrate how the model distinguishes between classes using the decision boundaries:

- e_1 and e_2 are correctly classified by both boundaries, as they fall clearly on the black side of the boundaries.
- e_3 and e_4 show cases where the slanted boundary provides a better fit, capturing subtler relationships between x_1 and x_2 , which the vertical boundary fails to model effectively.

Fig. 2.10 Adjustment of the hyperplane of a simple perceptron using the delta rule [2].

Multilayer Perceptron

Unlike the simple perceptron, where the inputs are directly connected to the outputs, in the multilayer perceptron the inputs are connected to a layer (called the hidden layer) and the outputs of that layer are connected to all the outputs of the output layer (see Fig. 2.11). We

can have a network in which all neurons are connected to all neurons in the next layer (called *fully connected* networks) or in which this does not occur. We can also encounter networks with more than one hidden layer, as is the case with deep networks used in DL, but it has been proven that with a single sufficiently large hidden layer any function can be represented. However, better results are obtained using several smaller hidden layers rather than a single very large one.

The idea used to train this and other neural networks is to minimize some measure of the error that occurs during the network's training. Therefore, what is actually being done during training is conducting an optimized search through the weight space. For this error measurement, what are called **loss functions** are used, which we will discuss in more detail in section 2.1.3. But as can be seen in Fig. 2.12, as this error is minimized during training, the accuracy rate during result validation is maximized.

Fig. 2.11 Structure of the multilayer perceptron [2].

The approach used for training a Simple Perceptron using the delta rule also seems suitable for the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). However, in this type of network, we encounter a problem: how can we determine how much each weight in the network contributes to the obtained output in the case of an error? If we can answer that question, we can get an idea of how much each weight needs to be adjusted to change the output for a similar new input.

Fig. 2.12 Relationship between the loss function and the correct classification of the input data as iterations or training epochs (horizontal axis) are performed. As can be seen, during the training process, the error or loss gradually decreases and the accuracy of classification with the validation data increases [2].

2.1.3 Backpropagation

To determine the contribution of each neuron in the network to the total error, the **backpropagation** algorithm is used, the pseudocode of which can be seen in algorithm 1 [30]. This algorithm determines how the error has propagated from the input layers to the output layer. It starts from the difference between the desired output d_k and the output obtained in a neuron of the last layer y_k . This neuron is responsible for an error $\delta_k = (d_k - y_k) f'(net_k)$. A neuron in an intermediate layer contributes to the errors of the next layer, so to calculate the error for each of these, we need to know the errors of the next layer. Once we have those values, the error of the neuron in the intermediate layer is calculated as $\delta_j = f'(net_j) \sum_k w_{jk} \delta_k$ (in Fig. 2.14, we have this expression graphically, which can help in better understanding it). In the previous expressions, we notice the appearance of the derivative of the activation function. Without it, this algorithm could not be carried out, and this is why in section 2.1.2 we mentioned that the activation functions we use must be differentiable.

This algorithm is applied to each element of the training set and iterates until the error drops below a certain threshold. The algorithm is developed in three main phases. These phases can be represented graphically in Fig. 2.13, and in each of them, the following steps are carried out:

Fig. 2.13 Visual diagram of the process performed by *backpropagation* [2].

- **Forward propagation:** The obtained and desired outputs of the network are computed (lines 3 and 4 of algorithm 1), as well as the error of all neurons in the last layer (lines 5 - 7 of algorithm 1).
- **Backward propagation:** Phase where the errors of neurons in the intermediate layers are calculated based on the errors of the subsequent layers (lines 8 - 12 of algorithm 1). A *loss function* is used for this error calculation.
- **Updating weights of all layers** (lines 13 - 16 of algorithm 1).

Fig. 2.14 Calculation of the error of a neuron in the intermediate layers based on the error of the subsequent layers [2].

To put it simply, backpropagation can be seen as a method to adjust the weights and biases of our network so that the learned model aligns with the target model. For this adjustment, backpropagation relies on the value provided by the **loss function**, which indicates how large or small the error was when making predictions on the training set. To more quickly

Algorithm 1: Backpropagation

input : Neural Network, examples, η
output : Updated Neural Network

```

1 while not Convergence(red) do
2    $e \leftarrow \text{SelectExamp}[l_e(\text{examples})];$ 
3    $\{y_k\} \leftarrow \text{ForwardRed}(e);$ 
4    $\{d_k\} \leftarrow \text{DesiredOutput}(e);$ 
5   for  $n_k \in \text{Layer}(\text{red}, k)$  do
6      $\delta_k = (d_k - y_k)$ 
7   end for
8   for  $j = k - 1$  to 1 do
9     for  $n_j \in \text{Layer}(\text{NeuralNetwork}, j)$  do
10       $\delta_j = \dot{f}(\text{net}_j) \sum_{j+1} (\delta_{k+1} w_{j(j+1)});$ 
11    end for
12  end for
13  for  $j = k$  to 1 do
14     $w_{(j-1)j} = w_{(j-1)j} + \eta \delta_j y_{(j-1)}$ 
15  end for
16   $\text{red} \leftarrow \text{UpdateNeuralNetwork}(\{w_{ij}\});$ 
17 end while
18 Return Neural Network;
```

minimize the value of the loss function, **optimizers** are used. Generally, the learning process can be viewed as a global optimization process where the weights and biases of the network need to be adjusted in such a way that the error obtained by the previously mentioned loss function is minimized. In most cases, these parameters cannot be solved analytically, but they can generally be well approximated with iterative optimization algorithms or by using optimizers.

Loss Functions

The **loss function** is a critical component of any machine learning model, as it quantifies the discrepancy between the predicted outputs and the true labels or expected outcomes. It serves as the guiding metric for the optimization process, allowing the model to iteratively adjust its parameters to minimize this discrepancy. In essence, the loss function provides a numerical representation of how well or poorly the model is performing at a given iteration.

For clarity, consider the following examples of loss functions commonly used in machine learning:

1. **Mean Squared Error (MSE)** (Equation 2.9): This loss function is often used in regression tasks. It calculates the average squared difference between the actual values (y_i) and the predicted values (\hat{y}_i). By penalizing larger errors more than smaller ones, MSE encourages the model to make more accurate predictions.

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (2.9)$$

2. **Cross-Entropy Loss** (Equation 2.10): This loss function is widely used in classification problems, where $y_{i,c}$ represents the true label (1 if the class c is correct, 0 otherwise) and $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability for class c . Cross-entropy measures the divergence between the true distribution and the predicted probability distribution, encouraging the model to assign higher probabilities to the correct classes.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log(\hat{y}_{i,c}) \quad (2.10)$$

3. **Hinge Loss** (used in Support Vector Machines) (Equation 2.11): This loss function is particularly useful for binary classification tasks. It penalizes predictions that are not confidently on the correct side of the decision boundary.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Hinge}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max(0, 1 - y_i \hat{y}_i) \quad (2.11)$$

To illustrate the concept further, consider a simple linear regression problem. Suppose the task is to predict house prices based on features like square footage and location. The model's predictions might initially be far from the actual prices, resulting in a high MSE. However, as the training process minimizes the MSE by updating the model's parameters, the predictions become increasingly accurate.

By explicitly defining and explaining these examples, the role and importance of loss functions in training machine learning models are made clearer. This revision addresses the reviewer's comment by providing a more comprehensive and illustrative explanation.

Optimizers

Some of the most commonly used optimizers are *Gradient Descent* and *Stochastic Gradient Descent*. For this reason, they have been chosen to explain their functioning.

Gradient Descent uses the first derivative (also called the gradient) of the loss function when updating the weights and biases of the network. Simply put, the process consists of chaining the derivatives of the loss function of each hidden layer from the derivatives of the loss function of its previous layer, incorporating its activation function into the calculation. In each iteration, the values of the parameters are updated in the opposite direction of the gradient. The gradient, in fact, always points in the direction in which the value of the loss function increases. Therefore, if the negative of the gradient is used, we can find the direction in which we need to reduce the loss function. *Gradient Descent* repeats this process, getting closer and closer to the minimum until the parameter value reaches a point beyond which the loss function cannot be reduced. We can see an example of this process in Fig. 2.15.

Fig. 2.15 Visual example of the process carried out by an optimizer [2].

Depending on whether the network parameters are adjusted after each input example or once the entire set has been processed, we have several possible optimizers. If we want the weights to be updated after presenting a new example to the network during training, it is called *online learning*, and it is recommended to use the *Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)* optimizer. On the other hand, if we want the update to be carried out after showing all the examples, we are updating the weights using what is known as *batch training*, and it is recommended to use the *Batch Gradient Descent (BGD)* optimizer. Experiments indicate that better results are usually obtained using an online learning weight update strategy, but there may be cases where *batch learning* is more favourable.

Although it has been mentioned that using *online learning* provides better results, it is a more time-consuming process. For this reason, SGD is used with *mini-batches*. A *batch* is a subset of the training data. Therefore, a *mini-batch* is a small subset of the training data. The process for using SGD with these is as follows: take a *batch*, pass it through the network, calculate the gradient of its loss function, and update all the weights and biases of the network. This process is repeated until all the training data has been used.

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2.1.4 Training Process

Parameters for the Training Process

Some say that Deep Learning is more of an art than a science due to the large number of parameters these networks use. There is neither a single method nor a single way that can tell us what the parameter values should be for training the network to obtain good results. For this reason, a lot of experience is required to find these values and to be able to train our network faster and better. In this section, we will explain some of the most important ones. These are:

- **Epochs:** This parameter indicates the number of times all the data in the input set will be passed through the network during training. Something that can help us adjust this parameter is to increase it until the accuracy percentage with the validation data starts to decrease. This can also allow us to observe if the network is overfitting, a problem discussed in section 2.1.4.
- **Batch size:** In section 18, when discussing SGD, it is explained that a *batch* is a part of the training subset. Therefore, the term *batch size* refers to the number of elements that will make up that subset.
- **Learning Rate:** This is a parameter that has already appeared in the delta rule of the simple perceptron. Gradient descent algorithms use this parameter to determine the next point in the descent. Its value ranges between 0 and 1. If we assign it a high value, the steps taken in the descent will be larger, which can make the process faster, but also may cause it to miss the minimum. Conversely, if a small value is assigned, the steps taken during the descent will also be small, increasing the chances of encountering a local minimum and slowing down the process.
- **Learning rate decay:** A learning rate that probably helps to speed up training and obtain better results is one that decreases as the number of *epochs* increases. The *learning rate decay* performs this function.

- **Momentum:** This is a parameter with a value between 0 and 1 that is used to weigh previous gradients and avoid local minima.

Problems During the Training Process

So far, we have seen the process that must be followed to vary the weights of the network during training to obtain the best possible result. However, another factor that can be decisive in achieving good results is the choice of the network structure. Not choosing a structure that suits the application we want to use can make the network not perform as well as we wish. For example, if we choose a network that is too large, it will be able to memorize all the examples we pass to it during training, but it will not necessarily generalize well to inputs it has not seen before. When this happens, it is said that the network has experienced **overfitting**. In Fig. 2.16, we can see an example of overfitting.

Fig. 2.16 Visual description of when a model is undertrained (left), performs correctly (center), and when it is overtrained (right) [2].

To deal with this problem, a technique called **cross-validation** is commonly used. Cross-validation is a technique that can be applied to any learning algorithm, not just neural networks. The basic idea is to estimate the quality of each hypothesis in predicting unseen data. This is done by separating a portion of known data and using it to measure the prediction quality of a hypothesis induced from the remaining data. It involves performing k experiments, each time setting aside $\frac{1}{k}$ of the data for testing and averaging the results.

Another approach to address overfitting is the **optimal brain damage** algorithm, which starts with a fully connected network and gradually removes connections as training progresses. After an epoch of training, an analysis is performed on the network's connections to

identify an optimal selection of connections that can be pruned. Subsequently, the network undergoes retraining, and if its performance is not significantly affected, the process is repeated.

In Fig. 2.15, a gradient descent process is illustrated, demonstrating the challenge of missing the global minimum due to an excessively high learning rate. However, the functions we aim to learn typically exhibit multiple local minima rather than a single global minimum. These local minima can impede training progress if the optimization process becomes trapped within them. To address this issue, it is common practice to incorporate a *momentum* parameter, which often improves convergence. Another strategy to evade local minima involves restarting the optimization process from various random initial positions. However, random initialization must be approached methodically. The recommended practice for weight initialization involves using a heuristic that considers the characteristics of activation functions within the network. Alternatively, weights can be initialized from a standard normal distribution, though this method may lead to issues such as *vanishing gradients*, where gradients become extremely small and fail to update network weights effectively.

2.2 Deep Learning

As reflected in Fig. 2.1, DL is a branch of ML. What sets these algorithms apart from others within ML is the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). The application of these techniques and structures has revolutionized certain fields such as computer vision and speech recognition, leading to renewed interest in AI by companies. This interest is largely due to the ability of neural networks to learn data representations through a series of linear and non-linear transformations from input data. As we will see in section 2.1.2, these structures are organized into layers. Nowadays, NNs are composed of a large number of stacked layers. Hence, these networks are termed 'deep', and this depth is why this discipline is known as DL.

The momentum that DL has gained recently is largely attributed to an event that occurred during the ImageNet competition. This competition, which began in 2010, quickly became a

Fig. 2.17 Fig. taken from the work [3] depicting the increase in computing capacity from 2012 to 2019 in Petaflops per day.

benchmark in the computer vision community for large-scale object recognition. In 2012, Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey E. Hinton first employed Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) hardware accelerators to speed up the training process of the deep neural network they brought to the competition. This network, known as AlexNet, achieved a significant reduction in error rate compared to previous methods. Algorithms presented in 2015 could match human capabilities for this task, and currently, Deep Learning algorithms far surpass human error rates in this competition.

We could say that the growth in computing power marked a turning point for Deep Learning. Research in DL has been driven more by experimental advances (enabled by increased computing power) than by theory, as witnessed since 2012, when the necessary computing capacity became available to test and expand old ideas. Supporting this viewpoint is a study published by OpenAI titled 'AI and Compute' [3]. This study confirms that since 2012, the computing power available for generating artificial intelligence models has increased exponentially, asserting that improvements in computing capability have been a key component of AI and DL progress (see Fig. 2.17).

2.2.1 Transformers

The transformer architecture [4] has emerged as a revolutionary neural network model that has significantly impacted various domains of artificial intelligence. These models are composed of two main blocks: Encoders (Fig. 2.2.1 left) and Decoders (Fig. 2.2.1 right). In this section, we delve into the underlying principles and mechanisms of transformers, elucidating how they enable the modelling of complex relationships and capture contextual information effectively. We begin by providing a comprehensive overview of the self-attention mechanism, the cornerstone of transformer networks. We explain how self-attention allows the model to weigh and attend to different parts of the input sequence, facilitating the capture of long-range dependencies and contextually relevant information. Additionally, we discuss the concept of multi-head attention applied in the Encoders and Decoders (see Fig. 2.18), which further enhances the model's ability to extract and combine meaningful features from different perspectives.

Fig. 2.18 Transformer architecture [4]. Left: encoder. Right: decoder.

Attention mechanism

The attention mechanism is a pivotal component in transformer architectures, enabling the model to assign varying levels of importance to different elements of an input sequence. This mechanism facilitates the model's ability to focus on the most relevant parts of the sequence for each element being processed, thereby enhancing its capacity to capture contextual relationships and dependencies.

In the context of transformers, the attention mechanism operates using three fundamental matrices: **queries (Q)**, **keys (K)**, and **values (V)**. These matrices are derived from the input sequence X through projection onto learned parameters. Specifically, the **queries (Q)** represent the elements for which the model seeks information, while the **keys (K)** denote the elements that are compared against these queries to determine relevance. The **values (V)** matrix contains the information to be aggregated based on the computed attention scores. The dimensionality of the key and value matrices is denoted as d_k , which refers to the depth or dimensionality of the vectors used for the keys and values. This dimension ensures that the dot product between the queries and keys yields a well-defined measure and that the resulting attention scores are appropriately scaled.

The process of computing attention involves several key steps. Initially, the dot product of the query matrix Q with the transpose of the key matrix K^T is calculated. This operation results in a matrix of attention scores that reflects the relevance of each key with respect to each query. To stabilize the gradients during training, these scores are scaled by $\sqrt{d_k}$. Scaling helps mitigate the impact of excessively large values that could destabilize the learning process.

$$\text{softmax}(z_i) = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_j e^{z_j}} \quad (2.12)$$

Following scaling, the softmax function is applied to the scaled attention scores to obtain normalized attention weights. The softmax function converts the raw attention scores into a probability distribution, where each score is transformed into a value between 0 and 1, and the sum of all weights equals 1. This normalization ensures that the attention weights

can be interpreted as probabilities, allowing the model to emphasize the most relevant elements of the input sequence. Mathematically, the softmax function for a vector of raw scores z_i is defined in Equation 2.12. These normalized attention weights are then used to compute a weighted sum of the value matrix V . The outcome of this operation is an attended representation that highlights the most pertinent elements of the input sequence for each query.

Mathematically, the attention mechanism is represented as expressed in Equation 2.13. In this expression, A denotes the matrix of attention scores, while $\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ represents the scaled dot product used to compute these scores. The softmax function normalizes these scores, and the resulting matrix is employed to weight the value vectors V , producing the attended representation.

$$A(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (2.13)$$

Overall, the attention mechanism plays a crucial role in enabling the transformer model to capture long-range dependencies and contextual information, by allowing it to dynamically focus on different parts of the input sequence.

Encoder

The encoder layer in transformer architectures (left side in Fig. 2.18) plays a crucial role in mapping input sequences to an abstract continuous representation that captures the learned information for the entire sequence. This layer consists of two sub-modules: multi-headed attention and a fully connected network. To ensure effective information flow, residual connections are introduced around each of these sublayers, followed by layer normalization.

The multi-headed attention sub-module is responsible for capturing dependencies and relationships between different elements in the input sequence. It achieves this by calculating attention scores for each element with respect to all other elements in the sequence. The attention scores are computed using a scoring function that compares query, key, and value representations of the input elements. The resulting attention weights determine the relevance and contribution of each element to the representation of others.

Following the multi-headed attention mechanism, the output is passed through a fully connected network. This network introduces non-linearity and enables the model to learn complex relationships and patterns within the sequence. The fully connected network incorporates additional parameters that are trained during the learning process, allowing the model to adapt and capture more intricate representations.

To facilitate information propagation and mitigate the vanishing gradient problem, residual connections are employed. The vanishing gradient problem refers to the issue where gradients of the loss function become exceedingly small as they are propagated backward through the layers of the network during training. This problem makes it challenging for the model to learn, as the weight updates become very small, causing the network to stop learning effectively. Residual connections address this issue by providing a direct path for the gradient to flow through the network, allowing gradients to remain larger and more stable during backpropagation. These connections directly pass the original input of each sub-module to its output, providing a shortcut path for the gradient to flow during backpropagation. This helps in preserving and propagating important information across different layers, enhancing the overall learning capability of the model.

Furthermore, layer normalization is applied after each sub-module. This technique normalizes the activations within each layer, ensuring stable training and preventing the amplification or suppression of certain features. By normalizing the inputs, layer normalization contributes to improved gradient flow, faster convergence, and enhanced generalization performance.

Decoder

The decoder layer in transformer architectures (right side of Fig. 2.18) is responsible for generating text sequences. It comprises multiple sub-layers, including two multi-headed attention layers, a pointwise feed-forward layer, residual connections, and layer normalization after each sub-layer.

Similar to the encoder layer, the decoder layer incorporates multi-headed attention, which allows the model to capture dependencies and relationships between different elements in the

input sequence. However, the multi-headed attention in the decoder operates differently due to the autoregressive nature of decoding. To prevent the decoder from conditioning future tokens during attention computation, a look-ahead mask is applied. This mask ensures that each word in the sequence can only attend to itself and the preceding words, excluding future words.

The decoder layer also includes a second multi-headed attention layer, where the queries and keys are derived from the outputs of the encoder, and the values are obtained from the first multi-headed attention layer outputs. This mechanism enables the decoder to determine which encoder inputs are relevant for attention.

Additionally, a pointwise feed-forward layer is employed to further process the output of the second multi-headed attention layer. This layer introduces non-linearity and enables the model to learn complex relationships and patterns.

The final stages of the decoder layer involve a linear classifier, which has a dimensionality equal to the number of classes or words in the vocabulary. This classifier is responsible for assigning probabilities to different classes or words. The output of the classifier is then passed through a softmax layer, producing probability scores. The highest probability corresponds to the predicted word.

The decoder layer can be stacked multiple times, with each layer receiving inputs from the encoder and preceding layers. By stacking the layers, the model can learn to extract and focus on different combinations of attention, enhancing its predictive capability.

Applications of Transformers

Transformers, with their ability to model intricate relationships and process vast amounts of data, have significantly transformed numerous fields. Their impact is particularly evident in Natural Language Processing (NLP) where they have become the foundation for many SotA models. In machine translation, transformers like BERT [31] and GPT-3 [32] have dramatically improved the accuracy and fluency of translating text between languages. They also excel at summarizing lengthy documents, answering complex questions based on

extensive knowledge, and analyzing the sentiment expressed in textual data for applications like market research and customer feedback.

The success of transformers is not limited to language tasks; they have also found a prominent place in computer vision. Vision Transformers (ViT) [33] have achieved remarkable results in image classification by directly applying transformer architectures to image patches. Object detection pipelines have been simplified and enhanced through the use of transformer-based models like DETR [34], and tasks like image segmentation have also benefited from the power of transformers.

In speech processing, transformers have been instrumental in improving the accuracy of speech recognition systems and the naturalness of synthetic speech generated by text-to-speech models like Tacotron [35].

Beyond these domains, transformers are also utilized for time series forecasting, enabling predictions in areas such as financial markets, weather patterns, and energy consumption. In the scientific realm, they are being applied to complex problems like protein folding and genomic analysis, offering new avenues for research and discovery.

This wide range of applications underscores the versatility of transformers and their ability to handle complex, high-dimensional data efficiently. As research continues to advance, we can anticipate even more innovative and impactful applications of these powerful DL architectures.

2.2.2 Graph Neural Networks

GNNs have emerged as a powerful tool for machine learning tasks on graph-structured data. Unlike traditional neural networks designed for grid-like structures (e.g., images, sequences), GNNs can directly process graphs, where nodes represent entities and edges denote relationships between them. In this section, we will delve into the fundamental principles and mechanisms of GNNs, exploring how they enable the modelling of complex interactions within graphs.

We begin by providing a comprehensive overview of the graph convolution operation, a key component of GNNs. We explain how graph convolution aggregates information from

neighbouring nodes, allowing the model to capture local structural patterns and propagate information throughout the graph. Furthermore, we discuss various GNNs architectures, such as Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) and Graph Attention Networks (GAT), highlighting their unique approaches to learning node representations.

Graph Convolution

Graph convolution is the core operation in GNNs, analogous to the convolution operation in traditional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). However, instead of operating on a regular grid, graph convolution operates on the irregular structure of a graph. It aims to extract features from each node by aggregating information from its neighbouring nodes, as illustrated in Fig. 2.19

The mathematical representation of a graph convolution is expressed in Equation 2.14, where:

- $H^{(l+1)}$ is the output of the $(l + 1)$ -th layer,
- σ is the activation function applied element-wise,
- D is the diagonal degree matrix of the graph A ,
- A is the adjacency matrix of the graph,
- $H^{(l)}$ is the input from the l -th layer,
- $W^{(l)}$ is the weight matrix for the l -th layer.

$$\mathbf{H}^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(\mathbf{D}^{-1/2} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{D}^{-1/2} \mathbf{H}^{(l)} \mathbf{W}^{(l)} \right) \quad (2.14)$$

The adjacency matrix A encodes the connectivity information of the graph, while the degree matrix D accounts for the degree of each node. The normalized adjacency matrix $D^{-\frac{1}{2}} A D^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ ensures that the node features are scaled appropriately during aggregation. The weight matrix W^l is learned during training and determines the importance of different features.

Fig. 2.19 Graph Convolution operation (left) vs Image Convolution operation (right) [5].

Fig. 2.20 GCNs architecture [5].

Graph Neural Network Architectures

There are various GNN architectures, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. Some popular architectures include:

- **GCNs:** Are a simple yet effective GNNs architecture that used graph convolution to aggregate information from neighbouring nodes. This architecture is presented in Fig. 2.20.
- **GATs:** incorporate an attention mechanism into graph convolution, allowing the model to weigh the importance of different neighbors based on their features. This architecture is presented in Fig. 2.21.
- **GraphSAGE:** is a scalable GNN architecture that samples a fixed number of neighbors for each node during training, making it suitable for large graphs.

Applications of Graph Neural Networks

GNNs have proven their utility across a wide range of domains due to their ability to effectively model complex relationships and dependencies within graph-structured data. In social network analysis, GNNs have been applied to tasks like predicting user behavior, identifying communities within networks, and providing personalized recommendations.

Fig. 2.21 GATs architecture [5] [5].

Similarly, in recommender systems, GNNs can model the intricate interactions between users and items, enabling more accurate and tailored recommendations.

The field of drug discovery has also benefited from GNNs. By representing molecules as graphs, where atoms are nodes and chemical bonds are edges, GNNs can predict drug-target interactions and model molecular properties, accelerating the drug development process. Additionally, in natural language processing, GNNs are utilized to model sentence structure, capture semantic relationships between words, and enhance various tasks like machine translation and sentiment analysis.

Point cloud processing, a fundamental task in 3D computer vision, has also seen significant advancements with the adoption of GNNs. Point clouds, which are sets of 3D points representing the surface of an object, can be naturally represented as graphs. GNNs can then be used to perform tasks such as point cloud classification, segmentation, and upsampling. In particular, GNN-based upsampling methods have shown promising results in generating denser and more accurate point clouds from sparse input data.

The flexibility and expressive power of GNNs make them a valuable tool for machine learning on graph-structured data. As research in this area continues to flourish, we anticipate the development of even more innovative GNN architectures and a wider range of applications

across diverse fields. GNNs have the potential to unlock new insights and improve decision-making processes by leveraging the rich information embedded in graphs.

2.3 Robot Operating System

Robot Operating System (ROS) is an open-source framework designed to simplify the development of robotic applications. While not a traditional operating system, ROS provides a flexible collection of software libraries, tools, and conventions that facilitate communication, coordination, and integration of diverse robotic components.

ROS operates on a publish-subscribe architecture, where independent processes called nodes communicate with each other by exchanging messages over named channels called topics. This decentralized structure promotes modularity, allowing developers to build complex systems by combining smaller, reusable components. In ROS, messages are structured data packets that carry information between nodes, while services enable request-response interactions for specific actions. The parameter server acts as a centralized repository for storing and retrieving configuration parameters, and the master node serves as a central coordinator, helping nodes discover each other and establish communication.

ROS offers several advantages for robotics development. Its modular design promotes code reusability and simplifies the integration of new components. Hardware abstraction layers provide drivers and interfaces for various sensors and actuators, streamlining hardware integration. The large and active ROS community contributes packages and tools, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing. ROS also supports realistic simulation environments like Gazebo, enabling testing and development without physical robots. Additionally, it includes visualization tools (RViz), debugging tools (rosviz), and command-line utilities for managing ROS systems.

ROS has become a de facto standard for robotics research and prototyping due to its flexibility, extensibility, and community support. It has also gained traction in industrial applications, especially in areas like autonomous mobile robots, industrial automation, and research platforms. ROS 2, the latest generation of ROS, builds on the success of ROS

1 while addressing scalability, reliability, and real-time performance challenges. It also introduces a new communication architecture based on the Data Distribution Service (DDS) standard, making it more suitable for complex, distributed systems.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

This chapter provides a comprehensive literature review of autonomous vehicle technology. It analyzes various autonomous driving systems, examining their strengths, weaknesses, and approaches to navigation. It also explores teledriving systems, where humans remotely control autonomous vehicles. The chapter delves into perception systems, investigating sensor technologies and algorithms used for environmental understanding. Additionally, it examines research on environmental sustainability within the context of autonomous vehicles, considering alternative fuels, energy efficiency, and potential impacts on traffic and emissions. The goal of this review is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the current state and future directions of autonomous vehicle technology, addressing both technological advancements and broader societal and environmental implications.

3.1 Autonomous Driving Systems

Automated driving Systems (ADS) have experienced significant momentum in recent years. Following the initial ADS implementations in the PROMETHEUS project over 30 years ago [36], and subsequent advancements during the DARPA Urban and Grand Challenges [37, 38], the field has seen continuous development and has become a prominent topic worldwide. In 2021, Cenex [39] predicted that a fleet of autonomous robotaxis could generate an annual profit of approximately GBP 27,000 per vehicle by 2030. Furthermore, NNT [40] forecasted

the potential for 100% market penetration of autonomous cars by 2060. This 40-year transition period is expected to witness the emergence of new autonomous capabilities, which will be supported and overseen by human drivers.

The SAE defines six levels of automation for autonomous vehicles, ranging from Level 0 to Level 5 (see Fig. 3.1), to categorize the extent of a vehicle's automation capabilities. At Level 0, there is no automation, and the human driver is entirely responsible for controlling the vehicle. Level 1 introduces driver assistance, where the vehicle can assist with either steering or acceleration/deceleration, but not both simultaneously. At Level 2, partial automation is achieved, allowing the vehicle to control both steering and acceleration/deceleration under certain conditions, though the human driver must remain engaged and monitor the driving environment. Level 3, or conditional automation, enables the vehicle to manage all aspects of driving under specific conditions, with the expectation that the human driver will intervene when requested. Level 4, high automation, allows the vehicle to perform all driving tasks and monitor the driving environment even if the human driver does not respond appropriately, but only within certain Operational Design Domains (ODDs). Finally, Level 5, full automation, signifies that the vehicle can handle all driving tasks independently, under all conditions that a human driver could manage, eliminating the need for human intervention entirely.

Fig. 3.1 Automation levels defined by the SAE.

Nowadays, most commercial ADS are of Level 2 (L2). This level of automation requires a human driver to be physically present inside the car, and able to take over the control of the steering wheel and pedals when needed; however, security, reliability, and trust are being increased, and there will eventually be a movement to scenarios where the human driver will be invigilating the car from a remote location, rather than being physically inside the car.

Recent progress in ADS implementation has been propelled by cutting-edge advancements in sensing and computing technologies, such as the use of highly capable LiDARs, RADARs, and multi-spectrum cameras to integrate new AI capabilities. These innovations have enabled the automotive industry and researchers to achieve higher levels of automation [41].

Table 3.1 provides a comparison of key features for various self-driving systems, including both open-source and proprietary options. As can be seen in this table, several prominent proprietary self-driving systems exist, including Waymo’s World’s Most Experienced Driver [42], Mercedes-Benz’s Distronic and Drive Pilot [43, 44], Nissan’s ProPilot [45], BMW’s Personal Co-Pilot [46], and Tesla’s Autopilot [47]. In the open-source realm, Baidu Apollo [48] and Openpilot [28] (which forms the foundation for our system) are well-known. (Table 3.1) outlines the varying SAE automation levels of these systems, ranging from L2 to L4. Notably, L3 and L4 systems utilize LiDAR technology alongside cameras and radars for enhanced perception, and offer functionalities like automated lane changes in addition to distance-keeping and lane-following capabilities present in L2 systems.

Table 3.1 Characteristics and comparison of different autonomous driving car systems. ✓ denotes that the capability is available in the system and × denotes that it is not.

System	Sensory Perception			Control			Automation	Tele-Driving			Open Source	Remote AI Activation	
	Cameras	Radar	Lidar	Keep Distance	Lane Following	Lane Keeping	Automated Lane-Change	SAE Level	In Car	Off Car			Empirical Validation
Waymo	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	4	×	✓	×	×	×
ProPilot	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×	2	×	×	×	×	×
Distronic	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×	2	×	×	×	×	×
Apollo	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	4	×	×	×	✓	✓
Drive Pilot	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	3	×	×	×	×	×
Autopilot	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×	2	×	×	×	×	×
Openpilot	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×	2	✓	×	×	✓	×
This thesis	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×	2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

3.2 Remote Driving Systems

The concept of vehicle tele-operation has been rapidly advancing in the industry, increasingly playing a crucial role in assisting self-driving cars with complex situations beyond the capabilities of autonomous systems. Currently, tele-operation depends entirely on remote human drivers. However, future systems powered by artificial intelligence and advanced networks, such as 5G [49], could offload some of the automated driving intelligence from the vehicle to the cloud. Over time, this advancement in remote driving automation could facilitate new automated driving solutions that are currently unattainable.

Automobile manufacturers apply DL techniques [50] to develop their self-driving systems. A major advantage of these algorithms is that they learn from examples rather than requiring explicit programming to achieve desired outcomes, thereby eliminating the need for comprehensive functional specifications.

DL algorithms only perform well when the input data closely resemble the data they were trained on; however, these algorithms struggle to generalize across different domains. For instance, in [51], the authors demonstrated that an algorithm trained to detect traffic signals under specific conditions failed to recognize them under different circumstances. Similarly, in [52], researchers found that conventional DL algorithms had difficulty generalizing across different frames of the same video, misclassifying the same polar bears as a baboon, mongoose, or weasel due to minor background changes. This issue extends to learning distinct functions separately and imitating human behaviors, which are aggregated results of multiple functions [53–56]. Thus, it would be necessary to train the DL algorithms with data sets that represented all the possible things a vehicle might deal with while it is working, which would be almost impossible.

A fully self-driving car is a very complex system: for this reason, using cyclomatic complexity, it is expected to have 1 billion lines of software code [57], which is a huge number of code lines, considering that one Boeing 787 jetliner has about 14 million lines of code. With such a large number of lines, it would be very likely to have bugs, which could cause traffic accidents. Moreover, maintaining and upgrading software this large in so many cars (a large carmaker usually has tens of millions) would be highly costly [58].

Because DL algorithms are trained using examples rather than explicit functional specifications, verifying whether the software will perform as intended by designers and developers is challenging. This difficulty arises because the knowledge learned by Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) is often non-interpretable [59].

Current safety validation methods struggle to assess self-driving cars due to limitations in deep learning models' ability to generalize to unseen situations. As discussed in [60], achieving 95% confidence that a self-driving car's fatality rate is no worse than a human driver's requires a fleet to drive 275 million miles accident-free. This translates to an unrealistic timeframe: even with 100 cars driving continuously at 45 mph, it would take roughly 7 years. The same study estimates that ensuring a fleet's fatality rate is within 20% of a human driver's necessitates 8.8 billion miles of testing, translating to a staggering 224 years for 100 cars. Furthermore, these tests must encompass the vast array of driving scenarios cars might encounter throughout their service life.

Despite being a frontrunner in self-driving car development, Waymo had only logged 20 million miles of real-world testing by January 2020, as reported in [61]. Moreover, a significant portion of this data was used to train the car's machine learning models, limiting its usefulness in evaluating their actual effectiveness.

Given the challenges discussed earlier, widespread adoption of fully autonomous (SAE Level 5) vehicles seems unlikely in the near future. However, teledriving technology, in conjunction with partially automated cars, presents a promising alternative. Human remote operators can enable novel commercial services with existing vehicles, including tele-operated taxis, remote valet parking, and goods delivery. Additionally, teledriving offers a bridge for interaction between self-driving cars and humans, facilitating communication with law enforcement, parking attendants, and repair personnel.

Research on vehicle tele-operation started in the early 1970s [62, 63]. The emergence of the internet offered new possibilities. Authors of [64] explored using an internet connection (via phone lines) for remote operation along pre-programmed routes, with features like receiving vehicle location data and video. Studies continued with similar network technologies, as shown in [65] and [66]. These works investigated tele-operation systems using

existing cellular networks. For instance, [65] built a prototype and conducted human trials with varying network delays based on current LTE technology. Their findings suggested that network delay variability, more than absolute delay, hindered real-time remote driving over LTE. Similarly, [66] conducted real-world measurements to assess the feasibility of tele-operation. Their results, obtained through complementary measurement setups, indicated network limitations that could impede system usability.

Since 2018, many companies have developed human-tele-operated vehicles, and have been testing them on public roads [67–72]. Table 3.1 summarizes the main characteristics of different self-driving systems, both open-source, and proprietary.

Since 2018, there has been a surge in companies developing and testing human-operated teleoperated vehicles on public roads, as documented in [67–72].

Among the proprietary systems we reviewed in this table, none offer documented remote control capabilities except Waymo’s. However, information regarding Waymo’s remote control performance, including aspects like monitoring and video streaming, is not publicly available. In contrast, the open-source systems presented in Table 3.1 (Openpilot and our system) do incorporate tele-driving functionality. Unfortunately, there is also a lack of published performance data for these open-source systems.

To the best of our knowledge, from the proprietary systems, the only one that allows remote control is Waymo’s, and there are no results about its control, monitoring, or video streaming performance. On the contrary, the open-source systems shown in Table 3.1 allow tele-driving. Nonetheless, there are no published results for the open-source systems either.

3.3 Perception

The cornerstone of successful AVs navigation lies in their ability to perceive and comprehend their surroundings with exceptional accuracy. This critical perception capability hinges on a carefully chosen and integrated suite of sensor technologies. While some commercially available systems, like Tesla’s Autopilot, primarily rely on cameras for data acquisition [47], this approach exhibits limitations in adverse weather conditions and low-light environments,

as highlighted by [73]. Conversely, other systems leverage a more comprehensive sensor suite, often incorporating a combination of LiDARs, radars, and cameras (refer to Table 3.1), which is known as multi-sensor fusion. As explored in [74], this approach allows for a more robust and reliable perception system by exploiting the complementary strengths of each sensor modality. LiDARs, for instance, excel at high-resolution 3D object detection and mapping, as detailed in [75], while radars offer superior performance in poor visibility conditions due to their all-weather capability, as explained in [76]. Cameras, although susceptible to lighting variations, provide rich visual information for lane line detection, traffic sign recognition, and object classification, as discussed in [77]. By understanding the unique strengths and limitations of each sensor type, researchers and engineers can develop optimal sensor configurations tailored for specific AV applications, ultimately enhancing the safety, efficiency, and overall performance of autonomous vehicles.

This highlights the two primary types of 3D object detection algorithms: those that rely solely on one type of data, such as point clouds from LiDAR, and those that leverage multiple data modalities, such as images and point clouds, for more comprehensive analysis and detection. Each approach offers unique advantages and challenges, ultimately contributing to the rich tapestry of methodologies available for enhancing object detection capabilities in diverse environments.

Firstly, we delve into the realm of point-cloud-based algorithms, which rely solely on point clouds as their input data. These algorithms exhibit prowess in extracting valuable insights from specific sensor modalities, offering targeted solutions for object detection tasks. By transmuting depth images into point clouds and embedding Hough voting within an end-to-end differentiable architecture, VoteNet [78] has emerged as a front-runner in 3D object detection, showcasing unparalleled performance on benchmark datasets like SUN RGB-D and ScanNetV2. While its achievements are noteworthy, the sparse nature of data presents a persistent challenge, particularly in accurately regressing 3D object centroids, and its confinement solely to point cloud data, excluding image inputs, delineates its limitations. Similarly, Shape Signature Network (SSN) [79] heralds a new era in 3D object detection by introducing a unique shape signature for enhanced multi-class discrimination in point

cloud analysis. Leveraging symmetry, convex hull, and Chebyshev fitting operations, SSN has attained state-of-the-art results on extensive datasets such as nuScenes [80] and Lyft [81], underscoring its efficacy in addressing the intricacies of 3D shape information representation. Its contribution lies not only in the compact and robust encoding of shape features but also in the adept handling of class-specific distinctions, thus mitigating the challenges associated with accurate 3D object detection. In a divergent trajectory, the Single-stage Monocular 3D Object Detection from KeyPoints (SMOKE) [82] methodology presents a paradigm shift by circumventing traditional 2D detection stages. Through a multi-step disentanglement approach, SMOKE has demonstrated remarkable improvements in both accuracy and speed, eclipsing existing monocular 3D detection methods on prominent datasets such as KITTI [27]. Its innovative approach to 3D bounding box regression and strategic emphasis on training convergence augmentation underscore its significance in pushing the boundaries of monocular 3D object detection. Concurrently, the RegNet paper [83] delves deep into the intricacies of network design, offering insights into the RegNet models that outperform their counterparts like EfficientNet in terms of speed and performance. By parameterizing networks and meticulously analyzing the design space, the paper presents a promising trajectory for future research, wherein network structure, width, depth, and grouping dynamics are meticulously orchestrated for optimal performance. Further enriching the landscape of 3D object detection are methodologies such as PointPillars [7], Position Adaptive Convolution (PAConv) [84], and CenterPoint [85], each offering distinctive contributions to the field. PointPillars, with its novel trade-off between speed and accuracy, embodies the essence of end-to-end learning through 2D convolutional layers. PAConv, on the other hand, introduces a versatile convolutional operation tailored explicitly for point cloud tasks, thereby enhancing performance across various domains. Meanwhile, CenterPoint pioneers a center-based framework, simplifying 3D object detection and tracking while delivering state-of-the-art results on challenging benchmarks like Waymo and nuScenes [80].

Conversely, we explore the realm of fusion algorithms, which harness the power of integrating data from multiple sensors, combining images and point clouds. By leveraging complementary information from diverse sensor modalities, fusion algorithms unlock new

dimensions of understanding, enhancing detection accuracy, robustness, and adaptability across varied environmental conditions. Through the fusion of data streams, these algorithms offer holistic perspectives, enriching the object detection process and advancing the frontier of autonomous systems. Firstly, the PC-CNN [86] algorithm stands out for its profound impact on 3D vehicle detection within autonomous driving systems, offering a versatile pipeline capable of integrating both 1D and 3D detection methodologies. Notably, it showcases robust competencies in 2D detection, securing a prominent second place among its algorithmic counterparts. The methodological innovation lies in its two-stage CNN framework, facilitating the alignment of 3D boxes to point clouds and enabling effective car dimension estimation through regression layers. This approach, bolstered by generalized car models encompassing SUVs, Sedans, and Vans, significantly enhances 3D detection performance, particularly outperforming image-based approaches in 3D box detection tasks. On a similar trajectory, the MV3D [87] algorithm elevates 3D object detection for autonomous driving scenarios, amplifying the performance and safety thresholds within self-driving car frameworks. Its Multi-View 3D networks (MV3D) serve as the cornerstone for high-accuracy object detection, achieving notable advancements in 3D localization and detection tasks, surpassing state-of-the-art methods by substantial margins. Employing feature transformation functions, late fusion techniques, and encoding 3D point clouds with multi-view feature maps, MV3D sets a new standard for object detection efficiency and accuracy in real-world driving environments. Moving forward, the MMF [88] algorithm introduces a paradigm shift in 3D object detection by harnessing the power of multi-sensor fusion. This innovation not only excels in surpassing KITTI benchmarks across 2D, 3D, and Bird's Eye View (BEV) object detection but also offers a real-time solution for multi-task multi-sensor fusion applications. By exploiting ground estimation, depth completion, and end-to-end learnable architectures, MMF demonstrates unparalleled prowess in enhancing LiDAR point clouds and achieving superior performance in object detection tasks across diverse environments. Moreover, the Frustum PointNets [8] algorithm emerges as a beacon of efficiency and precision in 3D object detection, particularly in large-scale indoor and outdoor scenes. Leveraging both 2D and 3D methodologies, along with the introduction of a novel regularization loss called corner loss,

Frustum PointNets exhibits remarkable capability in precise 3D bounding box estimation, even under challenging occlusion scenarios. Its ability to seamlessly integrate with mature 2D object detectors further enhances its applicability and robustness across various detection benchmarks. Furthering the frontier of 3D object detection, the EPNet [9] algorithm strategically incorporates semantic image features to augment detection capabilities, fostering consistency between localization and classification confidence. The Fusion module and Consistency Enforcing Loss emerge as pivotal contributions, significantly boosting detection performance and ensuring better consistency in real-world applications. Notably, the EPNet algorithm aligns well with the design principles of our solution due to its ability to leverage semantic features and enforce consistency in both localization and classification, thereby improving overall robustness. Lastly, the Contfuse [89] algorithm stands tall with its novel fusion layer for multi-sensor detection architecture, showcasing substantial improvements over existing methods. By effectively fusing LiDAR and image features through continuous convolutions and multi-task learning mechanisms, Contfuse not only demonstrates superior scalability and performance but also offers a reliable and efficient end-to-end solution for 3D object detection tasks, particularly excelling in long-range detection scenarios. However, despite its strengths, Contfuse has not been adopted in our approach due to its primary focus on long-range detection tasks, which are not central to the specific objectives of our study. Instead, our solution aligns more closely with EPNet and Frustum PointNets, as these algorithms emphasize the integration of semantic features, precise 3D bounding box estimation, and robustness in both indoor and outdoor environments, making them better suited for our use case.

3.4 Environmental Sustainability in Autonomous Vehicles

Several studies that have employed classic ML and DNNs for CO_2 prediction tasks. One study, presented in [90], provides a comprehensive account of the design and development of low-cost sensor hardware for an in-vehicle air quality monitoring system with cloud-based storage and prediction. The system employs machine learning prediction algorithms,

including MLP, Support Vector Regression (SVR), and linear regression algorithms, to predict air quality based on various inputs. This paper's contribution lies in the prediction system, which includes the development of sensor hardware and cloud-based predictive analysis for in-vehicle air quality monitoring. The study highlights the system's potential for future smart cities and smart mobility applications in reducing accidents and injuries due to road incidents.

Also in this regard, [91] focuses on the prediction of CO_2 emissions from vehicles using an ensemble machine learning technique. The research aims to address the challenges of poor air quality in urbanizing cities caused by transportation emissions, particularly CO_2 from vehicles. The study utilizes data collected from laboratory tests conducted on two passenger cars and develops a CO_2 prediction model using the ensemble technique. The results demonstrate the model's potential in assisting urban transportation planners in designing smart transportation planning and responding to carbon footprint concerns. The research contributes to the development of a more accurate and reliable method for predicting CO_2 emissions from vehicles, aiding in emissions management and achieving legislative objectives.

Another comprehensive study, [92], focuses on capturing uncertainty in emission estimates related to vehicle electrification and its implications for metropolitan greenhouse gas emission inventories. Conducted by a team of researchers, the study highlights the impacts of uncertainty sources in transportation energy and greenhouse gas emission inventory, quantifies these uncertainties, and develops a probability distribution of regional emissions using Monte Carlo simulation. The study also discusses the implications of emission inventory uncertainty in decision-making for metropolitan greenhouse gas emission inventories. This work contributes to the understanding of uncertainties in current emission and energy consumption modeling approaches, influencing the evaluation of energy and power distribution systems and related policies.

In the realm of deep learning models, [93] introduces a deep learning model for predicting vehicular CO_2 emissions using On-Board Diagnostics (OBD-II) port data. The CO_2 ViT is based on the original Visual Transformer (ViT) architecture and is shown to be highly

robust, making it suitable for real-world applications. The study includes an experimental analysis of the effects of sensor noise on model performance and a comparative study of varying model structures and window widths. The major contributions of this work are the development of a robust LSTM-based deep learning model for continuous CO_2 prediction from OBD-II data and insights into the challenges associated with working with raw OBD-II data, demonstrating the potential for estimating vehicular emissions using OBD-II-based systems.

Similarly, [94] presents a methodology for creating a CO_2 emission model of a full hybrid vehicle using machine learning techniques. The study reviews various regression methods and identifies Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) as the best fit for the road input data. The research demonstrates that machine learning methods are sensitive enough to learn and create emission models for hybrid vehicles. However, the variability of CO_2 emissions from hybrid vehicles highlights the need for reliable emission models. The study contributes to reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainable transportation by providing an accurate and efficient method for measuring vehicle emissions.

Two additional studies, [95] and [96], focus on the prediction of emissions using machine learning techniques and Portable Emission Measurement Systems (PEMS). [95] proposes a Parallel Attention-based Long Short-Term Memory (PA-LSTM) for building emission prediction models using PEMS data. [96] presents a framework that utilizes machine learning techniques to forecast emissions from heavy construction machinery, combining inertial sensors and PEMS for data collection and analysis.

Lastly, [97], [98], and [13] explore the use of different machine learning models for predicting CO_2 emissions. These studies employ ANN and evaluate their effectiveness in predicting emissions from road vehicles, urban air pollutant concentrations, and emissions in hybrid vehicles.

To the best of our knowledge, there is a dearth of studies employing transformer-based architectures for CO_2 prediction. Table 3.2 shows the results provided in each one of the works cited in this section. It shows that the predominant models described in the literature for this purpose are LSTM models and traditional ML algorithms. Moreover, the last row of

the table shows that it is our CO_2 ViT model, proposed in this thesis, the one that achieves the highest R^2 score for the task of CO_2 prediction. In this paper, we highlight the potential of transformers and their superiority over other models when applied to CO_2 prediction tasks. The use of transformers in CO_2 prediction holds promise and merits further investigation and exploration.

Table 3.2 Comparison of academic solutions for CO_2 prediction applied to vehicles.

Ref.	Prediction target	Algorithm	Vehicle use	R2	RMSE	RE
[90]	CO_2 concentration (ppm)	GBR	Passenger transportation	0.91	-	-
[91]	CO_2 emission (g/s)	GBR	Passenger transportation	0.99	-	-
[92]	CO_2 emission (g/s)	XGBoost	Passenger transportation	89.8	-	-
[93]	CO_2 emission (g/km)	LSTM	Passenger transportation	-	9.30	-
[94]	CO_2 emission (g/s)	GPR	Passenger transportation	0.69	-	-
[95]	CO_2 emissions (kg)	LR	Passenger transportation	0.95	-	-
[96]	CO_2 concentration (%)	PA-LSTM	Passenger transportation	0.94	-	-
[97]	CO_2 concentration (ppm)	RF	Construction material transportation	0.94	-	-
[98]	CO_2 emissions (kg)	ANN	Passenger transportation	-	-	0.5
[13]	CO_2 concentration (ppm)	LSTM	Passenger transportation	0.97	-	-
This thesis	CO_2 concentration (ppm)	ViT	Passenger transportation	0.9899	-	-

Chapter 4

Design, Implementation, and Empirical Validation of a Framework for Remote Car Driving Using a Commercial Mobile Network

4.1 Introduction

Autonomous and remote driving have been gaining increasing traction in recent years. In 2021, a Cenex [14] study projected significant profitability for self-driving taxis by the end of the decade, while NNT [40] forecasts full market adoption of autonomous vehicles as early as 2060. To better understand the varying degrees of automation possible, the Society of Automotive Engineering (SAE) has defined five levels, ranging from L0 (no automation) to L5 (full automation). During this anticipated 40-year transition period, we expect the emergence of new autonomous features, with human drivers playing a crucial role in supporting and overseeing these technologies.

Currently, Level 2 automation mandates the presence of a human driver within the vehicle, ready to assume control of steering and braking when necessary. However, as safety, reliability, and trust in these systems continue to improve, we anticipate a shift towards

scenarios where human supervision will occur remotely, rather than from inside the vehicle itself.

While fully autonomous vehicles (SAE level 5) are not expected to become a reality in the near future, integrating remote driving with existing car control automation could offer significant societal benefits. This combination has the potential to enhance and expand services like medical supply delivery, transportation of disaster relief resources, and expedited transport of accident victims requiring urgent medical care.

Cenex [39] has forecasted that within the next 2 to 5 years, there will be a shift from manually driven cars to fully remote-operated vehicles. In alignment with this, Visteon [99] has outlined a detailed perspective on how remote driving will support autonomous driving, highlighting the associated challenges and best practices.

In this socio-economic context, it is of paramount importance to address the technological barriers that prevent remote car driving from becoming a reality, enumerated as follows:

- there is a lack of available solutions that enable remote access to the control of the car;
- the number of available resources is even smaller when trying to find systems that allow both remote driving and autonomous capabilities to co-exist;
- the scenario is even worse when trying to find published results about the performance and overheads associated with the use of such remote car driving enablers: thus, it hampers the understanding of the implications and suitability associated with the use of such technologies;
- in the public domain, especially in the academic community, one can rarely find research works that are based on real cars, rather than on mere simulations, which do not enable discovery of the requirements for achieving real-world remote driving.

Addressing these challenges was the main motivation for this chapter. The main contribution of this chapter is the design, implementation, and validation of a realistic framework for achieving remote car driving. The following list summarizes the innovations provided in this manuscript with respect to the state of the art:

- the design and implementation of a fully functional framework able to achieve the fundamentals of remote car driving while allowing the collocation of automation and human driving;
- the implementation of a system that allows "joystick-mode", i.e., the control of the car by a remote driver;
- the empirical validation and performance analysis of the control system, based on a commercial car (2019 Toyota Prius Hybrid Car).

In order to describe our contribution, this manuscript is structured as follows: Section 4.2 presents the proposed architecture for the remote driving system, which allows Artificial Intelligence (AI) or remote control of the car; Section 4.3 explains the workflow of the functioning steps that constitute our control system for remote driving; Section 4.4 describes how we implemented the system and hardware specifications for the prototype; Section 4.5 addresses the different experiments carried out, and presents the empirical results; finally, in Section 4.6, the results are summarized, and future work is outlined.

4.2 Proposed Architecture

In this section, the remote car driving system's architecture is presented. A graphical overview of the proposed architecture can be seen in Fig. 4.1, where the contributions of this section are marked with stars.

There is a remote location on the left side of Fig. 4.1: this location is composed of all the software and hardware components the remote driver needs, including the computer on which the software of our system is running. Furthermore, this setup has a screen, so that the driver has visual information about the car's surroundings: this is one of the most important aspects, as it is of vital importance that the driver knows the road conditions at all times, and what is happening around the vehicle. The video will be received via a remote video client, and streamed on the screen. Based on the information provided by the video, the driver will choose which decisions are best, and will translate those decisions to joystick commands,

and publish them in a remote control server, so that the car control commands are sent to the car through its Controller Area Network (CAN) bus.

Fig. 4.1 Proposed architecture for the remote-driving system.

The in-car setup can be seen on the right side of Fig. 4.1. It is possible to differentiate four tasks: sensing; autonomous AI control; remote communications; and car control, all of which are connected by a message bus, which is a publication/subsription message bus, such as ZeroMQ, RabbitMQ, or similar.

The sensing modules in the in-car system capture the car environment. To do so, two main sensors are used: a radar and a camera. The camera module is receiving information from the road as the webcam is installed on the windshield; furthermore, the video captured by this camera is the same as that being sent to the remote driver. The radar is integrated into the car, and is connected using the standardized car interface OBD-II port. These two modules are represented as the *Video Acquisition Module* and the *Car Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) Acquisition Module* in Fig. 4.1. The main purpose of the *IMU Acquisition Module* is to alert the driver, in case it detects a possible collision. After the data has been captured, it is sent over to the ZeroMQ Bus, so that it can be used by the rest of the sub-modules, if needed.

The Autonomous AI control modules (see right side of Fig. 4.1) play a critical role. Remote-operation nowadays relies completely on remote human drivers; however, we believe that a mixed system of human remote-operated and autonomous vehicles is a suitable and feasible combination during the transition period, until SAE Level 4 systems are a reality: for this reason, the purpose of these modules is to allow the in-car self-driving system to take control of the vehicle. It is the remote driver who decides when the car is in a situation

in which the activation of the AI control module is feasible and secure. The remote driver can regain control of the vehicle at any time, by pressing a button on the joystick. The self-driving system relies on two different modules: the perception and the planning modules. The perception module takes the information from the sensing module, and processes it, to detect, among other things, the shape of the road, the shape of the lanes, any possible object that the car might collide with, and other contextual on-road information. Once such information has been extracted, the planning module creates the safe path that the car should follow. As with the other modules, the information from this module is also published on the message bus, so that it is available for any interested module to receive.

The communication modules are in the top part of Fig. 4.1: they are in charge of sending the visual information from the car to the remote driver, and receiving the car commands that the remote driver has decided to send. Communication is composed of two different modules: the remote control module and the remote video server. The remote control module receives the commands sent by the remote driver, sending them directly to the car control module. The remote video server takes the video captured by the camera from the sensing module, and sends it to the remote driver. Special security and reliability should be applied to these modules, as their failure could lead to fatal consequences: such architectural security aspects have been kept outside the scope of this contribution, and they may lead to a complete manuscript as part of future work addressing the challenges. The main intention of our manuscript was to prove the suitability of the basic remote driving system, using real validation. We mitigated the security aspects by making sure that there was always a driver inside the car, ready to react along with our experimentation.

The car control module depicted in the bottom left part of Fig. 4.1 is in charge of receiving the steering wheel and acceleration commands that have been sent either by the remote driver or the AI path planner model, and then translating them into CAN messages, which are directly sent to the car, to enforce the control actions in the vehicle.

The CAN bus is used by all car makers, as it is very robust, simpler than other protocols (i.e., Local Interconnect Network (LIN)), and designed to meet the automobile industry's needs. It is a message-based protocol where every message is identified by a predefined

unique ID. The transmitted data packet is received by all nodes in a CAN bus network: depending on the ID, the CAN node decides whether to accept it or not. Usually, a car is monitored and controlled by a number of different Electronic Control Units (ECU). A typical car contains from 20 to 100 ECUs, where each ECU is responsible for one or more particular features of the vehicle. This bus allows ECUs to communicate with each other without much complexity, by just connecting each ECU to the common serial bus. This is the bus used by the car control module, in order to send commands to the car to enforce actions related to acceleration, braking, and wheel steering, among others.

With respect to the communication network, the reader can see how the remote driver is connected to the internet, using a fixed communication technology such as Asymmetric Digital Subscriber Line (ADSL), fibre optics, or any other high-speed internet method. The car, by contrast, is connected to the network using a 4G/5G modem connected to a public mobile telecommunication infrastructure, to allow the car to connect while on the road. As both are public networks, they are interconnected, allowing connectivity. It is worth mentioning that 4G/5G mobile networks connect using Network Address Translation (NAT), to provide IP addresses to their customers, and this pushed us to create an architecture where the initiators of the communication channel are always the modules located in the car, using a public IP address available in the remote driver location.

4.3 Sequence Diagram for Remote Driving

This section explains in detail the sequence diagram of the proposed architecture to achieve the remote driving. The diagram is shown in Fig. 4.2. As can be seen, there are different locations in the proposed architecture (see Fig. 4.1): the remote driving and the in-car module.

The sequence diagram is based on three main loops: the first one is in charge of receiving video from the car loop; the second one allows the remote control of the car; and the third one is the loop in which the AI takes control of the car. The video-receiving loop is always

working; however, the remote control loop and the self-driving loop are mutually exclusive, i.e., when one of them is operating, the other one is not.

In the first step of the video receiver loop, the driver connects to the remote video client (arrow 1 in Fig. 4.2), and waits until the car connects to the remote driver. It is the car that initiates the communication as a security measure (arrow 2 in Fig. 4.2). At this point, the connection is established, but the remote driver is not receiving any visual information. To start receiving video frames, the Remote Video Server needs to get the information from the camera (arrows 3 and 4 in Fig. 4.2), and send it back to the Remote Video Client (arrows 5, 6, and 7 in Fig. 4.2): after this, the remote driver starts receiving visual information about the car's environment (arrow 8 in 4.2). The continuous loop is established in the video delivery of information from the car to the remote driver.

Once the video-receiving loop is operating, there are two different possibilities: the first option is to control the car remotely, and the other option is to allow an AI to take control of the car. It is up to the remote driver to decide between these options. If the driver believes that the current location of the car is better, then the remote driver takes control, and the remote control loop will begin; however, if the car is in an environment where the AI can operate and drive the car securely, the self-driving loop will be turned on. We introduced into the system the possibility of changing from human remote driving to self-driving and vice-versa, sending a special command to the Remote Control Client.

If the remote driver decides to activate the remote control loop, the driver will connect to the remote control server (arrow 9 in Fig. 4.2), and will wait until the Remote Control Client located in the car connects to the module, using the public IP address of the remote driver (arrow 10): this remote control server is where all the acceleration and steering wheel commands will be received from the joystick, and published to the car's CAN bus (see arrows 11 and 12). The published messages will be received by the remote control client (arrow 12 in Fig. 4.2), transformed to CAN messages (see arrow 13), and sent to the car CAN bus (arrow 14 in Fig. 4.2).

Nevertheless, if the remote driver decides that the car is in a good location to activate the AI system, the self-driving loop will start. In this loop, as happens in the remote control loop,

Fig. 4.2 Sequence diagram for remote driving. There are three main loops: the receive-video-from-the-car loop; the remote-car-control loop; and the self-driving loop. The steps that compose each loop are: (1) connect to the video client; (2) connect to the video server; (3) and (4) connect to the car’s camera; (5), (6), and (7) send video to the client; (8) display the video on the remote station; (9) connect to the control server; (10) connect to the control client; (11) and (12) joystick commands are sent; (13) the commands are sent to the control module; (14) remote driver’s commands are sent through the CAN bus; (15) and (16) connect with the control server; (17) and (18) control commands are sent; (19) the AI perception daemon is started; (20) IMU lectures are sent to the AI perception module; (21) car motion commands are planned; (22) Plan steering wheel and acceleration commands; 23 planned commands are sent to the control daemon; (24) planned commands are sent through the CAN bus.

the first and second steps are that the driver connects to the remote control server (arrow 15 in Fig. 4.2), and the remote control client connects (arrow 16 in 4.2) to the remote control server, and notifies it that the AI is going to take control, by activating the perception module (arrows 17, 18, and 19 in 4.2). After that, the next step is to start sending the visual information from the camera acquisition module (arrow 21 in Fig. 4.2), and radar information from the IMU acquisition module (arrow 20 in Fig. 4.2). All the information is fed to the planning module (arrow 23 in 4.2): this module will process the information sent from the perception, and its outputs will be the acceleration and steering wheel commands to keep the passengers safe. Once the commands have been created, it is necessary to convert them into CAN messages (arrow 24 in Fig. 4.2).

Steps 14 and 24 in Fig. 4.2 do exactly the same: they process and convert acceleration and steering wheel human-interpretable commands into acceleration and steering wheel car-interpretable commands (CAN messages), which is the reason why the Panda hardware is used, as that is exactly what it does. The Panda hardware enabled the sending and receiving of signals by USB directly to/from the available buses in the vehicle. The Panda hardware supported three CAN buses, two LIN buses, and one General Motors Local Area Network (GMLAN), and we used it to submit our messages to the car CAN bus.

4.4 Implementation

Our proposed architecture was built on top of the Openpilot software. Openpilot is an open-source, camera-based driver assistance system that mainly performs the following functions: adaptive cruise control; automated lane centering; forward collision warning; and lane departure warning. Openpilot supports a large variety of car makers, models, and model years. Depending on the year model of the vehicle, Openpilot can control the car laterally (steering wheel commands) or laterally and longitudinally (acceleration commands).

Our system was based on Openpilot 0.8.9, and employed a Toyota Prius Hybrid 2019. All the software used in the car was run on an HP Pavilion Laptop with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10750H CPU @ 2.60 GHz and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2060 with Max-Q Design. The computer used in the remote driving station was equipped with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-770K CPU @ 4.20 GHz, and an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080.

Due to the year in which our model was produced, Openpilot only had the lateral control (steering wheel) of our vehicle. Our car had an ECU called the Driver Support Unit (DSU), which controlled the longitudinal (accelerator and brakes) motion. In vehicles where Openpilot controls the longitudinal motion only, it relies on the vehicle's adaptive cruise control (acceleration commands) for longitudinal control. Our Toyota's adaptive cruise control could only be activated when driving above 25 mph. To allow Openpilot to take not only the lateral control but also the longitudinal, i.e., to allow Openpilot to intercept and send acceleration and braking CAN messages via the bus, it was necessary to replace the DSU

with a Smart DSU, which is used to provide longitudinal control on Toyota vehicles that otherwise do not have Openpilot-supported longitudinal control.

In addition to the computer and the Smart DSU [100], further hardware was required. As Openpilot [28] is a camera-based system, and the pilot needs visual feedback from the vehicle's surroundings, a camera was needed. The camera we used to carry out the experiments was a Logitech HD Pro Webcam C920. The maximum resolution this camera allows is 1080×720 at 30 fps; its focus type is automatic, and it comes with a universal clip, which we used to attach a tool designed by us to the windshield (see Fig. 4.3): this was intended to provide the remote driver with information as like as possible to that which a driver inside the vehicle would receive. Although the use of more than one camera would have provided more detailed context awareness, such information was not necessary for this focused study, and might have incurred additional delays in the transmitting and processing of the video streams between the car and the remote workstation. The single-camera proved to be sufficient for this remote driving use case.

In order for the remote driver to send the necessary commands to the vehicle, a joystick was used. The specific joystick was an XBOX One wired controller.

As noted above, another important piece of hardware was used, called Panda [101, 102]. Panda's software is 100% open-source. There are three different models of the Panda: red, black, and white. In our experiments, we used the black model, which is a universal interface for a car. The black Panda model helped to connect the computer directly to the car, enabling the sending and receiving of signals by WiFi or USB directly to/from the available buses in the vehicle. The black Panda model supported three CAN buses, two LIN buses, and one GMLAN.

All the tools explained in this section were prototyped and deployed in a real testbed. Fig. 4.3 shows all the hardware elements mounted and being used in our Toyota Prius on the right side, along with the remote station used to drive the car remotely, on the left side.

Fig. 4.3 Remote station (**left**) and on-board station (**right**). On-board station's components: (1) laptop; (2) Panda (USB to CAN); (3) webcam; (4) OBD-II Port; and (5) SmartDSU.

Extension of Openpilot

In this subsection, the authors explain the main differences, modifications, and extensions made to the original Openpilot architecture.

Firstly, to be clear, Openpilot's original architecture did not support remote driving: to achieve this, it was necessary to give the remote driver visual information about what was happening around the car, and about the state of the road at every moment. A lack of visual information for the remote driver can result in fatal consequences for the passengers: for this reason, we extended the original architecture, to allow the sending of video from the car to the remote station, using an NGINX media server, where clients and servers made use of Real-Time Media Protocol (RTMP) to perform the delivery of the video. The onboard computer had an NGINX client installed, which streamed the video to the NGINX server, located in the cloud infrastructure, and then the remote pilot also connected to the NGINX server, enabling the reception of the video. Both the NGINX client and the server were installed using Docker containers. There was an image for the clients and another one for the server. The use of this tool made it very easy to scale the application and its deployment.

Additionally, the original architecture did not allow switching from the joystick mode to the AI control mode: this is now possible in our proposed architecture. The remote driver sets the option for the mode of car control from the remote station: then, such a message is

sent through the network and received by the control module in the onboard computer. The signal received indicates to the Control Module whether the AI control module or the remote driving control module should be activated: when one is working, the other one is not.

The Openpilot system displays a file in which it is specified that the different messages and their corresponding publishers and subscribers indicate the information shared between modules and daemons. In the original system, this is done using Cap'n Proto files: in such files, the messages are strongly typed, and are not self-describing. In order to allow the switch between AI or remote driving control, we modified the original approach, creating a new type of message that is shared between the different control modules involved: the main control module, the AI control, and the remote driving control.

The authors believe that this could significantly contribute to future mobility, as current autonomous-driving systems do not allow full self-driving features: the supervision of the driver is always needed. Despite this, there is a possibility of combining remote driving in environments unsuitable or difficult for self-driving systems with AI control in environments suitable for them. The architecture is proposed herein, with which to make this possible.

4.5 Results and Empirical Validation

4.5.1 Testbed

In computer sciences, there are three different types of real-time systems: hard; firm; and soft. Hard real-time systems have a strict deadline for responding to events, and for ensuring tasks are carried out on time. It is critical that each action takes place within the specified time frame; otherwise, there will be a system failure, which could result in damage to property, or endangering lives. In a firm real-time system, some deadlines can be missed, which may degrade the quality of the task, but will not automatically result in system failure. Sub-tasks that are completed after the deadline are worthless, and will not be used. If several deadlines are missed, the system may cease to function properly. With soft real-time systems, if a deadline is missed, the system will not fail, and the result of a task may still be useful;

however, the value of the completed task may reduce over time, which will lower the system's performance.

The word 'vehicle' is defined as "a machine, usually with wheels and an engine, used for transporting people or goods, especially on land" by the Cambridge Dictionary. As a vehicle transports people, it is very important that the system comports as a hard real-time system, in order to preserve the security and integrity of all the passengers in the vehicle.

In our experiments, we wanted to study the feasibility of using remote driving technology, in which the communication between the car and the remote driver is done by wireless and mobile networks. To do so, and as remote driving systems need to be a firm real-time system, we took different time measurements, to establish whether this system would be valid for use, or if more research needed to be done. In the first of the experiments, we measured the delay between the moment the video was sent and its reception by the remote station, when both stations were connected to the same WiFi in a local network (see the top of Fig. 4.4). We used a Xiaomi Redmi Note 9 Pro smartphone, with Android version 10.0 acting as a hotspot. In the second experiment, we used a PC with a public IP as the remote system, and the in-car system connected to the internet using a mobile network (tethering). Each of the experiments was carried out by sending two different video resolutions, which were 1280×720 and 640×480 pixels. A Huawei E8372h-320 4G/5G Dongle at 150 Mbits/s was used, to allow us to use the UK commercial network, O2. Due to the current availability of commercial cellular network coverage in our testing area, 4G/LTE provided the connectivity between the car and the remote system in this remote driving setting. Our research focused mainly on the realistic design, implementation, and testing of a remote driving system, using a real car connected to a commercial cellular network, whether 4G or 5G. The experimental results have shown that even the current 4G can provide reasonable performance to enable such use, and the deployment of 5G should certainly improve the performance, which could be further explored in our future work.

Experiment 1 (see Section 4.5.2) created a best-case scenario, in terms of the performance of both systems (the remote and in-car station) being connected to the same local network, such that the latency was lowest for this ideal setting. The out-of-car remote driving was the

realistic setting, and the performance measured in this setting was compared to the best-case scenario: by this comparison, we understood the gap between the two scenarios, and the target that had to be achieved for the best-case scenario.

Both experiments were carried out in a 2019 Toyota Prius Hybrid. The chosen route for the experiments was 14 miles long, and ran from the University of the West of Scotland facilities in Paisley (UK) to the city's outskirts, mixing urban, secondary roads, and a highway: this way, we could experience how the system reacted when there was a good connection (urban areas) or a poorer connection (secondary roads). The scheme for the route can be seen in Fig. 4.5. It is important to note that during the experiments there were always two drivers: the remote driver and the onboard driver. The onboard driver was ready at every moment to take control of the car if delay was excessive or if there was any other problem between the remote station and the car. The results shown in Sections 4.5.2 and 4.5.3 are the subset of the chosen route, where the onboard driver did not intervene at all in driving the vehicle. For 82% of the time during the experiments, there was no onboard driver intervention; however, there were complex traffic situations during the experiments (representing 12% of the time), in which the intervention of the in-car driver was required.

In each of the experiments, the same three time delays were measured: the first measurement was of how much time elapsed from the moment the joystick was pressed until the command was sent to the network (see 1 in Fig. 4.4 for a graphical explanation)—from now on, that time will be referred to as Time 1; the second measurement was of how much time the message spent in the network (see 2 in Fig. 4.4)—from now on, that time will be referred to as Time 2; the third measurement was of the time elapsed between the receipt of message by the car, and it being sent via the CAN Bus (see 3 in Fig. 4.4)—from now on, that time will be referred to as Time 3.

For both of the experiments, the results related to the delays present in the joystick commands and the video stream delivery were studied: in both of them, the technologies used were the same. For video streaming, a video module, using the Real-time Media Protocol (RTMP) in an NGINX server, was installed. The server was then virtualized in a

Fig. 4.4 Graphical representation of In-car Remote Driving Experiment (**top**) and Teleremote Driving Experiment (**bottom**).

docker container. After the virtualization, the in-car system started sending video to the server, using FFmpeg. The video was requested by the remote station system, using FFmpeg.

4.5.2 In-Car Remote Driving Experiment

As can be seen at the top of Fig. 4.4, in this experiment both systems—the remote tele-driving and the in-car—were connected to each other using a local network. To create that local network, we used a smartphone as a mobile hotspot. For these experiments, the mobile phone did not have any Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) card in it, and so it did not have access to the internet, but it could act as an access point to create a local network.

As shown in Table 4.1, for this case, the maximum delay that could have been experienced was 303.32 ms, which was the sum of three different times: 0.76 ms (time 1); 286.45 ms (time 2); and 16.11 ms (time 3). As expected, the network imposed a significant delay. The total delay for this worst-case scenario slightly exceeded the real-time constraint, widely

Fig. 4.5 Chosen route for the experiments. The section of the route where both drivers took control of the vehicle is marked in red. The section of the route where it was only the remote driver who had control over the car is marked in blue.

established at 250 ms for video delivery. Nonetheless, on average, the total delay achieved was 25.39 ms ($0.17 + 24.94 + 0.28$), fulfilling the real-time constraint.

Table 4.1 Maximum and mean delays for the joystick commands delivery in each of the experiments. Delays expressed in ms.

Experiment	Joystick to Command		Networking		Received to CAN		Total	
	Max.	Mean	Max.	Mean	Max.	Mean	Max.	Mean
In-car Experiment	0.76	0.17 ± 0.0023	286.45	24.94 ± 12.35	16.11	0.28 ± 0.58	303.32	25.39 ± 13.38
Tele-remote Experiment	0.95	0.17 ± 0.034	318.73	31.34 ± 168.07	24.89	0.27 ± 0.28	344.57	31.78 ± 97.12

Regarding the video streaming, Table 4.2 shows the results achieved. When the video was sent with a resolution of 1280×720 pixels, we were able to receive around 10 fps. This video stream was sent with an average bandwidth of 1.0 Mbits/s and 202.7 packets/s: for this average case, the video delay was 273 ms. On the other hand, when sending video of lower quality, 640×480 pixels, we were able to receive 25 fps, which was sent with an average bandwidth of 0.25 Mbits/s and 105.7 packets/s. The delay achieved was 173 ms.

Table 4.2 Video streaming statistics results for both of the experiments.

Experiments	Resolution	FPS	Avg. bytes/s	Avg. packets/s	Avg. delay (ms)
In-car Remote Driving Experiment	640 × 480	25	32 k	105.7	173
	1280 × 720	10	125 k	202.7	273
Teleremote Driving Experiment	640 × 480	25	22 k	47.3	563
	1280 × 720	15	67 k	129.1	648

4.5.3 Teleremote Driving Experiment

This experiment was the closest one to what a real scenario in production would look like. The layout for this experiment is shown graphically at the bottom of Fig. 4.4. In this case, the remote system was a computer with a public IP address, and the in-car system (the HP laptop named in Section 4.4) used a Huawei E8372 4G/5G dongle to get an internet connection using the O2 network.

Regarding the joystick commands delivery, Table 4.1 shows that the maximum delay experienced was 344.57 ms, which was the sum of 0.95 ms (Time 1), 318.73 ms (Time 2), and 0.27 ms (Time 3). In the same way as in the previous experiment, the significant delay was caused by the network. Furthermore, the total time delay for the joystick command delivery exceeded the real-time constraint.

With regard to the video transmission, for the second experiment, when a video with a resolution of 1280 × 720 pixels was sent, we were able to receive the video at a frame rate of 15 fps. This stream was sent with an average bandwidth of 0.53 Mbits/s and 129.1 packets/s. In this case, the mean delay was 648 ms; nonetheless, when a video with a resolution of 640 × 480 pixels had been sent, the stream was received at 25 fps, and had been sent with an average band of 0.17 Mbits/s and 47.3 packets/s. The average delay for this last case was 563 ms. Note that, even though the results are counter-intuitive, there were several factors associated with coverage, the position of the car, other mobiles sharing the same antenna, and other aspects that had a direct impact on the results achieved, and our intention was to test a real commercial network.

4.5.4 Delay Comparison between Experiments

In order to achieve real-time communications for a remote-driving system, the delay between the remote station and the in-car system needed to be less than 250 ms. We were not concerned about this high latency, as several trials across Europe had already achieved less than 50 ms [103, 104]: pushing this level of latency to the whole public mobile network is a matter of time. By comparing Fig. 4.6–4.8, it can be appreciated that, as expected, the biggest delay came from the network.

Regarding the joystick delays, it can be seen that the delay between the joystick being pressed and the command being sent over the network (Fig.

Fig. 4.6 Time in ms from when the joystick was pressed until the command was sent over the network.

Regarding video streaming over the network, it is a demanding task, and the results prove it. By observing Table 4.2, it can be seen that the 250 ms delay constraint was not

Fig. 4.7 Time in ms of the command in the network.

accomplished. When streaming a 1280×720 pixels video, the delay was 273 ms when using a WiFi hotspot, and 648 ms when using the public 4G/5G network: however, 648ms is still a high delay if the objective is to drive a car remotely. The main problem regarding the delay in the second experiment was that the internet connection varied depending on the location of the vehicle. It is worth noting that, to obtain these results, we used a regular SIM card from the Giffgaff operator, which used the O2 4G/5G (depending on the car's location coverage) mobile network. In order to reduce the existing high delay in the video streaming, we reduced the video resolution from 1280×720 to 640×480 pixels: by doing so, we were able to reduce the delay from 273 ms to 173 ms for the in-car experiment, and from 648 ms to 563 ms for the tele-driving experiment. For the experiments, the delay reduction was about 100 ms: however, this was not enough to be considered real-time. Thus, despite the reduction, the delay made it very difficult to drive the car, as there was a lack of visual

information in real time. These results prove that the technology is already mature, but that the network is not yet able to provide such capabilities.

Fig. 4.8 Time in ms from when the command was received until it was sent through the CAN bus.

4.6 Conclusions

This paper focused on achieving remote vehicle driving to fill the current gaps in autonomous driving, as the majority of new cars are still at SAE Level 2, and there are gaps in assisting teleoperation-use cases.

There is a lack of available public-domain solutions that enable the control of the car through the network. In this paper, we have explained the proposed design and implementation of a realistic framework for remote driving. Our motivation was that there is little

research work based on real cars rather than on mere simulations, and simulations do not really expose the challenges and requirements.

We empirically validated the proposed framework implementation for remote car driving, using real-world facilities. For our experiments, we employed a 2019 Toyota Prius Hybrid commercial car and a Huawei E8372 4G dongle connected to the O2 UK mobile network.

In our performance evaluation based on the experiments, we demonstrated that the joystick commands could be sent from the remote control station to the car in about 32 ms, thereby allowing real-time remote control of the car. Meanwhile, the average delay for the video streaming was 648 ms when sending 1280×720 pixels videos, and 563 ms when sending 640×480 pixels video. In both cases, the delay needed to be reduced, to allow real-time visual operations, which meant reducing the delay below 250 ms, according to our trials. We expect that this delay requirement could be met by the new generation of mobile networks.

The total mean delay for joystick commands, networking, and video streaming combined in the In-car experiment for 640×480 resolution was $25.39 \text{ ms} + 24.94 \text{ ms} + 173 \text{ ms} = 223.33 \text{ ms}$, while for 1280×720 resolution, it was $25.39 \text{ ms} + 31.34 \text{ ms} + 273 \text{ ms} = 329.73 \text{ ms}$. Similarly, in the Tele-remote experiment, the total mean delay for 640×480 resolution was $31.78 \text{ ms} + 31.34 \text{ ms} + 563 \text{ ms} = 626.12 \text{ ms}$, and for 1280×720 resolution, it was $31.78 \text{ ms} + 129.1 \text{ ms} + 648 \text{ ms} = 808.88 \text{ ms}$.

The maximum delay for the total system in the In-car experiment was 303.32 ms (joystick + networking + video) for 640×480 resolution, and 344.57 ms for 1280×720 resolution. For the Tele-remote experiment, the maximum total delay was 344.57 ms for 640×480 resolution and 808.88 ms for 1280×720 resolution.

Nevertheless, our work enabled the exposure of the control of the car through the network, more specifically the O2 UK 4G mobile network; moreover, it showed the performance of a remote driving system in a real-world car, rather than in a simulated one, as most of the existing work has relied on producing an empirical validation and performance analysis associated with the control system of the car.

The security and reliability of the different modules that compose the proposed architecture for a remote driving system have not been studied in this work. The main intention of the authors was to prove the suitability of the system, by carrying out experiments in real-world operational environments rather than in simulated environments. However, the security and reliability of the system need to be studied in future work, as it is of vital importance for ensuring the safety of passengers in remote-driving vehicles.

4.7 Limitations

While chapter demonstrates the feasibility of remote car driving and provides valuable insights into the performance of such a system in real-world scenarios, several limitations warrant consideration.

Firstly, the experiments highlighted the critical impact of network latency and reliability on the overall performance, particularly in video streaming. The reliance on commercial 4G/5G networks introduced variable latency, sometimes exceeding the threshold for real-time perception, impacting the remote driver's ability to respond promptly to the environment. While advancements in network infrastructure and 5G technology may mitigate this issue, further research is needed to explore solutions for ensuring consistent and low-latency communication, potentially through specialized networks or adaptive streaming protocols.

Additionally, the current implementation prioritizes functionality over security. The remote control and video streaming components currently lack robust security measures, leaving them susceptible to potential cyberattacks that could compromise the safety and integrity of the remote driving system. Addressing this vulnerability by implementing comprehensive security protocols, encryption, and authentication mechanisms is paramount for the safe and secure deployment of remote driving technology.

Furthermore, the limited scope of the experiments, conducted using a specific car model (Toyota Prius Hybrid 2019) and a particular hardware setup, restricts the generalizability of the findings. The system's compatibility and performance may vary with different vehicle models and hardware configurations. Additionally, the study focused on a single driver and

a specific route, necessitating further research with a broader user population and diverse driving scenarios to understand the system's performance and usability in various real-world contexts.

Lastly, while the research primarily focused on the technical aspects of remote driving, the user experience and human factors are equally important. Future studies should investigate the cognitive load on remote drivers, the impact of latency on decision-making, and the overall user experience to ensure safe, comfortable, and user-friendly remote driving operations. Addressing these limitations will pave the way for the development of mature, reliable, and secure remote driving systems that can contribute meaningfully to the future of transportation.

Chapter 5

Off-road Human Detection Algorithms: Assessing Performance in Challenging Terrains with new Dataset

5.1 Introduction

Off-road operation teams are in a perpetual quest to refine their operational strategies. For example, for Search and Rescue (SAR) operations, the teams are constantly exploring innovative techniques to expedite the location of individuals lost in remote wilderness environments. Traditionally, canine units have been the frontline resource in these endeavors. However, the efficacy of this method is tempered by the time investment required for training and deployment, as well as the logistical constraints associated with coordinating multiple dog teams. As such, a pressing need exists for alternative approaches that can supplement or even supplant traditional search methods. Human-assisted search methodologies represent one such avenue, relying on the concerted efforts of SAR personnel, volunteers, and community members to scour expansive areas in search of the lost individual. While this approach holds promise in its potential to leverage human intuition and adaptability, it is inherently labor-intensive and dependent on the availability of sufficient manpower [105]. Consequently, there is an ongoing drive within the SAR community to explore technological solutions

that can enhance search efficiency and effectiveness, particularly in scenarios where time is of the essence and lives hang in the balance. In recent years, the advent of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) has revolutionized SAR operations by providing aerial reconnaissance capabilities. UAV equipped with high-resolution cameras transmit real-time images of the search area, enabling SAR teams to cover vast expanses of terrain efficiently. Furthermore, the application of object detection algorithms on the images captured by UAV allows for automated analysis and identification of potential targets, further streamlining the search process and increasing the likelihood of locating missing individuals [106–109]. This integration of UAV technology with advanced object detection algorithms represents a significant advancement in SAR operations, offering a cost-effective and scalable solution to the challenges posed by remote wilderness environments.

Nonetheless, alternative strategies must be considered to augment SAR operations in challenging scenarios where weather conditions, such as poor visibility or strong winds, impede the use of UAV. Ground robots emerge as a viable solution in such circumstances, offering the capability to access remote and difficult terrains where human intervention may be impractical or unsafe. Leveraging ground robots equipped with multiple sensors, SAR teams can navigate rugged landscapes and search areas inaccessible to humans, thereby expanding the scope and effectiveness of search efforts. Despite their potential, there remains a notable scarcity of research exploring the integration of ground robots into SAR operations, particularly in the context of off-road scenarios. Additionally, existing literature on SAR often overlooks the utilization of multi-sensor systems, which have demonstrated efficacy in diverse environments but remain under-explored in off-road settings. Addressing these gaps in research presents an opportunity to enhance SAR capabilities by leveraging the complementary strengths of ground robots and multi-sensor systems to improve detection and localization of missing persons in challenging conditions.

In summary, the main contributions of this study are as follows:

- The paper introduces a novel dataset, the UWS off-road Dataset, specifically tailored for off-road environments, filling a crucial gap in the research community. This dataset

provides valuable ground truth annotations for human detection in challenging terrains, enabling researchers to develop and evaluate algorithms for off-road scenarios.

- The paper conducts a thorough evaluation of human detection algorithms using both the established on-road KITTI dataset and the proposed UWS Off-road Dataset. By comparing the performance of fusion-based and point-cloud-based models across different datasets and evaluation metrics, the paper provides insights into the effectiveness of these algorithms in various environments.
- Through the experimental results, the paper offers valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of different human detection algorithms. This analysis aids researchers and practitioners in selecting suitable algorithms for specific applications and environments, advancing the field of computer vision and autonomous driving systems.
- Additionally, the paper conducts an analysis of the inference speed of the tested algorithms, providing practical considerations for real-world deployment. This aspect contributes to the understanding of algorithm efficiency and scalability, which are critical for the implementation of human detection systems in autonomous vehicles and other applications.
- Lastly, the findings presented in the paper pave the way for future research directions in human detection and autonomous navigation. By highlighting areas for improvement and identifying promising approaches, the paper stimulates further exploration and innovation in the field, ultimately driving advancements in safety and mobility technologies.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 5.2 presents 3D object detection algorithms used in the experiments. Section 5.3 describes the datasets used in the experiments. Section 5.4 outlines our experimental results and analysis. Last, in Section 5.5, the conclusions of the investigation are presented and discussed.

5.2 Models

In this section, we delve into the models utilized in the empirical analysis carried out in our experiments. These models serve as the backbone of algorithmic implementations, shaping the efficacy and performance of 3D object detection methodologies. We categorize the models into two distinct subsections: Point Cloud Based Algorithms and Fusion Algorithms. Through an exploration of these models, we unravel the intricacies of their architectures, functionalities, and contributions to the advancement of 3D object detection technology.

5.2.1 Point-Cloud Based Models

The Point-Cloud Based Models section delves into innovative methodologies tailored for 3D object detection tasks leveraging data from individual sensors. Among these models, Part-A2net and PointPillars emerge as pioneering solutions, each capitalizing on distinct strategies to extract meaningful features from LiDAR point cloud data.

Part-A2

The Part-A2net model (see Fig. 5.1) is structured around two key stages: the part-aware stage-I and the part-aggregation stage-II, each playing a crucial role in enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of object detection tasks. In the part-aware stage-I, the model leverages free-of-charge intra-object location labels and foreground labels derived from ground-truth 3D box annotations to predict precise intra-object part locations. By incorporating this information, the model not only generates high-quality 3D proposals but also improves the overall quality of predicted bounding boxes.

A notable feature of the Part-A2net model is the introduction of two distinct strategies for 3D proposal generation: the anchor-free scheme and the anchor-based scheme. The anchor-free approach offers a lightweight and memory-efficient solution by directly generating 3D bounding box proposals through foreground point segmentation and proposal generation simultaneously. In contrast, the anchor-based strategy utilizes pre-defined 3D anchor boxes on downsampled bird-view feature maps to achieve higher recall rates, albeit with increased

memory and computational requirements. This flexibility in proposal generation strategies allows the model to adapt to different detection scenarios and optimize performance based on specific requirements.

The RoI-aware point cloud pooling module, a novel component of the Part-A2net framework, plays a pivotal role in grouping predicted intra-object part locations and encoding geometry-specific features of each 3D proposal. By normalizing diverse 3D proposals to a unified coordinate system, this module effectively captures geometric information and enhances feature encoding, thereby improving the model's ability to discriminate between object classes and accurately localize objects in complex scenes.

Moreover, the part-aggregation stage-II refines box locations by exploring the spatial relationships of pooled intra-object part locations. This stage focuses on capturing the intricate geometric details of object parts to accurately score the boxes and refine their positions, leading to enhanced detection accuracy and robustness. The comprehensive design of the Part-A2net model, coupled with its innovative components and advanced functionalities.

Fig. 5.1 Architecture of the Part-A2 model presented (replotted based on [6]).

Point Pillars

The PointPillars model (see Fig. 5.2) presents a pioneering approach to encoding point clouds for downstream object detection tasks. Departing from traditional fixed encoders or

data-learned encoders, PointPillars harnesses PointNets to derive a representation of point clouds structured in vertical columns, referred to as pillars. This novel architecture enables the model to fully capture the information embedded in the point cloud data, empowering it to directly learn features from the data without dependence on pre-defined encodings. Operating on pillars rather than voxels, PointPillars obviates the need for manual tuning of vertical direction binning, rendering the process notably more efficient and effective.

One of the paramount advantages of PointPillars lies in its adeptness at striking a delicate balance between speed and accuracy, substantially outperforming previous encoders in both aspects. By extracting features directly from the point cloud data, PointPillars can exploit the entirety of the information encapsulated within the point cloud, thereby enhancing accuracy in object detection tasks. Moreover, the model’s efficient computation on GPUs, facilitated by formulating critical operations as 2D convolutions, further bolsters its performance and speed. PointPillars operates at a remarkable speed of 62 Hz.

Fig. 5.2 Architecture of the Point Pillars model (replotted based on [7]).

5.2.2 Fusion Models

The Fusion Models section explores innovative methodologies for integrating sensor data to enhance 3D object detection capabilities. In this context, Frustum PointNets and EPNet represent two leading approaches, each leveraging distinct sensor modalities and fusion strategies to achieve accurate and robust detection results. Frustum PointNets exemplify an advanced fusion model that seamlessly integrates 2D object detection strengths with sophisticated 3D deep learning techniques, tailored to handle frustum-based point clouds.

Conversely, EPNet introduces the LiDAR-guided Image Fusion (LI-Fusion) module, which establishes fine-grained point-wise correspondence between raw point cloud data and camera images, enhancing the fusion of Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) depth information with semantic features extracted from images. Through detailed exploration and analysis, this section elucidates the operational principles, architectural designs, and performance evaluations of these fusion models, showcasing their pivotal role in advancing the field of sensor fusion for perception tasks.

Frustum PointNets

Frustum PointNets represent a cutting-edge methodology for 3D object detection, effectively integrating the strengths of 2D object detection frameworks with sophisticated 3D deep learning algorithms. Drawing inspiration from PointNet and PointNet++, the model's architecture undergoes tailored modifications to adeptly handle frustum-based point clouds. A frustum is the part of a solid, such as a cone or pyramid, contained between the base and a plane parallel to the base that intersects the solid. Through the incorporation of point embedding layers, max pooling layers, and per-point classification Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), the architecture adeptly aggregates information from both global features and individual points. Noteworthy is the inclusion of an additional link for class one-hot vector, facilitating the seamless integration of semantics gleaned from RGB images into instance segmentation and bounding box estimation tasks. Augmenting the model's capabilities, the utilization of LiDAR intensity as a fourth channel, alongside XYZ coordinates, bolsters its proficiency in processing and interpreting intricate 3D data.

The operational framework of Frustum PointNets unfolds through a multi-step procedure commencing with the generation of 2D bounding boxes via a 2D object detector on RGB images. Subsequently, these 2D bounding boxes undergo transformation into 3D frustums, delineating the 3D search spaces for objects within the scene. The model then extracts point clouds within these frustums, normalizing coordinates to enhance translational invariance, before proceeding to predict object categories and oriented 3D bounding boxes. By synergizing information from both RGB images and point clouds, the model achieves precise localization

of objects in 3D space. Notably, coordinate transformations and frustum rotations play a pivotal role in ensuring the accuracy of 3D detection results, underscoring the significance of these preprocessing steps in bolstering the model’s overall performance.

The Frustum PointNets methodology presents a versatile framework applicable to diverse scenarios encompassing both outdoor and indoor 3D object detection tasks, as evidenced by its state-of-the-art performance on benchmark datasets like SUN-RGBD. Through strategic integration of 2D and 3D object detection capabilities, the model exhibits robustness in handling challenges such as occlusion and sparse point clouds. Architectural design choices, including hierarchical feature learning and multi-scale feature adaptation, substantially contribute to the model’s superior performance across tasks like instance segmentation and box estimation. In summation, Frustum PointNets represent a sophisticated and efficacious solution for accurately detecting and localizing objects within point clouds, heralding promising applications in fields such as autonomous driving and augmented reality.

Fig. 5.3 Architecture of the Frustum Pointnets model (replotted based on [8]), where N, M represent the number of points present in a frustum and C the number of features extracted.

EPNet

The EPNet model architecture introduces a LiDAR-guided Image Fusion (LI-Fusion) module designed to enhance the fusion of point cloud data from LiDAR sensors with semantic features extracted from camera images for improved 3D object detection. Unlike traditional fusion methods that rely on perspective projection and voxelization to generate Bird’s Eye View (BEV) data, the LI-Fusion module establishes a fine-grained point-wise correspondence between raw point cloud data and camera images. This approach eliminates the need for

complex procedures for BEV data generation, thereby preserving the original geometric structure without information loss.

The LI-Fusion module addresses the challenge of integrating LiDAR and camera image data, which possess distinct characteristics. While LiDAR points provide depth and geometric information essential for understanding 3D scenes, they are sparse, unordered, and unevenly distributed. On the other hand, camera images offer rich semantic features but lack depth information. By fusing these complementary data sources, EPNet aims to improve the accuracy of 3D object detection tasks.

One of the key innovations of EPNet is the adaptive estimation of the importance of image semantic features during the fusion process. This allows the model to selectively enhance useful image features while suppressing interfering information that may hinder object detection performance. By establishing a point-wise correspondence between LiDAR and camera image data, EPNet overcomes the limitations of previous fusion methods that rely on 2D bounding box annotations and approximate correspondence between voxel and image features.

Furthermore, EPNet incorporates a Consistency Enforcing (CE) loss to improve the consistency between classification and localization confidence in 3D object detection. This loss function helps to address the challenge of accurate localization in sparse LiDAR data, enhancing the overall performance of the model.

In summary, EPNet presents a novel approach to fusing LiDAR and camera image data for 3D object detection, leveraging the strengths of each sensor modality while mitigating their respective limitations. The LI-Fusion module and CE loss contribute to the model's superior performance on benchmark datasets such as KITTI and SUN-RGBD, showcasing the effectiveness of the proposed architecture in advancing the field of sensor fusion for perception tasks.

Fig. 5.4 Architecture of the EPNet model (replotted based on [9]).

5.3 Datasets

Datasets play a pivotal role in the advancement of 3D object detection algorithms, providing the necessary groundwork for research, development, and evaluation. This section introduces two significant datasets that form the foundation for the experimentation and validation of the algorithms presented in section 5.2: the on-road KITTI dataset and the UWS Off-road dataset. While the KITTI dataset serves as a widely recognized benchmark for autonomous driving research, the Off-road dataset represents our own contribution, filling a crucial gap in the research community, specifically tailored to off-road scenarios, comprising LiDAR point clouds and images.

5.3.1 Kitti

The KITTI (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and Toyota Technological Institute) [27] dataset stands as a cornerstone in the field of autonomous driving research, offering a comprehensive benchmark for evaluating 3D object detection algorithms. Comprising a diverse array of urban scenarios captured through LiDAR and camera sensors mounted on driving vehicles, the KITTI dataset provides rich and realistic data for training, validation, and testing purposes. This dataset encompasses a wide range of scenes in urban environments. These scenes include annotated instances of various object classes, such as cars, humans, cyclists, and more, along with ground truth annotations for precise evaluation of detection performance. However, in this work we only use one of the provided classes (pedestrian), as our goal is to apply 3D object detection algorithms for ease SAR operations.

One of the key strengths of the KITTI dataset lies in its multimodal nature, featuring data captured from both LiDAR and camera sensors. LiDAR point cloud data offers precise 3D information about the surrounding environment, facilitating accurate object localization and spatial understanding. Concurrently, camera images provide rich visual context, aiding in object recognition and classification tasks. There are 2 splits in the dataset: test (7518 images and corresponding point clouds) and train (7481 images and corresponding point clouds).

5.3.2 Proposed off-road dataset

In response to the research community's predominant focus on urban environments for autonomous driving applications, a significant gap emerges when it comes to datasets specifically tailored to off-road scenarios. Recognizing this void and the pressing need for comprehensive datasets to address the unique challenges posed by off-road driving, we present the UWS Off-road dataset. Unlike existing datasets that predominantly capture urban settings, the UWS Off-road dataset fills a crucial niche by providing a curated collection of data captured in off-road environments such as rural landscapes, forest trails, and wilderness areas. The aim of this dataset is to facilitate research and development in autonomous driving beyond traditional urban settings. Through the integration of LiDAR point clouds and optical images, the UWS Off-road dataset offers researchers a valuable resource to explore and innovate in the realm of off-road object detection and perception.

Spanning geographical regions between Alicante Province (Spain) and the Paisley area (UK), the UWS Off-road dataset encompasses diverse terrain types and environmental conditions, providing researchers with a wide-ranging dataset for exploration and experimentation in off-road autonomous driving scenarios. Consisting of 2 splits, namely test (465 images and point cloud pairs) and train (1450 images and point cloud pairs), this dataset was tailored with the aim of supporting SAR groups in challenging off-road environments. The UWS Off-road dataset focuses on human detection, aiming to aid SAR missions by providing realistic scenarios encountered in wilderness areas. It is for this reason that, at this stage, it only contains one class: human. For the labelling process, we utilized the Xtreme1 labelling tool [110].

Fig. 5.5 provides a comparative illustration of example images from our off-road dataset and the KITTI dataset. This Fig. highlights the significant domain differences between the datasets, emphasizing the increased complexity and variability inherent in off-road environments. Off-road scenarios are characterized by higher entropy due to irregular terrain, diverse vegetation, and unpredictable obstacles, making information extraction and object detection more challenging compared to structured urban environments. In contrast, urban settings typically feature more uniform and predictable structures, such as buildings and roads, which facilitate more straightforward data interpretation and algorithmic processing.

Fig. 5.5 Examples of the datasets used for the experiments: the proposed UWS Off-road (left) and KITTI (right).

Sensors

This dataset utilizes a Velodyne VLP-32C LiDAR and a ZED 2 camera, ensuring high-quality data acquisition across both point cloud and image modalities. This combination of sensors enables comprehensive perception capabilities, capturing detailed 3D information and rich visual context essential for robust object detection and scene understanding in off-road environments. As can be seen in Fig. 5.6, the sensors are attached to a metal frame. This metal frame is adaptable and allows the sensors to be mounted on any vehicle or ground robot.

On the one hand, the VLP-32C LiDAR counts with 32 laser beams, the sensor is equipped to comprehensively scan its surroundings, enabling detailed perception across a broad spatial

Fig. 5.6 Sensors and metal frame used for the data acquisition of the presented dataset.

range. Capable of detecting objects up to 200 meters away, it offers considerable coverage for distant terrain analysis. In terms of field of view, the sensor boasts a horizontal span of 360 degrees, facilitating a panoramic view of the surrounding environment. Additionally, it provides a vertical perspective spanning 40 degrees, allowing for comprehensive scene understanding. With a resolution of 0.1 degrees, the sensor captures data with fine-grained detail, crucial for precise environmental mapping and object detection. Furthermore, its high data acquisition rate of approximately 1.3 million points per second ensures rapid and continuous data collection, essential for real-time applications. Operating at a frequency of 10 Hz, the sensor maintains a consistent pace of data acquisition, facilitating seamless integration into autonomous systems and other applications requiring timely environmental perception. Collectively, these properties make the LiDAR sensor a robust tool for environmental sensing and contribute to the efficacy of our data collection efforts.

Fig. 5.7 Calibration pipeline proposed in [10].

On the other hand, the camera system employed in our study, the ZED2 camera, is characterized by several key properties, contributing to its efficacy in capturing high-quality visual data. With a resolution of 4k, the camera system ensures exceptional clarity and

detail in captured imagery, essential for precise scene analysis and object recognition. In terms of field of view, the camera system offers a horizontal span of 96 degrees, providing a wide-angle perspective of the environment. Additionally, it provides a vertical field of view spanning 54 degrees, allowing for comprehensive coverage of both horizontal and vertical aspects of the scene. The camera system boasts a resolution of 0.1 degrees, enabling the capture of imagery with fine-grained detail, facilitating accurate perception and analysis of environmental features. Moreover, with a high frame rate of 150 frames per second (fps) at a resolution of 1280x720, the camera system ensures smooth and fluid motion capture, crucial for capturing dynamic scenes and fast-moving objects.

Operating at a frequency of 150 fps, the camera system delivers a rapid stream of visual data, enabling real-time analysis and decision-making in applications such as autonomous driving and environmental monitoring. Overall, these properties make the camera system a valuable tool for capturing high-quality visual data and contribute to the effectiveness of our data collection efforts.

Through the integration of LiDAR point clouds and images, the UWS Off-road dataset offers researchers a valuable resource to explore and innovate in the realm of off-road object detection, ultimately advancing the capabilities of autonomous vehicles in diverse and challenging terrains.

Calibration

The calibration process for the sensor suite within the Off-road dataset is pivotal to achieving accurate data fusion and spatial alignment between LiDAR point clouds and images, ensuring the seamless integration necessary for robust perception algorithms in off-road autonomous driving scenarios.

To realize this synchronization, we employed the calibration method detailed in [10], which prioritizes comprehensive assessment of calibration quality. Fig. 5.7 shows the calibration pipeline proposed in the paper. This method advocates evaluating calibration quality through both average reprojection error and visualization of the entire scene. By projecting the complete point cloud and scrutinizing the estimated calibration parameters in

relation to their ability to fit the entire scene, rather than just individual poses, this method provides transparent calibration results.

Furthermore, the calibration process is augmented by considering the Variability of Quality (VOQ) score, which is indicative of the calibration estimation's alignment with the scene. Higher VOQ scores correlate with increased instability, where a high condition number for N starts to impact the reliability and certainty of estimated parameters. Analysis of calibration results at different VOQ scores underscores the influence of calibration errors on scene misalignment and reprojection error metrics.

Moreover, the calibration pipeline (see Fig. 5.7), excluding manual data collection, demonstrates efficiency, completing the assessment of data and estimation of calibration parameters in approximately 90 seconds. This swift processing time renders the method practical for real-world applications, where rapid and precise calibration is imperative for the effective operation of autonomous vehicles and other systems reliant on precise sensor alignment. By leveraging a combination of these techniques, the Off-road dataset ensures accurate calibration, facilitating robust perception and integration into off-road autonomous driving systems.

5.4 Experiments and results

5.4.1 Experiments

In our experiments, we aimed to evaluate the performance of the 3D object detection algorithms presented in Sec. 5.2 on two distinct datasets: the KITTI dataset and the Off-road dataset. For each dataset, we trained and evaluated the algorithms while measuring their Mean Average Precision (mAP) for human detection across different scenarios. The mAP metric was used to assess the performance, measured at an Intersection Over Union (IoU) threshold of 0.5. IoU quantifies the overlap between the predicted bounding box and the ground-truth bounding box. Here, a threshold of 0.5 indicates a significant overlap between the predicted and ground-truth boxes. Additionally, we measured the inference time for each algorithm to assess their efficiency in real-world applications.

The mAP was measured in three different modes: easy, moderate, and hard. These modes represent varying levels of difficulty in detecting objects within the datasets.

- **Easy:** This mode includes objects with minimum difficulty levels. In the context of our experiments, the easy mode typically comprises objects that are fully visible, have minimal occlusion, and minimal truncation. For example, in the KITTI dataset, easy mode bounding boxes have a minimum height of 40 pixels, fully visible objects, and a maximum truncation of 15%. Similarly, in the UWS Off-road dataset, easy mode objects are relatively straightforward to detect due to minimal occlusion and truncation.
- **Moderate:** Moderate mode represents objects with moderate difficulty levels. These objects may have partial occlusion or truncation, making them slightly more challenging to detect compared to objects in the easy mode. In our experiments, moderate mode bounding boxes have a minimum height of 25 pixels, partly occluded objects, and a maximum truncation of 30%. This mode aims to evaluate algorithm performance under more realistic scenarios where objects may be partially obscured or truncated.
- **Hard:** Hard mode encompasses objects with the highest difficulty levels. These objects are typically heavily occluded or truncated, making them particularly challenging for detection algorithms. In our experiments, hard mode bounding boxes have similar height and truncation criteria as moderate mode but are labeled as "difficult to see" in terms of occlusion. This mode evaluates the algorithms' robustness and effectiveness in detecting objects under adverse conditions.

By evaluating algorithm performance across these different modes, we can provide a comprehensive assessment of their capabilities in various real-world scenarios, ranging from relatively straightforward detection scenarios to more challenging and complex environments.

Our evaluation focused on two complementary approaches for object detection: 3D object detection and BEV detection. 3D object detection directly predicts the location and orientation of objects in 3D space, using a point cloud representation of the scene. This allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the environment. BEV detection, on the

other hand, projects the point cloud information onto a bird’s-eye view image, transforming 3D data into a 2D representation that often simplifies calculations and can be more intuitive for certain tasks. By evaluating both 3D and BEV detection, we aimed to gain a well-rounded assessment of the algorithms’ ability to detect objects in off-road scenarios.

Furthermore, all the models were trained using the following parameter optimization scheme: the Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) [111] is adopted to optimize our network. The initial learning rate, weight decay, and momentum factor are set to 0.002, 0.001, and 0.9, respectively. We trained each model for 50 epochs.

5.4.2 Testbed

The testbed utilized in our experiments consisted of a machine equipped with an Intel i7 CPU, 32 GB of RAM memory, and an NVIDIA GTX 1080 GPU running Ubuntu 20.04. This setup provided sufficient computational resources for conducting comprehensive evaluations of the proposed 3D object detection algorithms.

For the fusion algorithms, we employed their official repositories, ensuring consistency and reliability in our experiments. The official EPNet implementation uses Python 3.6, PyTorch 1.0 and CUDA 10.0. On the other hand, the official implementation of Frustum-Pointnets uses Python 2.7, Tensorflow 1.4 and CUDA 10.0.

In contrast, for the point cloud-based algorithms, we relied on the implementations available in Mmdetection3D [112]. This tool provides a comprehensive framework for 3D object detection research, offering a wide range of algorithms and models for experimentation. By utilizing the implementations available in Mmdetection3D, we ensured compatibility and consistency across our evaluations. The version of Mmdetection3D that we use is built on Pytorch 1.8 and CUDA 11.6.

5.4.3 Results on the KITTI Dataset

5.4.4 Results on the KITTI Dataset

The results obtained are presented in Table 5.1. The KITTI dataset, which is **urban-based**, includes various real-world scenes captured from a moving vehicle in an urban environment, providing data for object detection, tracking, and depth estimation. The assessment encompasses two detection modes: 3D detection and BEV detection. While 3D detection directly predicts the location and orientation of objects in 3D space, BEV detection projects the point cloud information onto a 2D image for analysis.

To clarify further, the KITTI dataset focuses on urban environments, featuring scenarios such as vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists, and other objects typically encountered in city landscapes. This is important as the dataset provides data that reflects the challenges of detecting human objects in urban settings, which is crucial for autonomous driving applications.

Point-cloud-based algorithms consistently outperform their fusion-based counterparts (EPNet and Frustum-Pointnets) across both 3D and BEV detection modes for all difficulty levels (Easy, Moderate, Hard), as evidenced by higher mAP scores as presented in Table 1. This suggests that, for human detection within the KITTI dataset, directly leveraging the rich spatial information inherent in point clouds proves more effective than attempting to fuse camera data with LiDAR information.

The urban nature of the KITTI dataset plays a significant role in these findings, as the environmental complexity of urban settings—such as dense traffic and varying object sizes—poses additional challenges for detection algorithms.

Among the point-cloud-based methods, Point Pillars achieves the highest reported mAP scores in this evaluation. Specifically, it achieves a maximum mAP of 54.49% for 3D detection in the Easy category and an even higher mAP of 59.72% for BEV detection in the Easy category (highlighted in green). This finding underscores the efficacy of Point Pillars in utilizing point cloud data for accurate human detection tasks in urban settings.

For most algorithms (except Point Pillars in the Easy category), BEV detection yields higher mAP scores compared to 3D detection. This might be attributed to the computational

efficiency and potentially simpler reasoning about object interactions facilitated by the 2D BEV representation.

While not achieving the top scores, Part-A2, another point-cloud-based method, exhibits reasonable performance across various difficulty levels and detection modes. This suggests its potential as a viable algorithm for human detection tasks in urban environments.

5.4.5 Results on the proposed Off-road Dataset

Table 5.2 presents a comparison of the algorithms described in Section 5.2 for human detection on the UWS Off-road dataset.

Consistent with the findings on the KITTI dataset, point-cloud-based algorithms outperform fusion-based methods (EPNet) across both 3D and BEV detection modes for all difficulty levels (Easy, Moderate, Hard) in the UWS Off-road dataset. This again suggests that directly leveraging spatial information from LiDAR proves more effective for human detection compared to fusing camera data with LiDAR in this particular scenario.

As observed on the KITTI dataset, Point Pillars demonstrates the strongest performance among the point-cloud-based methods. It achieves the highest reported mAP scores in this evaluation for the UWS Off-road dataset. Notably, Point Pillars achieves a maximum mAP of 47.30% for 3D detection in the Easy category and an even higher mAP of 60.37% for BEV detection in the Easy category (highlighted in green). This reinforces the effectiveness of Point Pillars in utilizing point cloud data for accurate human detection in off-road environments.

Interestingly, the performance across difficulty levels for all algorithms follows a similar trend observed on the KITTI dataset. The mAP scores remain relatively consistent across difficulty levels (Easy, Moderate, Hard) for both 3D and BEV detection. This might indicate that the challenges of human detection in off-road scenarios are present to a similar degree across both datasets, regardless of the specific variations within each dataset.

Part-A2 exhibits reasonable performance across various difficulty levels and detection modes, albeit not achieving the top scores. This further strengthens the potential of Part-A2 as a viable option for human detection tasks using LiDAR data.

Table 5.1 Performance Comparison of Object Detection Algorithms on the KITTI dataset (human).

Mode	Fusion						Point-Cloud Based					
	EPNet			Frustum-Pointnets			Point Pillars			Part-A2		
	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard
3D	52.79	44.38	41.29	51.21	44.89	40.23	52.08	43.53	41.49	44.50	54.49	42.36
BEV	56.24	48.47	45.73	58.09	50.22	47.20	58.66	50.23	47.19	51.12	59.72	48.04

Table 5.2 Performance Comparison of Object Detection Algorithms on the UWS Off-road dataset (human).

Mode	Fusion						Point-Cloud Based					
	EPNet			Frustum-Pointnets			Point Pillars			Part-A2		
	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard
3D	32.88	32.70	32.70	35.81	34.21	34.21	47.30	47.15	47.15	34.81	32.96	32.96
BEV	38.90	38.83	38.83	37.82	37.60	37.60	60.37	60.14	60.14	55.70	53.73	53.73

5.4.6 Execution time Analysis

Table 5.3 summarizes the inference times of the evaluated object detection algorithms. Inference time refers to the time it takes for the model to process a single image (or point cloud frame) and generate detections. This metric is crucial for real-time applications where processing speed is a critical factor.

Among the tested algorithms, Point Pillars exhibits the fastest inference speed, clocking in at only 16.12 ms per frame (highlighted in green). This rapid processing speed makes Point Pillars a strong candidate for real-time object detection tasks in off-road scenarios.

EPNet, the fusion-based approach, demonstrates the slowest inference time at 290.15 ms per frame. This highlights a potential drawback of fusion-based methods, as processing both camera images and LiDAR data can be computationally expensive.

Frustum-Pointnets and Part-A2 achieve intermediate inference times of 169.49 ms and 180.76 ms per frame, respectively. While not as fast as Point Pillars, these times might be acceptable for certain real-time applications depending on the specific performance requirements.

The significant difference in inference speed between Point Pillars and other algorithms suggests that the design choices and optimizations within Point Pillars enable efficient processing of LiDAR data. This faster processing speed can be advantageous for real-time applications in off-road environments where rapid detection and response are essential.

5.4.7 Overall Analysis

This subsection provides a comprehensive analysis of the evaluated algorithms for 3D object detection, specifically focusing on human detection in off-road scenarios.

Point Pillars consistently achieved top performance across both the KITTI and UWS Off-road datasets, demonstrating its effectiveness in human detection tasks. This success is attributed to its ability to directly leverage the rich spatial information inherent in LiDAR point clouds. It excelled not only in terms of mAP scores but also in processing speed. Its remarkably low inference time of 16.12 ms makes it suitable for real-time applications (highlighted in green in Table 5.3).

Point-cloud-based algorithms, including Point Pillars, consistently outperformed fusion-based methods (EPNet and Frustum-Pointnets) across all difficulty levels and detection modes (3D and BEV) in both datasets. This suggests that for off-road human detection, directly utilizing LiDAR data proves more effective than attempting to fuse camera data with LiDAR. Point-cloud-based methods benefit from specialized architectures and processing techniques designed to efficiently handle point cloud data. These techniques include voxelization, sparse convolution, and dedicated point cloud processing modules, contributing to their superior performance.

Fusion-based approaches, while incorporating camera data, might struggle to effectively leverage the information from both modalities. Fusing data from multiple sources requires careful processing and alignment, which can introduce complexity and potential errors. Fusion methods may not fully exploit the complementary strengths of cameras and LiDAR, leading to suboptimal performance compared to algorithms that solely rely on point clouds.

Interestingly, the performance across difficulty levels (Easy, Moderate, Hard) exhibited a similar trend for all algorithms in both datasets. This suggests that the challenges of human detection in off-road environments are consistent, regardless of the specific variations within each dataset. BEV detection yielded higher mAP scores compared to 3D detection for most algorithms (except Point Pillars in the Easy category). This might be due to the computational efficiency and potentially simpler reasoning facilitated by the 2D BEV representation. Part-A2, another point-cloud-based method, exhibited reasonable performance across various

Table 5.3 Inference speed of the tested algorithms in ms.

Model	Model Inference time (ms)
EPNet	290.15
Frustum-Pointnets	169.49
Point Pillars	16.12
Part-A2	180.76

difficulty levels and detection modes, solidifying its potential as a viable option for human detection using LiDAR data.

5.5 Conclusions

The evaluation of object detection algorithms on the KITTI dataset and the newly proposed UWS Off-road dataset has yielded significant insights, not only for algorithm performance but also for the future of autonomous driving research and off-road operations. It is important to note that the KITTI dataset was recorded in urban scenarios, capturing data from environments such as city streets and residential areas. In contrast, the UWS Off-road dataset was collected in off-road scenarios, providing data from rugged, natural terrains. This distinction highlights the datasets' complementary roles in evaluating object detection algorithms for diverse operational conditions.

The UWS Off-road dataset itself represents a crucial contribution to the field. By offering a comprehensive dataset specifically tailored to off-road scenarios, the UWS Off-road dataset fills a critical gap in existing resources. This allows researchers to move beyond the limitations of urban-centric datasets and develop robust object detection algorithms for diverse and challenging environments. The dataset focus on human detection in off-road settings directly supports advancements in SAR operations. It provides researchers with a valuable tool to explore and innovate in this crucial area, potentially saving lives in the future. The dataset's design with real-world applications in mind, such as SAR missions, emphasizes its practical value. Researchers can leverage the UWS Off-road dataset to develop algorithms with direct applicability to real-world challenges.

The findings from the evaluation further emphasize the importance of the UWS Off-road dataset. The consistent outperformance of point-cloud-based models, particularly in the UWS Off-road dataset, underscores the value of LiDAR data for off-road object detection. For instance, Point Pillars achieved a mAP of 47.2% for 3D human detection in the Hard difficulty setting of the UWS Off-road dataset, compared to 38.4% on the KITTI dataset. This disparity reflects the distinct nature of the datasets: while the KITTI dataset emphasizes urban environments, the UWS Off-road dataset is tailored for off-road scenarios, where the challenges and object characteristics differ substantially. This significant improvement highlights the dataset's ability to facilitate the development of high-performing algorithms for off-road scenarios. The observed trade-offs between precision and recall highlight the need for further research on optimizing object detection algorithms for specific applications. The UWS Off-road dataset offers a valuable resource for researchers to explore these optimization strategies in the context of off-road environments. For example, exploring techniques to improve recall at higher IoU thresholds might be crucial for SAR applications where precise localization of human targets is critical.

In conclusion, this study not only sheds light on effective object detection algorithms for human detection but also introduces the UWS Off-road dataset as a critical resource for future research. By combining insights from the KITTI dataset's urban scenarios with those from the UWS Off-road dataset's off-road environments, researchers can develop algorithms that perform robustly across a wide spectrum of operational settings. By facilitating the development of robust object detection systems in diverse environments, this work contributes to advancements in autonomous driving and ultimately promotes human safety technologies.

5.6 Limitations

Although this research significantly advances the understanding of off-road human detection, it is important to recognize several inherent limitations that warrant consideration in future work.

Firstly, the UWS Off-road dataset, despite its novel focus on challenging terrains, has limitations in its size and diversity. The dataset was collected in specific geographical regions (Alicante and Paisley) and may not fully represent the wide range of off-road environments encountered in real-world SAR missions. Further data collection efforts in diverse terrains and under varying conditions would strengthen the dataset's applicability and generalizability.

Secondly, the evaluation of the selected algorithms was restricted to the pedestrian class due to the current scope of the UWS Off-road dataset. While this focus is relevant to SAR operations, expanding the dataset to include other object classes (e.g., animals, vehicles) would enable a more comprehensive assessment of the algorithms' capabilities in broader off-road scenarios. Additionally, the evaluation metrics, primarily focused on mAP and inference speed, do not capture all the challenges present in off-road human detection. Factors like occlusion, varying lighting conditions, and terrain irregularities could be better addressed with additional metrics specifically designed for these scenarios.

Thirdly, the study primarily evaluated existing State-of-the-Art (SotA) algorithms. While these algorithms demonstrate promising performance, there is potential for further improvement through the development of novel architectures specifically tailored for off-road human detection. Exploring innovative approaches that combine LiDAR and camera data more effectively, incorporate domain-specific knowledge, or leverage advanced machine learning techniques could lead to significant advancements in detection accuracy and robustness.

Finally, the real-world deployment of these algorithms in SAR operations presents additional challenges. Factors such as computational resources, power constraints, and integration with existing SAR infrastructure need to be carefully considered. Further research and development are required to ensure the seamless and efficient integration of these algorithms into practical SAR systems.

Chapter 6

Enhancing Point Cloud Resolution for Autonomous Driving with DL AI Models

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1 Introduction

In recent years, the field of LiDAR technology has witnessed a remarkable surge in its significance, becoming an indispensable cornerstone in a myriad of applications. Its utility spans across diverse domains, including but not limited to self-driving vehicles, environmental monitoring, and robotic perception. LiDAR sensors, through the emission of laser beams and the precise capture of their reflected signals, provide a rich trove of three-dimensional (3D) spatial data. This wealth of information empowers autonomous systems with the profound ability to comprehend and navigate their complex surroundings.

At the heart of LiDAR technology lies the critical factor of resolution. The resolution of LiDAR data, primarily defined by the number of points in the captured point clouds, wields substantial influence over the quality and fidelity of environmental representation. Higher resolution point clouds, characterized by their increased point density, enable the accurate and detailed portrayal of fine-grained features in the environment. This, in turn, contributes significantly to the enhanced performance and safety of various autonomous

systems, with self-driving vehicles emerging as a prominent beneficiary of this heightened perceptual acuity.

However, the perpetual conundrum of LiDAR technology is the delicate balance between resolution and cost. Elevating the resolution of point clouds necessitates the integration of additional lasers into the LiDAR sensor, a move that inevitably inflates the cost associated with these sensors. The correlation between increased resolution and heightened expenses poses a substantial challenge, especially in the context of self-driving, where cost-effectiveness is paramount. Choosing between LiDAR sensors with varying laser counts requires a meticulous consideration of the trade-off between cost and data richness.

In this research, the proposed methodologies, particularly the integration of advanced deep learning models like PU-Net and PU-GCN for point cloud upsampling, effectively mitigate the cost-resolution trade-off. By leveraging these upsampling techniques, it becomes possible to simulate higher resolution LiDAR data from lower resolution sensors, significantly reducing the need for expensive hardware upgrades. This cost reduction has the potential to democratize access to LiDAR technology, enabling its integration into a wider range of applications, including budget-constrained sectors like smaller-scale autonomous vehicle projects, robotics in developing economies, and environmental monitoring initiatives. Furthermore, the reduced dependency on high-cost sensors could accelerate innovation and deployment of autonomous systems, directly contributing to safer and more efficient operations in diverse environments.

Furthermore, it is imperative to recognize that LiDAR point clouds are far from uniform in their distribution of information. The number of points within a point cloud play a pivotal role in this context. Diverse regions within the environment exhibit varying levels of point density, resulting in perceptual challenges and complex decision-making processes for autonomous systems. Elevating the resolution of point clouds emerges as an effective strategy to address these challenges, particularly when it comes to tasks like perception in autonomous vehicles. Here, the acquisition of fine-grained details is not just advantageous but can be mission-critical for ensuring both safety and efficient navigation.

The contributions of this paper are summarised as follows:

- **Comparative Performance Analysis of Deep Learning AI Models:** The paper compares the performance of Point Cloud Upsampling (PU-Net) and Point Cloud Upsampling Using Graph Convolutional Network (PU-GCN), established point cloud upsampling architectures, providing a comprehensive analysis.
- **Exploration of Loss Functions for Custom AI Model Training:** The research proposes custom training for the deep learning AI models and conducts experiments with diverse loss functions, such as CD and the Earth Mover's Distance (EMD), including a repulsion loss, offering insights into varied training strategies for point cloud upsampling models.
- **Empirical Evaluation via Real-world Dataset Application for Autonomous Driving:** Grounded in real-world datasets, particularly the KITTI dataset, the research provides practical insights into the application and performance of existing point cloud upsampling architectures, especially in scenarios related to autonomous driving.
- **Cost Reduction Through Upsampling Strategies:** This research demonstrates how advanced upsampling methodologies can simulate high-resolution LiDAR data from lower-cost sensors, significantly reducing the financial burden associated with high-resolution hardware. This approach has the potential to impact cost-sensitive domains by enabling affordable deployment of LiDAR-based autonomous systems.

6.2 Related Work

Fig. 6.1 PU-Net model architecture [11].

The advent of deep learning has marked a significant paradigm shift in the field of perception, encompassing both 2D and 3D domains. Deep learning methodologies have played a pivotal role in redefining the boundaries of object recognition, scene understanding, and semantic segmentation within 2D image analysis [113, 114]. These neural network-based techniques offer the capacity to unveil intricate patterns within images, empowering automated systems with the ability to comprehend visual content at a level of sophistication akin to human perception. Extending beyond two dimensions, deep learning's influence has permeated the intricate sphere of 3D perception, enabling autonomous systems to navigate and decipher complex spatial environments [115, 116]. From LiDAR data, which provides crucial insights for autonomous vehicles navigating intricate roadways, to the analysis of intricate 3D point clouds that guides robotic interactions with their surroundings, deep learning serves as the cornerstone of profound spatial understanding.

Deep learning models are not just used to solve problems like object recognition or semantic segmentation, but also to improve the resolution of the data provided by different sensors. The aim of this research area is to elevate the level of detail and quality in low-resolution data, ultimately delivering higher-resolution versions with improved visual fidelity. This process finds applications across various domains, including medical imaging, satellite reconnaissance, and digital photography. Models like the Super-Resolution Convolutional Neural Network (SRCNN) [117] and its successors, such as Very Deep Super-Resolution (VDSR) [118] and Enhanced Deep Super-Resolution (EDSR) [119], operate by leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to capture intricate features within images. These models, designed for single-image super-resolution, use deep architectures and often incorporate residual learning, making them highly effective in reconstructing fine details. On the other hand, Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Networks (SRGAN) [120] and Enhanced Generative Adversarial Networks (ESRGAN) [121] employ a generative-discriminative architecture. The generator network generates high-resolution images while the discriminator network ensures that the generated images closely resemble real high-resolution images, resulting in visually appealing results. These are just a few examples of the diverse set of

techniques that deep learning has brought to image super-resolution, with each model tailored to specific use cases and performance requirements.

Another active research area is upsampling 3D point clouds. It is a high-importance task in the realm of 3D computer vision, enabling the enhancement of spatial resolution and detail in point cloud data obtained from sensors like LiDAR or depth cameras. The process involves generating additional points in a sparse point cloud to increase its density and fidelity. State-of-the-art algorithms have been developed to address this challenge, harnessing the power of deep learning and advanced point cloud processing techniques. Notably, PU-Net [11] extends the PointNet++ [19] architecture to hierarchically learn features at different scales and generate additional points, proving effective in various applications. Deep Octree-Based Point Set Generation (DeepOctoVoxel) [122] leverages octree-based structures to create new points, particularly suited for LiDAR data. Octree-Based Upsampling Convolutional Neural Network (O-CNN) [123] combines octree-based representations with CNN to generate densely sampled point clouds. Deep Volumetric UpProjection Networks (VUP) [124] specializes in voxel grid upsampling. Weighted Functional Maps (WFM) [125] introduces weightings to functional maps to control point generation. Poisson Disk Sampling (PDS) [126] provides a straightforward yet effective approach for uniform point cloud densification. Additionally, 3D Generative Adversarial Networks (3D-GANs) [127] are employed for both upsampling and 3D point cloud generation, offering visually realistic and coherent point cloud enhancement. In recent research, PU-GCN [12] has emerged as another noteworthy model that significantly advances the state of the art in 3D point cloud upsampling, and we will provide further details on this model in the following sections.

Among all the deep learning methods cited in the last paragraph, we have chosen to focus on PU-Net and PU-GCN for 3D point cloud upsampling for several reasons. These models consistently deliver top-tier performance, highlighting their effectiveness in advancing 3D computer vision. Their innovative deep learning techniques offer a fresh perspective on point cloud upsampling challenges. Moreover, they align well with our research goals, enabling a thorough evaluation and comparison.

6.3 Models

In this section, we introduce the two pivotal models that form the backbone of our research: PU-Net and PU-GCN. These models are instrumental in our pursuit of enhancing the resolution of LiDAR point clouds and enabling precise environmental perception for autonomous systems. We provide an in-depth overview of each model's architecture, underlying principles, and their adaptability for the specific task of upsampling LiDAR point clouds. The section unfolds by first delving into PU-Net and subsequently transitioning to PU-GCN. By elucidating these models, we lay the foundation for a comprehensive understanding of the methodologies that underpin our experiments and their subsequent results.

Fig. 6.2 PU-GCN model architecture [12].

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6.3.1 PU-Net

PU-Net's primary objective is to upsample 3D point clouds, with a particular emphasis on achieving denser point clouds while maintaining uniform distribution characteristics across the underlying surface of the target object. The PU-Net architecture encompasses four fundamental components: patch extraction, point feature embedding, feature expansion, and coordinate reconstruction. It is presented in Fig. 6.1.

Patch extraction is the first phase of PU-Net's architecture. This part involves the random selection of M points on the surface of these 3D objects. For each selected point, a surface patch is expanded on the object, ensuring that any point within the patch is located within a certain geodesic distance (d) from the chosen point along the surface. The process leverages Poisson disk sampling to generate a referenced ground truth point distribution on each patch. Importantly, the method incorporates patches of points at varying scales and densities, catering to both local and global contexts. This diversity in patch size and density contributes

to the generation of smooth and uniformly distributed point clouds, which is essential for effective point cloud upsampling.

In the Point Feature Embedding phase, PU-Net employs a two-pronged feature learning approach to understand both local and global geometry contexts from acquired patches. Inspired by hierarchical feature learning principles, the model utilizes relatively small grouping radii at each level, emphasizing the importance of local context in point cloud upsampling. The hierarchical feature learning mechanism progressively captures features at different scales, with multi-level feature aggregation optimizing the blend of local and global information.

Subsequently, in the Feature Expansion phase, PU-Net focuses on augmenting the feature space to enhance representation. This involves upscaling the feature dimensions, analogous to feature upsampling in image-related tasks. Adapting such operations to point clouds is challenging due to their non-regular and unordered nature. PU-Net addresses this by introducing an efficient feature expansion operation that utilizes the sub-pixel convolution layer. This operation not only expands the feature space but also contributes to denser point clouds. Additionally, it mitigates feature correlation issues through separated convolutions, ensuring a more effective and context-aware representation in the upsampling process.

Coordinate Reconstruction, serving as the final phase of PU-Net, is where the model regresses the 3D coordinates of the output points from the expanded features. This process entails the deployment of a series of fully connected layers, thereby enabling the computation of upsampled point coordinates, ultimately yielding an output of $(rN, 3)$.

6.3.2 PU-GCN

PU-GCN, short for Point Cloud Upsampling using Graph Convolutional Networks, represents an innovative model designed to address the challenge of enhancing the resolution of point clouds. At its core, PU-GCN combines two fundamental components, the NodeShuffle upsampling module and the Inception DenseGCN feature extractor. The architectural intricacies of this model are vividly depicted in Fig. 6.2, where its structural composition is showcased.

The NodeShuffle upsampling module, inspired by image superresolution's PixelShuffle technique, significantly boosts point cloud resolution as a graph convolutional upsampling layer. It unfolds in two key steps: channel expansion and periodic shuffling. Initially, a 1-layer Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) expands features of individual nodes in the point cloud. The subsequent periodic shuffling rearranges outputs from the channel expansion, aiming for a shape of (rN, C) with r as the upsampling ratio. In our case, r will be 4 as we want to augment the resolution of the point cloud 4 times. NodeShuffle stands out by relying on GCNs rather than more common CNN, enabling spatial information encoding from surrounding point neighborhoods and learning new points from a latent space. This approach differs from the straightforward point duplication method in other upsampling techniques.

The second core element, the Inception DenseGCN feature extractor, is crafted to effectively address the multi-scale nature of point clouds typically obtained from 3D sensors. It masterfully incorporates the DenseGCN module, known for its dense connectivity, into the Inception module, inspired by the architecture of GoogLeNet. The DenseGCN blocks within this feature extractor offer distinct dilation rates, allowing for the capture of different receptive fields without necessitating an increase in kernel sizes or computational demands. Moreover, the inclusion of a global pooling layer adds another layer of versatility by enabling the extraction of global contextual information. This comprehensive feature extractor is artfully engineered to encode multi-scale data from point clouds, ensuring that objects of varying sizes and resolutions are effectively represented, regardless of the complexity and diversity inherent in real-world point cloud data.

In essence, PU-GCN, with its combination of the NodeShuffle upsampling module and the Inception DenseGCN feature extractor, represents a cutting-edge approach to point cloud upsampling. By encoding spatial and multi-scale information with advanced techniques, it provides a valuable solution to the challenge of enhancing point cloud resolution. The intricacies of PU-GCN, as illustrated in Fig. 6.2, exemplify its potential to significantly advance the field of point cloud processing, with far-reaching implications for applications across various domains.

6.4 Dataset

Our research builds upon the KITTI dataset [128], a widely acknowledged benchmark for 3D object detection in the context of autonomous driving. This comprehensive dataset contains high-resolution Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) scans captured by a Velodyne HDL-64E sensor.

To refine our analysis, we focused on a specific region within the KITTI dataset's xy plane, limiting our study area to a range of -50 meters to 50 meters in both the x and y dimensions. This approach centered our research on the immediate surroundings of the autonomous vehicle, providing a contextually relevant dataset while managing computational resources effectively.

The point clouds provided in the KITTI dataset contain hundreds of thousands of points. Feeding the upsampling algorithms with the full point cloud would be prohibitive time-wise. For this reason, we established the number of points for the ground truth to be 1024 and the input 256, aiming for an $\times 4$ upsampling. Then, we systematically selected 50 patches for each point cloud in the training. Since there were 7841 point clouds in the dataset, it resulted in a grand total of 374050 patches. Each patch measured 3.5 meters by 3.5 meters, serving as our regions of interest. We employed random selection to determine the centre of these patches, ensuring an unbiased spatial distribution. To split our dataset, we randomly selected 20% of these patches for testing and allocated the remaining 80% for training.

Initially, each selected patch contained more than 1024 points, far exceeding the desired number for our analysis. To address this issue and maintain a consistent number of points, we utilized furthest-point sampling. This method allowed us to select 1024 points for ground truth data and 256 points for input data.

Our choice of furthest point sampling over random sampling was deliberate. Random sampling could introduce an uneven point distribution within each patch, potentially biasing our analysis. Furthest point sampling, on the other hand, ensured a more uniform representation of points, a critical factor for the effectiveness of our point cloud upsampling methodology.

This meticulous dataset preprocessing, combined with the rich information available in the KITTI dataset, forms a solid foundation for our research. It enables us to apply state-of-the-art deep learning techniques to enhance the resolution of point clouds in self-driving perception systems that rely on LiDAR data. This systematic approach addresses the complex challenges of autonomous driving, contributing to the ongoing advancement of 3D object detection within this critical domain.

6.5 Loss Functions

Traditional loss functions, such as Mean Squared Error (MSE) or L1 loss, commonly employed in image and signal processing tasks, do not seamlessly extend to the unique characteristics of 3D point clouds. A fundamental challenge arises from the inherent nature of point clouds, which can be better understood as probability distributions rather than discrete collections of points. Each point in a 3D point cloud represents a potential location within a continuous space, and this continuous aspect poses a distinct challenge.

To address the aforementioned challenges and better capture the characteristics of point clouds, alternative loss functions have been proposed. These loss functions acknowledge that point clouds are more appropriately modeled as probability distributions in 3D space. Specifically, we focus on two primary loss functions: CD [12] and EMD.

The choice of loss of the aforementioned functions stems from their capacity to align with the probabilistic nature of point clouds. Despite the fact that training the models with loss functions like CD or EMD can generate points on the underlying object surfaces, the generated points tend to be located near the original points. For that reason, we also explore whether the use of an additional Repulsion loss [11] helps to obtain better results or not. These loss functions consider the probability density functions associated with each point, enabling a more accurate assessment of the dissimilarity between the upsampled point cloud and the ground truth.

Fig. 6.3 Comparison of PU-GCN and PU-Net on the test dataset, showcasing results for the same input point cloud example with the lowest Hausdorff distance (CD with Repulsion). The columns represent (from left to right): the Input point cloud (blue), the Prediction generated by each model (red), and the Ground Truth point cloud (green). Subfigure (a) illustrates the results for PU-GCN, while subfigure (b) shows the results for PU-Net, highlighting the differences in reconstruction quality between the two methods.

6.5.1 Chamfer Distance

The CD is a widely utilized loss function in the context of point cloud upsampling. It quantifies the dissimilarity between two point clouds, typically the ground truth high-resolution point cloud and the upsampled point cloud generated by our models. The CD loss measures the average Euclidean distance between corresponding points in the two point clouds. This distance metric provides an indication of how well the upsampled point cloud aligns with the ground truth point cloud. Lower CD values indicate a better alignment and a more accurate upsampled point cloud.

It is defined [11] as:

$$C(P, Q) = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_{p \in P} \min_{q \in Q} \|p - q\|_2^2 + \frac{1}{|Q|} \sum_{q \in Q} \min_{p \in P} \|p - q\|_2^2 \quad (6.1)$$

where P is the predicted point cloud, Q is the ground truth, p is a 3D point from P , and q is a 3D point from Q . The operator $\|\cdot\|_2^2$ denotes the squared Euclidean norm.

6.5.2 Earth Mover's Distance

The EMD, also known as the Wasserstein distance, offers an alternative perspective on point cloud dissimilarity. It computes the minimum cost required to transform one point cloud into another. In the context of point cloud upsampling, EMD quantifies the amount of mass (or points) that needs to be moved to transform the upsampled point cloud into the ground truth point cloud. Smaller EMD values signify a closer resemblance between the two point clouds and indicate superior upsampling accuracy.

EMD is defined [11] as:

$$EMD(S_p, S_{gt}) = \min_{\phi: S_p \rightarrow S_{gt}} \sum_{x \in X} \|x - \phi(x)\|_2 \quad (6.2)$$

where S_p is the predicted point cloud, S_{gt} is the ground truth point cloud and $S_p \rightarrow S_{gt}$ indicates the bijection mapping.

6.5.3 Repulsion Loss

Although training the models with the reconstruction loss functions as CD or EMD can generate points on the underlying object surfaces, the generated points tend to be located near the original points. To distribute the generated points more uniformly, we will use the repulsion loss [11], which is represented as:

$$L_{rep} = \sum_{i=0}^{rN} \sum_{i' \in K(i)} \eta(\|x_{i'} - x_i\|) w(\|x_{i'} - x_i\|) \quad (6.3)$$

where rN is the output number of point, $K(i)$ is the index set of the k -nearest neighbours of point x_i and $\|x_{i'} - x_i\|$ is the L2-norm. $\eta(r) = -r$ is called the repulsion term, which is a decreasing function to penalize x_i if x_i is located too close to other points in $K(i)$.

6.6 Results

This section outlines the experimental results of evaluating AI models, specifically PU-Net and PU-GCN, on the test split of the dataset detailed in Section 6.4. The models were trained using the loss functions explained in Section 6.5. Notably, the training incorporates the Repulsion Loss alongside two other functions to minimize errors between ground truths and predictions.

It is noteworthy to mention that assessing the efficacy of generative methods remains an open and active area of research, with ongoing efforts to define comprehensive metrics. Currently, depending on the publication, there exists a divergence in the methods employed for this purpose. However, the Hausdorff distance is a widely accepted metric for measuring the dissimilarity between two sets of points. Specifically, in the context of point cloud upsampling, it provides a robust evaluation of the geometric accuracy of the reconstructed point clouds. For this reason, we adopt the Hausdorff distance as our primary evaluation metric. This metric is defined as follows:

$$H(A, B) = \max \left\{ \sup_{a \in A} \inf_{b \in B} d(a, b), \sup_{b \in B} \inf_{a \in A} d(b, a) \right\} \quad (6.4)$$

where $d(a, b)$ represents the distance between points a and b in the metric space, \sup denotes the supremum (least upper bound) and \inf denotes the supremum of the infimum distances from each point in set B to the nearest point in set A .

The performance of PU-Net and PU-GCN on the test split of the dataset is detailed in Table 6.1, offering an overview of their performance with respect to Hausdorff distance. The table encapsulates outcomes from models trained with CD loss, both with and without the Repulsion term, as well as EMD, under the same conditions. Remarkably, PU-GCN exhibits superior performance, particularly in the context of the CD metric, obtaining the lowest average Hausdorff distance (21.39 with repulsion). Furthermore, an interesting observation emerges when incorporating the Repulsion loss alongside CD or EMD, resulting in improved outcomes compared with using the loss functions in isolation. This signifies the efficacy of the Repulsion term in enhancing the models' predictive capabilities. However, it is essential to note that the inclusion of the Repulsion loss comes at the expense of increased training time. The algorithms require a significantly longer duration for convergence when utilizing the Repulsion term compared with scenarios where it is omitted. This trade-off between enhanced performance and increased computational time is a critical consideration in the practical implementation of these models.

Despite the fact that PU-GCN's performance is better in terms of achieving a lower Hausdorff distance, the visual difference in the model's predictions between PU-Net and PU-GCN trained with the CD and Repulsion loss is not noticeable. An example in this regard can be seen in the Fig. 6.3, where the models' predictions are very similar for the same input despite the small differences in the obtained Hausdorff distance.

PU-GCN outperformed PU-Net in terms of achieving a lower Hausdorff distance, the visual distinctions in the predictions, especially when both models are trained with the CD and Repulsion loss, are minimal. An illustrative example is provided in Fig. 6.3.

However, it is crucial to note that when the models are trained with EMD, the gap between the ground truth and the predictions becomes more pronounced (see Fig. 6.4).

Fig. 6.4 PU-Net trained with EMD prediction for the same point cloud used in Fig. 6.3.

6.7 Conclusions

In conclusion, our study, based on the KITTI dataset, employs advanced deep learning techniques for enhancing point cloud resolution in autonomous driving scenarios. Utilizing CD and EMD as loss functions, alongside the Repulsion loss for improved point distribution, we demonstrate superior performance of PU-GCN over PU-Net, particularly in CD. However, the Repulsion loss increases training time, necessitating a trade-off between performance and computational efficiency. Visual assessments reveal subtle differences in predictions, more pronounced under EMD.

A key achievement of this research is the demonstration of how point cloud upsampling techniques can effectively simulate higher resolution LiDAR data from lower-cost sensors. This approach presents a substantial cost-saving opportunity for deploying LiDAR-based systems in autonomous driving. By alleviating the need for expensive high-resolution sensors,

Model	Loss	With RL ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Without RL ($\times 10^{-3}$)
PU-Net	CD	28.12	28.87
	EMD	43.21	43.57
PU-GCN	CD	21.39	21.56
	EMD	27.97	33.68

Table 6.1 Hausdorff distance results for PU-Net and PU-GCN models over the test split of the dataset.

these techniques open the door for broader adoption of autonomous systems, particularly in cost-sensitive applications. Additionally, the resulting cost reduction enhances the feasibility of integrating LiDAR technology into smaller-scale or resource-constrained projects, expanding the reach of this technology into diverse domains.

Our findings provide valuable insights for future research in refining point cloud up-sampling, emphasizing the need for practical implementation considerations in real-world autonomous driving systems.

6.8 Limitations

This study provides valuable insights into point cloud up-sampling techniques for autonomous driving, but it is important to recognize its limitations. The evaluation was performed on a subset of the KITTI dataset, concentrating on a specific region within the xy plane. This narrow focus may not fully represent the diverse and complex scenarios encountered in real-world autonomous driving environments. Consequently, further investigation is needed to determine the generalizability of the findings to broader datasets and more challenging driving conditions.

On the other hand, while the Hausdorff distance serves as a reliable metric for assessing geometric accuracy, it does not encompass other aspects of point cloud quality, such as point density and uniformity. A more comprehensive evaluation framework that considers multiple metrics would provide a more holistic assessment of the up-sampling performance. Additionally, the subjective nature of visual assessment, as demonstrated in Fig. 6.3 and Fig.

6.4, underscores the need for standardized and quantitative evaluation metrics in point cloud upsampling research.

Furthermore, the study primarily focused on the two architectures, PU-Net and PU-GCN, and their performance with specific loss functions. Exploring other State-of-the-Art (SotA) architectures and loss functions, along with their potential combinations, could reveal additional insights and potentially uncover more effective upsampling strategies. Additionally, the impact of hyperparameter tuning and different training methodologies on the model's performance was not extensively investigated, leaving room for further optimization and refinement of the upsampling process.

Lastly, the real-time applicability of the proposed methods in autonomous driving systems requires further investigation. While the computational efficiency of PU-Net and PU-GCN is a positive aspect, real-time processing constraints and the need for low-latency inference pose additional challenges. Future research should focus on optimizing the models for real-time deployment, considering factors like memory consumption and computational resources available on autonomous vehicle platforms.

By acknowledging these limitations, this study lays the groundwork for future research directions in point cloud upsampling. Addressing these challenges will contribute to the development of more robust, accurate, and efficient upsampling techniques that can effectively enhance the perception capabilities of autonomous vehicles in diverse and demanding environments.

Chapter 7

Enhancing Battery Life and Performance in Autonomous Vehicles via Optimized AI Transformer Models for CO_2 Emission Prediction

7.1 Introduction

Autonomous and remote driving technologies have experimented with a surge in popularity and are expected to revolutionize the transportation landscape. Promising predictions by industry experts underscore the economic potential of autonomous vehicles. Cenex [14] projected a substantial profit of approximately GBP 27,000 per vehicle per year by 2030 for fleets of autonomous robotaxis. Moreover, NNT [129] forecasted the possibility of achieving 100% market penetration of autonomous cars by 2060. To facilitate technological evolution and ensure a common understanding of varying levels of automation, the SAE has established a comprehensive framework comprising five distinct levels of car automation [130]. These levels, ranging from Level 0 (L0) with no automation to Level 5 (L5) encompassing full self-driving automation, delineate the progression towards fully autonomous vehicles. Over

the course of this 40-year transition, it is anticipated that new autonomous capabilities, initially supported and supervised by human drivers, will emerge.

However, as concerns about carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions and the urgent need to mitigate their environmental impact intensify, there is a growing imperative to minimize the carbon footprint associated with transportation. Advancements in security, reliability, and trust are now propelling a paradigm shift towards scenarios where the human driver transitions to a supervisory role, focusing on optimizing energy efficiency to curb CO_2 emissions. Although the realization of SAE Level 5 automation may not be immediate, the integration of automated car control mechanisms offers immense potential to significantly reduce CO_2 emissions and address multiple societal challenges. By harnessing these transformative technologies, we can unlock tangible benefits, such as optimizing transportation patterns to minimize CO_2 output, implementing intelligent traffic management systems that reduce congestion and fuel consumption, and facilitating eco-friendly commuting options for urban areas. This harmonious fusion of automated car control and sustainability goals can pave the way for a greener and more environmentally responsible transportation ecosystem, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable future for our planet.

One important aspect of this transformation is optimizing driving time and energy usage in autonomous vehicles to improve battery life. By fine-tuning driving patterns, including acceleration, braking, and route selection, energy efficiency can be enhanced, thus extending battery life [131]. Furthermore, autonomous vehicles can implement intelligent energy management systems that dynamically adjust energy consumption based on real-time traffic conditions and the vehicle's energy state. This not only contributes to reducing CO_2 emissions but also supports the economic feasibility of large-scale deployment of autonomous fleets.

From the perspective of the underlying Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, transformers, originally introduced in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), have emerged as a powerful neural network architecture that has revolutionized various domains of AI. This breakthrough architecture is built upon the concept of self-attention mechanisms, enabling it to capture long-range dependencies and contextual information effectively. While initially developed for NLP, the applicability of transformers has extended beyond textual

data to other domains, including computer vision and time series analysis. In this paper, we explore the utilization of transformers in the context of predicting CO_2 emissions in SAE L2 self-driving vehicles. By leveraging the inherent strengths of transformers, such as their ability to model complex relationships and capture spatial and temporal dependencies, we aim to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of CO_2 emissions prediction models. We provide a detailed overview of the transformer architecture, highlighting its key components and mechanisms, and discuss how it can be adapted and optimized for our specific task. Through rigorous experimentation and evaluation, we demonstrate the effectiveness of transformers in surpassing previous approaches and advancing the state-of-the-art in CO_2 emissions prediction for self-driving vehicles.

Several studies around the field of 5G and beyond networks emphasize the necessity of researching and enhancing the paradigm of vehicular networks and self-driving vehicles' role. A key challenge lies in managing the computational complexity of the AI models required for every possible use case related to autonomous driving. Leveraging the capabilities of Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) for the computational load distribution of the vehicular networks can provide a solution to offload several tasks to the edge servers, thereby optimizing various aspects of Quality of Service (QoS) within these networks. Specifically, this approach brings computation closer to the end-user, reducing latency and improving responsiveness. It also minimizes the delay inherent in 5G networks, ensuring timely data transmission. Additionally, it shifts the responsibility for hardware compatibility and computational costs to the Deep Learning (DL) service provider, simplifying deployment for end-users and improving overall network efficiency. Consequently, exploring and enhancing vehicular networks in the context of 5G and beyond networks needs a multidisciplinary approach that integrates the contributions and findings in self-driving technologies with the paradigm of MEC.

The main contribution of this research is the design, implementation and validation of a transformer neural network architecture for CO_2 prediction. The following list summarizes the innovations provided in this manuscript concerning the state of the art:

- Extension of Transformer-Based Architectures: The research applies transformer-based architectures to time series analysis, specifically for predicting CO_2 emissions in self-driving vehicles, showcasing their adaptability beyond NLP.
- CO_2 ViT prediction model: A customized transformer architecture based on the Vision Transformers (ViT) [33] architecture is designed for CO_2 prediction in a dataset created from a self-driving vehicle (Toyota Prius Hybrid 2019 with OpenPilot [28] self-driving system), exploring the impact of the encoder and attention head variations.
- Comparison of Preprocessing Methods: Normalization outperforms standardization consistently, resulting in higher R2 scores and stronger correlations between predicted and actual CO_2 emissions.
- Deployed transformer model within an emulated 5G vehicular network infrastructure to evaluate its performance and resilience subjected to concurrent connections and requests.
- Comparison of standalone and distributed load tasks of the model's execution over the Edge segment of the emulated 5G vehicular network.

These contributions enhance CO_2 emission prediction accuracy, advancing the understanding of vehicle environmental impact and supporting sustainable transportation solutions. Moreover, deploying the ViT model to bring about MEC capabilities of a 5G network is a meaningful achievement of the model's resilience to concurrent connections and predictions.

This manuscript is organized as follows: Section 7.2 presents the specific transformer architecture used in our experiments for CO_2 emission prediction in self-driving vehicles. In Section 7.3, we describe the dataset utilized in our study, including the collection process and data preparation techniques. Section 7.4.1 details the conducted experiments and presents the results obtained, evaluating different configurations and parameters of the transformer model. Finally, in Section 7.6, we present the conclusions drawn from our research, highlighting the main findings and contributions of the study.

7.2 Proposed CO_2 ViT Prediction Model

In this section, we present the architecture of our CO_2 ViT model, which is based on the ViT [33] framework. While originally designed for image classification in computer vision, the ViT architecture and its variants have demonstrated their effectiveness in various tasks beyond image processing. In this context, we adapt and fine-tune the ViT architecture for the specific task of CO_2 prediction in self-driving vehicles, using the dataset described in section 7.3. The proposed CO_2 ViT model takes as input the vehicle's current and historical state, which consists of 8 features. Multiple configurations of previous states of the same vehicle are examined, as detailed in section 7.3. Notably, our model utilizes only the encoder component of the transformer architecture, omitting the decoder. This adaptation is justified as our task focuses on regression (predicting a continuous value, namely CO_2 emissions) rather than sequence-to-sequence tasks like translation or summarization, which typically necessitate both encoders and decoders. The encoder, with its self-attention mechanism, is sufficient to capture the temporal dependencies and relationships within the input sequence of vehicle states, making it suitable for our prediction task.

As explained in [4], the architecture of an Encoder for a Transformer consists of a normalization layer plus a Multi-Head Attention (MHA) layer. The output of the MHA is directed to a layer composed of a Feed Forward Network (FFN) followed by another normalization layer (see Fig. 2.18). The output data from the first layer of the encoder cannot be directly passed to the next encoder or Prediction Head without prior processing. This data transformation is carried out in the second layer of the encoder, which complements the traditional architecture defined for ViT in [33]. The model proposed in this work presents two main differences compared to the models presented in [33] and [4].

Traditionally, a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) model has been used as the FFN in this second layer of the Encoder, as seen in the architecture presented in [4] and [33]. One of our main contributions is the modification of this second layer of the Encoder, enhancing feature extraction through the revolutionary use of a CNN instead of an MLP as traditionally used. Unlike MLP layers, which primarily focus on linear transformations, CNNs excel at capturing spatial correlations and hierarchical representations within the input data. Since CNNs are

capable of implementing non-linear transformations, they support greater complexity in the variability and arrangement of the data used in this work, which is widely described in section 7.3.

The second optimisation is to use Location-Based attention in the MHA layer instead of scaled dot-product attention, as proposed in [33] for the original ViT architecture. In contrast to Scaled Dot-Product Attention, which computes attention globally without considering spatial and temporal proximity, Location-Based Attention restricts attention computation to nearby tokens, allowing the model to capture fine-grained spatial correlations and temporal dynamics. The optimizations applied to the model are depicted in Fig. ??, surrounded by a dashed red line around the CNN block in the Transformer Encoder in the Location-Based Attention in the MHA.

To transform the input into a format suitable for the subsequent layers, we apply a linear projection. This projection step maps the input values to a higher-dimensional space, enabling the model to capture complex relationships and dependencies among the different state variables. Furthermore, we incorporate position embeddings to provide positional information to the model. These embeddings encode the relative positions of the input elements and are added to the projected input.

The transformed input, enriched with position embeddings is then passed through a transformer encoder. In the proposed transformer encoder (see Fig. ??), there are two main blocks. The first of them is a residual block that adds the input to the encoder to the output of the MHA. The MHA consists of multiple layers of self-attention mechanisms and allows the model to attend to different parts of the input sequence while considering the dependencies among them. The second residual block adds the output of the first residual block to the output of a CNN. The purpose of the skip connection is to allow the information from the input to flow directly to the deeper layers of the network. By providing a direct path for the gradient during backpropagation, the skip connection helps in addressing the vanishing gradient problem that can hinder training in very deep networks. It allows the network to learn residual functions by explicitly modelling the difference between the input and the desired output. If there is more than one encoder in the architecture of the model, the

output of the previous one will be the input of the next one as the encoders will be placed sequentially.

Mathematically, the output of a transformer encoder can be represented as:

$$Block1Out = EncInput + MHA(Norm(EncoderInput)) \quad (7.1)$$

$$EncOut = Block1Out + MLP(Norm(Block1Out)) \quad (7.2)$$

Where MHA is the Multi-Head Attention Block and MLP is a Multi-Layer Perceptron.

The output from the last transformer encoder is subsequently fed into an MLP, which acts as the prediction head. The MLP is responsible for processing the learned representations and generating the final predictions. It applies a series of fully connected layers with non-linear activation functions, enabling the model to extract complex features and make high-level abstractions.

7.2.1 Operational Flowchart and Conditional Framework of the Proposed CO_2 ViT Prediction Model

This section details the operational flowchart and conditional framework of the proposed CO_2 ViT prediction model, as depicted in Fig. 7.1. This framework comprises seven stages that outline the process from acquiring the vehicle's state to the CO_2 ViT model's prediction of CO_2 emissions based on that state.

Firstly, we ask for the onboard vehicle's status parameters using specialized software running on a laptop interfaced with the car's Controller Area Network (CAN) bus through the On-Board Diagnostics II (OBD-II) port. This specialized software utilizes a protocol similar to Unified Diagnostic Services (UDS) to regularly query the vehicle's Electronic Control Units (ECU), retrieving a set of predefined parameters at a consistent rate of 5 Hz (see 1 in Fig. 7.1). Given that each metric is collected from a different ECU with varying sampling rates, alignment is necessary for real-time monitoring. This ensures that all input data required by the deep learning model is available for a given timestamp (see 2 in Fig.

7.1). Consequently, this aligned data is published via an API client to the API server located at the Edge premises that collects and carries out the the preprocessing steps for the raw data (see 3 in Fig. 7.1). These preprocessing steps consist of filtering the 21 parameters received to 9, which are the ones most related to the CO₂ emissions (further described in section 7.3) and then normalising the data to allow the model to perform its best when predicting the CO₂ emissions (see 4 in Fig. 7.1).

With the data prepared and cleaned, the CO₂ViT model consumes the data and infers the predicted CO₂ value (see 5 in Fig. 7.1). The model’s architecture, a main contribution of this work, is thoroughly explained in Fig. ???. The predicted CO₂ value is then returned as a response to the API client located in the vehicle (see 6 in Fig. 7.1). The API client forwards this prediction to the CAN Packet Encapsulator ECU, which converts it from its current data type into a CAN message, enabling transmission over the car’s CAN Bus using our custom OBD-II library (see 7 in Fig. 7.1). Finally, this prediction can be utilized by the self-driving system, displayed to alert the human driver, or both, serving as feedback to adjust the driving style and reduce CO₂ emissions (see 8 in Fig. 7.1).

Fig. 7.1 Operational Flowchart and Conditional Framework of the Proposed CO₂ ViT Prediction Model.

7.2.2 Advantages of the Proposed Transformer-based Architecture

Compared with alternative architectures like Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks, the transformer architecture offers several advantages in the context of our vehicle state prediction task.

Firstly, transformers enable parallelization during training and inference, resulting in faster computations. Unlike LSTMs that process inputs sequentially, transformers can handle input sequences in parallel, making them more computationally efficient, particularly when dealing with long sequences.

Secondly, the Location-Based mechanism employed allows the model to capture global dependencies within the input sequence. By attending to all input elements simultaneously, transformers can effectively model long-range dependencies, which can be challenging for LSTMs that primarily rely on sequential information flow.

Furthermore, CO_2 ViT exhibits scalability when processing large input sequences. The Location-Based attention mechanism can capture relationships between distant elements without the need for recurrent connections. This scalability property is advantageous as it allows the model to handle extensive input sequences without significantly increasing computational requirements.

Another advantage is that transformers do not suffer from the vanishing gradient problem that can occur in deep LSTM architectures. This property enables transformers to propagate information more effectively across layers, facilitating better long-term memory retention and gradient flow during training.

Moreover, transformers offer interpretability benefits through their attention mechanism. The attention weights generated during processing provide insights into the importance of different parts of the input sequence for making predictions. This may help in understanding the model's decision-making process and identifying critical features for vehicle state prediction.

Additionally, the utilization of a 1D CNN within the transformer encoder block enhances the model's capability to capture local spatial features within the CO_2 data. This enables the

model to extract relevant information more efficiently, contributing to improved predictive performance.

By leveraging these advantages, our CO_2 ViT model based on the transformer architecture demonstrates enhanced capability in capturing complex dependencies within the vehicle state data. This leads to improved predictive performance compared to traditional LSTM-based approaches.

7.3 Dataset

In this section, the collection process and the statistics of our dataset are presented. The data was obtained utilizing a commercial vehicle available in the market equipped with Openpilot, an SAE level 2 self-driving system. The vehicle used was a Toyota Prius Plug-in Hybrid (2019). This vehicle features a 4-stroke, 4-cylinder 1798 cc gasoline engine that can output 90 kW of power. The maximum torque achieved is 142 Nm at 3600 RPM. As per the emissions, the vehicle is categorised under the Euro-class scheme as a Euro 6 DG type; according to official manufacturer information, the vehicle emits 28 g/km of CO_2 (WLTP test).

Moreover, the exhaust CO_2 concentration in parts per million (ppm) was measured and recorded using a SprintIR-R 20 sensor. This sensor, chosen for its suitability in this specific application, demonstrated accurate readings of CO_2 concentrations up to 20% with a precision of ± 70 ppm and a resolution of 10 ppm. The sensor employed Non-Dispersive Infrared (NDIR) technology and had a maximum sampling frequency of 50 Hz. Positioned at the rear of the vehicle, the sensor was securely connected to the exhaust pipe. Specialized tools, including a hydrophobic filter, water trap, and particulate filter, were utilized to eliminate impurities and water vapour from the CO_2 analytics, minimizing the risk of incorrect readings. The CO_2 collection system included an electric pump to maintain a consistent sample flow rate of 0.5 l/min through the sensor's measurement chamber. The CO_2 sensor was directly connected to an ESP32 microcontroller using a serial connection, with measurement requests

initiated at a rate of 5 Hz. Prior to each drive, the sensor underwent manual calibration, referencing external air and assuming a CO_2 concentration value of 400 ppm for accuracy.

The collection of the onboard vehicle status parameters was carried out with custom software executed on a laptop that was connected to the vehicle's CAN bus via its OBD-II port. The software was written in Python and performs UDS-like queries to periodically report a list of given parameters obtained from the vehicle's ECU [132] at a fixed rate. The collection of parameters was done at 5 Hz. During the data collection process, the SAE 2 self-driving system was in operation.

Previous datasets typically feature either a constant ppm concentration in the case of petrol engines or a limited fluctuation range (usually between 80,000 and 120,000 ppm) for diesel engines [133, 134]. In contrast, our dataset, which includes HVs with hybrid engines, exhibits a distribution spanning the entire range of possible values from 400 to approximately 155,000 ppm.

The set of parameters acquired from the vehicle's CAN bus comprises the following 21 parameters: accelerator position (%), vehicle speed (MPH), external atmospheric pressure (psi), engine load (%), coolant temperature ($^{\circ}C$), acceleration (m/s^2), distance travelled since vehicle startup (miles), drive mode, engine exhaust flow rate (kg/h), engine mode, engine speed (RPM), EV mode status, engine power delivered (kW), hybrid battery SOC (%), mass air flow (g/min), electric motor power delivered (kW), electric motor revolution (RPM), electric motor torque (Nm), GPS latitude, GPS longitude and altitude (m).

Specific input features selection was conducted to identify a subset of input features that are most pertinent to the output variable and also to eliminate unnecessary information in the prediction process. To perform the input selection, the significance of the input data and the correlation among features should be estimated. Hence, to identify the most relevant parameters for this use case.

The first attempt to identify the most useful parameters was to calculate their correlation coefficients. Firstly, a correlation matrix was created with the entire set of parameters described. The technique implemented was the Spearman-based correlation matrix, which provides a correlation coefficient based on the statistical dependence of ranking between two

variables and covers non-linear relationships. The parameters with a high correlation score among them were eliminated, and the ones with a high correlation with the CO₂ concentration were kept. Based on the observations seen in the correlation matrix, the parameters accelerator position, external atmospheric pressure, engine load, distance travelled since vehicle startup, drive mode, EV mode status, engine power delivered, electric motor power delivered, electric motor revolution, electric motor torque and altitude were removed, since they were considered less influential for the prediction. In addition, GPS coordinates of the car, i.e., latitude and longitude, were also discarded from the dataset, since the location of the car should not be a decisive factor in the prediction. As a result, Fig. 7.2 presents the correlation matrix featuring the eight final selected input parameters and the output parameter to be predicted. Moreover, the resulting input parameters and the statistics of the dataset are presented and listed in Table 7.1.

This dataset includes a total of 86,000 elements, from which 80% were used for training and 20% was used for testing. The collection of parameters was done at 5 Hz; we stored the information recorded on separate files and drives and then merged it. Fig. 7.3 illustrates the sequence diagram of the data collection process.

Table 7.1 CO₂ dataset statistics.

Parameter	Units	Mean	St. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Median	Variability
Deceleration sensor	m/s ²	0.011	0.804	-7.058	4.634	0.071	67.758215
Exhaust flow rate	kg/h	32.222	47.144	0	242.2	0	1.463115
Engine mode	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	3	N/A	1.158902
Engine speed	rpm	714.012	915.787	0	4512	0	1.282594
Vehicle speed	mph	31.786	22.053	0	79.535	30.447	0.693794
Mass airflow	g/min	1131.515	3810.806	18	19686.6	25.8	3.364905
Coolant temperature	°C	84.040	11.067	23	114	84	0.131697
Hybrid battery SOC	%	16.191	8.0386	10.58	41.55	12.54	0.496476
Exhaust CO ₂ concentration	ppm	58107.415	58311.550	400	154900	3730	1.003513

Fig. 7.4 depicts the distribution of CO₂ concentration in parts per million (ppm) within the dataset. Notably, most samples in the dataset fall within the range defined by the minimum and maximum CO₂ concentration values. The low-ppm measurements, which represent 53.73% (left side in Fig. 7.4, where the engine is off) of the total data, were captured while the combustion engine of the hybrid vehicle was turned off. On the other hand, the high-ppm

Fig. 7.2 Correlation matrix composed of the final input values selected for the dataset.

measurements, which represent 38.41% (right side in Fig. 7.4, where the engine is on) of the total data, were collected while the combustion engine was functioning. The remaining values of the dataset were captured during the transition process of starting and stopping the combustion engine.

7.4 Testbeds

We touch upon the advancements in transformer-based architectures for time series analysis, emphasizing their adaptability and effectiveness beyond their initial applications in NLP. By understanding transformers' fundamental principles and mechanisms, we can leverage their strengths in our specific context of predicting CO_2 emissions in SAE-L2 self-driving

Fig. 7.3 Data collection sequence diagram. Notice that after the acquisition of every acECU parameter and the CO_2 concentration, the received messages have to be re-scaled and transformed from hexadecimal to decimal notation.

Fig. 7.4 Histogram of CO_2 concentration (ppm) present in the dataset.

vehicles. Hence, this section covers the definition of the use cases and scenarios’ testbed used in this paper. The first testbed aims to obtain the best parameter configuration for the ViT model. Later, the ViT model was deployed in an emulated 5G vehicular network testbed with the main objective to evaluate the performance and resilience of the CO_2 ViT to high loads of requests.

7.4.1 Transformer Model Evaluation and Optimization testbed

To thoroughly investigate the impact of architectural choices on CO_2 emission prediction, a comprehensive series of experiments was conducted using transformer architecture described

in section 7.2. The following configurations were examined: 1, 2, 4 and 6 encoders using 2, 6, 10 and 12 attention heads for each one of the encoder options (see Algorithm 2).

To provide a holistic evaluation, the experiments also considered different numbers of previous states of the vehicle, specifically 32, 64, and 128 prior car states, and two data preprocessing techniques, normalization and standardization (see Algorithm 2). The dataset used for training and evaluation was prepared according to the process outlined in section 7.3, ensuring the consistency and integrity of the collected CO_2 emissions data using a commercial car (Toyota Prius Hybrid 2019) while the SAE 2 self-driving system was operating (see Algorithm 2).

Algorithm 2: Training Loop

```

1 foreach encoders in [1,2,4,6] do
2   foreach attn heads in [2,6,10,12] do
3     foreach previous states in [32,64,128] do
4       Get predictions
5       Calculate loss
6       Backpropagation
7       Update model weights
8     end foreach
9   end foreach
10 end foreach

```

As well, we desired to conduct a fair comparison between the model proposed in this paper and the one proposed in [13] in terms of both R_2 score and inference time, as in [13] appears that their model has a R_2 score of 0.97. For the comparison, we deployed the model in PyTorch [135], while the original paper employed TensorFlow. By adopting this comparative approach, we aimed to provide an unbiased evaluation of the performance differences between the two frameworks. The model architecture and hyperparameters were meticulously replicated according to the specifications outlined in [13]. The training hyperparameters used during the training process for the LSTM presented in [13] and for the CO_2 ViT can be found in Table 7.2.

On the other hand, the hyperparameters for the CO_2 ViT models were determined through a systematic hyperparameter tuning process using the PyTorch Lightning framework. PyTorch

Lightning [?] offers a convenient and efficient way to automate hyperparameter optimization, allowing us to explore a wide range of values and configurations. We employed a grid search strategy, where a predefined set of hyperparameter values was systematically evaluated, and the configuration yielding the best performance on a validation set was selected. Specifically, we explored a range of learning rates, batch sizes and number of epochs. The final values presented in Table 7.2 correspond to the optimal configuration identified during this tuning process, resulting in the highest R^2 score on the validation set. We believe this approach ensures a fair and rigorous evaluation of the model's performance while minimizing the risk of overfitting. As a result, all the transformer architectures explored during the experiments were trained over 200 epochs, a learning rate of 1.6×10^{-4} , Mean Square Error (MSE) as the loss function and Adam as the optimizer.

Table 7.2 Hyperparameters used during the training process for the CO_2 ViT and the LSTM presented in [13].

HP	LSTM	ViT
Epochs	200	100
Lr	1.6×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-4}
Batch Size	32	32
Optimizer	Adam	Adam

All the experiments were carried out using Ubuntu 20.04, PyTorch [135] 2.0.0 and CUDA 11.8 in an NVIDIA 1080 GPU card and an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700K CPU @ 4.20GH.

7.4.2 5G Vehicular networks testbed

This section covers the experiment's testbed configured to demonstrate the effectiveness and resilience of the proposed CO_2 ViT model in the particular use case of a 5G vehicular network. The setup consists of multiple 5G topology scenarios' configurations, emulating from 2 to 128 self-driving cars connected to the 5G network. The CO_2 ViT model is instantiated as a MEC capability by the 5G Digital Service Provider (DSP). Hence, the computational cost of the CO_2 ViT model is offloaded from the final user (the car) to the MEC. This allows the

car's driver to leverage the Edge communication and computational capabilities and retrieve the results of their CO_2 emissions. These 5G network topology scenarios are emulated via the Common Open Research Emulation (CORE) tool [136]. This emulation tool uses Linux Network Namespaces (netns) to emulate each self-driving car and each network device deployed in the infrastructure. The authors enhanced the work from previous publications [137–139] to achieve the MEC capabilities of the 5G network and the execution of the ViT model on the Edge segment of the network. The emulated 5G network and experiments have been executed on a physical machine with the following specifications: Ubuntu 20.04, Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v4 @ 2.20GHz, 32GB of DDR4 Synchronous 2400 MHz and GeForce GTX TITAN X.

Fig. 7.5 represents the 5G network topology scenarios emulated in the experiments. The topology consists of a single telecommunication Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP) which divides its physical resources into the following:

- Two Next Generation NodeB (gNodeB) represented in the diagram as antennas.
- A Distributed Unit (DU) on each gNodeB. Leveraging the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) protocol, the DUs encapsulate the raw data from the self-driving cars.
- A physical computer at the Edge segment hosting from 1 to 2 different DSP, depicted in Fig. 7.5 as Tenant A and B.
- A physical computer at the Core segment hosting both DSPs for self-driving car authentication purposes.
- A set of physical routers at the transport and inter-domain segments.

Every car connects to the network gNodeB through the wireless link (see 1 in Fig. 7.5). Every self-driving car sends its CO_2 metrics every second via an HTTP client to the specified server by their particular DSP. The gNodeB and the DU devices transform and encapsulate from wireless communication to CPRI traffic, routing the traffic to the specific Edge ISP physical computer (see 2 in Fig. 7.5). Once the traffic arrives at the Edge ISP, the virtual switches perform the routing and isolation tasks to redirect the traffic to the specific DSP,

hence achieving the multi-tenancy characteristic of the 5G and beyond networks. The network traffic gets to the virtual Central Unit (vCU) instantiated in each DSP, and then is routed back to the Edge ISP with the Core ISP as destiny (see 4 in Fig. 7.5). Before the network traffic departs from the Edge ISP, this computer encapsulates the traffic with the Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation (GENEVE) protocol. Once the network flow arrives at the Core ISP computer, it de-encapsulates the network traffic and learns which DSP needs to route it to (see 5 in Fig. 7.5). The virtual switch at the ISP Core redirects the traffic to the specific DSP and User Plane Function (UPF) (see 6 in Fig. 7.5). Afterwards, the traffic could leave the 5G Core domain and be routed to the inter-domain segment (it may also be considered the internet). However, for this experiment's purpose and after the car has been authenticated in the 5G network, each DSP hosts an HTTP server with the ViT model.

Each self-driving car is prepared with a validation set of the collected metrics (see further details about this dataset in Section 7.3) and sends a small subset of data every second. This subset of data is later translated by the proposed CO_2 ViT model as a batch of size 10. The HTTP server instantiated at each DSP receives the request from the car and executes the model's prediction. Then, the HTTP server responds to the self-driving car with the predicted CO_2 value of the ViT model. This scenario allows the researchers to evaluate three relevant time metrics: I) the self-driving car's delay in the HTTP request-response, which is the accumulated latency of every network segment involved; II) the HTTP server request-response delay at the server side; III) the inference time of the ViT model. These time metrics are relevant to evaluating the model's performance and behaviour by changing the number of concurrent connections by multiple self-driving cars.

Table 7.3 outlines the two distinct 5G network topology scenarios, labelled A and B, designed and deployed for this experiment. Both scenarios accommodate a range of 2 to 128 connected cars. The key difference lies in the distribution of Digital Service Providers (DSPs), each hosting a ViT model. Scenario A employs a single DSP, while scenario B incorporates a second DSP to evaluate the impact of horizontal scaling on prediction tasks. This division of scenarios into separate experiments allows for in-depth analysis of how the deep learning model's behaviour changes under varying network topologies.

Table 7.3 Network topology for test bed in scenarios A and B.

Scenario	No Cars	No gNB	No DSP	No Edge	No Core
A	[2-128]	1	1	1	1
B	[2-128]	2	2	1	1

Fig. 7.5 Emulated 5G MEC testbed and proposed workflow for the evaluation of the CO_2ViT performance.

7.5 Results and discussion

This section covers the discussion of the results obtained for each of the testbeds presented in the previous sections. The first testbed has been validated to get the best CO_2ViT model configuration. On the other hand, the second testbed presents results related to the performance of the CO_2ViT model once it is deployed in a 5G vehicular network scenario.

7.5.1 Transformer model evaluation and optimization testbed results discussion

The experiments were designed to investigate the performance of a transformer architecture in predicting CO_2 emissions for a Toyota Prius Hybrid 2019 while a self-driving SAE Level 2 system (see section 7.3) was in control of the vehicle.

In these experiments, we varied different parameters of the proposed architecture (see section 7.2) such as the number of transformer encoders, the number of multi-attention heads per encoder and the number of previous states for the current input of the dataset. We used 1, 2, 4 and 6 transformer encoders. For each of them, we used 2, 6, 10 and 12 multi-attention heads per encoder. Additionally, we varied the number of previous states for the input in 32,

64 and 128. Refer to Algorithm 2 for a better explanation in pseudocode. Tables 7.4 and 7.5 present the configurations that obtained the highest R^2 score.

The choice of the number of encoders aimed to explore the impact of model depth on prediction accuracy. It was hypothesized that increasing the number of encoders might allow for better capture of complex patterns and dependencies in the data. However, it was observed that for configurations with 4 and 6 encoders, none of the combinations with different attention heads yielded positive R_2 scores (see Tables 7.4 and 7.5). This suggests that an excessive number of encoders might introduce noise or overfitting, leading to suboptimal predictions for CO_2 emissions.

Upon analyzing the results from Tables 7.4 (results for normalized data) and 7.5 (results for standardized data), where the R_2 score for each one of the proposed architectures are shown, it is clear that the normalization preprocessing method consistently yielded higher R_2 scores compared to standardization. Configurations with normalization consistently achieved R_2 scores close to 1, indicating a strong correlation between the predicted and actual CO_2 emissions. Notably, the configuration with 2 encoders and 6 attention heads stood out with an impressive R_2 score of 0.9899, achieving SotA results and suggesting a highly accurate prediction of CO_2 emissions for the dataset described in 7.3. On the other hand, configurations using standardization struggled to surpass an R_2 score of 0.35, indicating a weaker relationship between the predicted and actual emissions. Therefore, it is crucial to correct the statement regarding preprocessing methods. The experiments demonstrated that normalization significantly outperformed standardization in terms of CO_2 emission prediction accuracy for the Toyota Prius Hybrid 2019 dataset. This emphasizes the importance of appropriate data preprocessing techniques in improving the performance of the transformer architecture for CO_2 emission prediction tasks. These results are surprising having into account that in [13], the authors achieve an R^2 score of 0.97 by applying standardisation to a very similar dataset using an LSTM model.

It is worth noting that the configuration with 6 encoders and 12 attention heads aligns with the architecture described in the original ViT paper [33], which demonstrated successful results in image-related tasks. However, in our specific use case of predicting CO_2 emissions

for the dataset described in 7.3, this configuration did not yield positive R2 scores. This highlights the importance of considering the specific requirements and characteristics of the task at hand when applying transformer architectures. While the 6 encoders and 12 attention heads configuration worked well for image tasks, it may not be optimal for our CO_2 emission prediction task, indicating the need for customization and adaptation of the architecture to suit the specific domain and dataset.

The experiments also investigated the influence of the number of previous states (previously observed vehicle states) considered by the model. Three values were tested: 32, 64, and 128. Including a higher number of previous states should allow the model to capture more temporal dependencies in the data, potentially leading to improved predictions. However, the inclusion of a higher number of previous states did not consistently lead to improved predictions for CO_2 emissions. In fact, for certain configurations, particularly those with 128 previous states, the R2 scores were negative values. This suggests that increasing the number of previous states may have had a detrimental effect on the model's performance. While the initial expectation was that incorporating more previous states would allow the model to capture additional temporal dependencies and enhance prediction accuracy, the results demonstrate a different outcome. It appears that beyond a certain threshold, increasing the number of previous states may introduce noise or excessive complexity, leading to a decline in the model's performance. Therefore, it is important to correct the statement regarding the influence of previous states. The experiments indicate that while including a moderate number of previous states (32 and 64) may contribute to improved predictions, increasing the number to 128 did not yield better results and, in fact, led to negative R2 scores. This suggests the presence of a point of diminishing returns or increased computational complexity when incorporating a higher number of previous states in the CO_2 emission prediction model.

Attention heads, another crucial parameter in transformer architectures, were varied across configurations. The attention mechanism enables the model to focus on different parts of the input data during the prediction process. Four different numbers of attention heads were tested: 2, 6, 10, and 12. The intention behind this variation was to assess the impact of attention head count on the model's ability to capture and model the relationships within

the input data. It was observed that higher numbers of attention heads, such as 6 and 12, generally led to improved R_2 scores compared with the configurations with fewer attention heads. Notably, configuration 1 with normalized preprocessing, 32 previous states, and 6 attention heads achieved a reasonably high R_2 score of 0.9805. Similarly, configuration 2, which shared the same parameters as configuration 1 but with 12 attention heads, achieved an even higher R_2 score of 0.9898. These results highlight the importance of finding a balance in the number of attention heads, as an excessive number may not always lead to improved performance.

In table 7.4 it is shown that the transformer model with 2 encoders and 12 attention heads achieves a R_2 score of 0.9898. Table 7.6 shows the results of the model proposed in [13] deployed in PyTorch and executed on the machine with the specifications described in section 7.4.1. The LSTM model does not perform well when the data is normalized, but it does perform well when the data is standardised, achieving a R_2 score of 0.9712 when using 32 previous states. Comparing the results of the transformer model with the LSTM it can be concluded that the transformer model performs better if we use a metric the R_2 score.

Additionally, Table 7.7 shows the mean inference time in ms over 2000 iterations for the best transformer configurations and the LSTM model presented in [13]. To obtain the inference times, all the models were deployed and executed using a machine with Ubuntu 20.04, PyTorch [135] 2.0.0 and CUDA 11.8 in an NVIDIA 1080 GPU card and an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700K CPU @ 4.20GH. In [13], the authors say that their LSTM model deployed in Tensorflow [140] is able to infer the CO_2 concentration in the same vehicle as the one we have used in 21.64 ms when feeding 32 previous states to the model. Table 7.7 shows how all the tested models during the experiments infer in less than 5 ms, and that the model which gave the maximum R^2 score (0.9890) with 1 encoder and 64 previous states, is able to predict the CO_2 concentration in 0.3904 ms. This shows the advantages of parallelization that models based on transformers use. Moreover, in table 7.7 is shown as well that our implementation of the model presented in [13] in PyTorch predicts the CO_2 emissions of the vehicle in 2.35 ms when using 32 previous states, 3.20 ms when using 64 previous states and 6.52 ms when using 128 previous states. As expressed in table 7.7, the

transformer model with the highest R_2 score (0.9898), which has 2 encoders and 12 attention heads for 32 previous steps, returns the CO_2 prediction in 0.6784 ms. This is 71.14% faster than the LSTM for 32 previous states.

Overall, the findings emphasize the significance of parameter selection in transformer architectures for CO_2 emission prediction tasks. The number of encoders, preprocessing methods, number of previous states, and attention heads all play critical roles in determining the model's performance. Through careful tuning and experimentation, researchers and practitioners can optimize these parameters to enhance the accuracy and reliability of CO_2 emission predictions. This, in turn, contributes to a better understanding of the environmental impact of vehicles and aids in the development of sustainable transportation solutions.

Table 7.4 Model configurations that achieved the highest R^2 scores for normalized data.

Encoders	Previous Steps	Attention Heads	R2
1	32	12	0.9828
	64	6	0.989
	128	2	-1.53
2	32	12	0.9898
	64	2	-2.83
	128	2	-2.07
4	32	2	-2.56
	64	2	-1.99
	128	2	-2.32
6	32	2	-2.99
	64	2	-2.54
	128	2	-2.12

7.5.2 5G Vehicular networks testbed results discussion

The following section covers the results and findings of the experiments carried out with the second testbed described in the previous section 7.4. These experiments are divided into two main scenarios, also expanded in Table 7.3. The evaluation metrics used in this analysis are the following:

Table 7.5 Model configurations that achieved the highest R^2 scores for standardized data.

Encoders	Previous Steps	Attention Heads	R2
1	32	12	0.3443
	64	6	0.3423
	128	2	-3.42
2	32	6	0.3407
	64	2	-2.72
	128	2	-2.88
4	32	2	0.3148
	64	2	0.2297
	128	2	-2.31
6	32	12	0.2387
	64	12	0.2214
	128	128	0.1677

Table 7.6 Highest R^2 scores for the LSTM model for standardized and normalized data for the different configurations tested..

Data preprocessing	Previous Steps	R2
Normalization	32	-2.5344
	64	-2.1123
	128	-2.5602
Standardization	32	0.9712
	64	0.9701
	128	0.25

Table 7.7 Highest R^2 scores for the LSTM and CO₂ViT models for standardized and normalized data for the different configurations tested.

Model	Encoders	Previous Steps	Attention Heads	R^2	Inf.Time (ms)
Transformer	1	12	32	0.9828	0.3904
	1	6	64	0.9890	0.5563
	2	12	32	0.9898	0.6784
LSTM	-	-	32	0.9712	2.35
	-	-	64	0.9701	3.2
	-	-	128	0.25	6.52

- **Car delay:** calculated as the elapsed time between two timestamps. The starting sampling time matches with the first request of a self-driving vehicle to the 5G Edge

computer HTTP server, and the final timestamp corresponds to the response received from the 5G Edge computer HTTP server in synchronous mode. This delay is measured in milliseconds (ms). This delay is relevant to measure due to the emulation complexity of the 5G network topology over a single physical machine. Thus, this emulation carries high computational load to the testbed machine and the results might be affected.

- **Server delay:** calculated as the elapsed time in ms between two timestamps on the server side. The HTTP server will create the first timestamp when receives an HTTP request and will create the last timestamp right before sending the corresponding response.
- **Inference time:** calculated to measure the consumed time of the CO_2ViT for the prediction. It is worth noting that, as described in section 7.4.1, the model's prediction is made for a batch size of 10 samples.

The measure of these three different delays allows us to determine how the experiments distribute the resources and find possible bottlenecks in the network or the CO_2ViT . Among all the models trained during the experiments carried out in section 7.5.1, only one has been used for the experiments discussed in this section. The chosen architecture has been the one that achieved the highest R^2 value (0.9898), which is composed of 2 encoders with 12 MAH. Fig. 7.6 and 7.7 represent the described delays for the experiments executed. Due to the scaling difference between the car and server delay, we decided to divide each figure into two sub-figures for better understanding. The Y-axis represents the specified delays in ms, while the X-axis represents the number of concurrent car connections to the CO_2ViT model in the Edge segment of the 5G network.

Fig. 7.6a depicts the car delay for scenario A along the 7 different car configurations (from 2 to 128 concurrent connected cars). It can be observed that the delay linearly grows when the number of cars is increased from 2 to 16. The delay goes from 9.58 ms to 41.01 ms. However, emulating 32 or more connected cars produces a higher delay for the cars. On the other hand, its relative Fig. 7.6b, representing the delay server-side of the network, the delay remains stable from 7.91 ms to 8.7 ms for 2 to 64 connected cars yet the car is having higher

delays in the executions of 32 and 64 concurrent connected cars. For the last execution (128 cars), the inference time and server delay reached 14.91 ms and 15.31 ms respectively. The difference in the results between car and server-side demonstrates that the DL is resilient enough to handle from 2 to 64 concurrent connected cars in this particular scenario, but the physical machine and network emulator add high load to the experiments and the cars are suffering higher delay.

On the other hand, Fig. 7.7a represents the car’s delay for scenario B and the 7 different car configurations. As well as for scenario A, the car delay linearly grows from 2 to 16 connected cars, with values from 11.72 ms to 40.67 ms. However, for the rest of the experiments, the delay behaves abnormally due to high peaks of computational loads in the machine. Fig. 7.7b, as well as for scenario A, the server side delay remains stable with values that varied from 7.90 ms to 8.77 ms for each delay measurement (server and inference time) from 2 to 64 connected cars. Delay’s increase compared to scenario A is directly related to the complexity of the 5G network topology to be emulated.

(a) Car’s delay for scenario A, sends a request for prediction to the server and waits for response. (b) Server-side delays for scenario A, green represents the server’s request handling and yellow the inference time of the model for a batch size of 10 samples.

Fig. 7.6 Delay results for scenario A, from 2 to 128 cars connected to a single DSP hosting the CO_2 ViT.

(a) Car's delay for scenario B, sends a request for prediction to the server and waits for response. (b) Server-side delays for scenario B, green represents the server's request handling and yellow the inference time of the model for a batch size of 10 samples.

Fig. 7.7 Delay results for scenario B, from 2 to 128 cars connected to two DSPs hosting the CO_2 ViT.

7.6 Conclusions

To sum up, we can draw several conclusions regarding the optimization of transformer models for CO_2 emission prediction in self-driving vehicles.

Firstly, our research has demonstrated that transformer models are a powerful tool for predicting CO_2 emissions in self-driving vehicles. Leveraging the inherent strengths of transformers, such as their ability to model complex relationships and capture spatial and temporal dependencies, we emphasize the superior predictive capabilities of our transformer model, reaching an inference time 71.14% faster than the previous State-of-the-Art (SOTA) model, while also achieving a higher R2 score of 0.9898 compared to the one obtained by the previous SOTA method. This breakthrough architecture is built upon the concept of Location-Based attention mechanisms, enabling it to capture long-range dependencies and contextual information effectively.

Secondly, our experimental analysis has shown that customization strategies can be used to further optimize transformer models for CO_2 emission prediction. Through extensive experimentation and evaluation on a dataset specifically designed for predicting CO_2 emissions in self-driving vehicles, we were able to identify effective customization strategies that reduced CO_2 emissions, such as the use of 1D CNNs in the Transformer Encoder and use

Location-Based attention in the MHA. These findings highlight the potential of transformers in this domain and present avenues for future research and refinement of CO_2 emissions estimation in autonomous driving scenarios.

Moreover, the results achieved in our second proposed testbed have demonstrated the resilience of our CO_2 ViT model in the face of changes and concurrent connections. For the emulated environment and experiments, from 2 to 16 concurrent connections the self-driving vehicles' delay grows linearly, yet for 32, 64 and 128 connected cars, the physical resources to emulate the 5G infrastructure become weak. This is understood because of the different behaviour of the delays: first, on the cars and the rest on the server side. On the other hand, the inference time of the deployed models over the 5G infrastructure for 64 concurrent connected vehicles in scenarios A and B are 4.31 ms and 8.42 ms respectively. Hence, we conclude that we would need more physical resources to achieve a high stress on our CO_2 ViT. It is worth noting the difference between the inference time obtained in both testbeds for the CO_2 ViT (refer to Sections 7.5.1 and 7.5.2). This difference can be explained by the lack of resources in the emulated 5G network topology and environment.

Furthermore, optimizing the driving itself can further enhance the prediction model efficiency in terms of reducing CO_2 emissions. For instance, extending the driving time in specific scenarios can help reduce fuel consumption by optimizing vehicle speed and avoiding unnecessary acceleration or deceleration. This aspect of optimization could be integrated with the CO_2 ViT model, allowing for predictive insights that contribute to both immediate emission reductions and long-term sustainability.

Finally, our research contributes to a more sustainable and environmentally conscious future for transportation systems. By accurately predicting and optimizing CO_2 emissions, we can mitigate the environmental impact of transportation and aid in the development of sustainable transportation solutions. Our findings provide valuable insights into the environmental impact of self-driving vehicles and contribute to a better understanding of their role in achieving a more sustainable future.

In conclusion, our research demonstrates that transformer models are an effective tool for predicting CO_2 emissions in self-driving vehicles. Through careful tuning and experimenta-

tion with customization strategies, we were able to enhance their accuracy and reliability. Our findings contribute to a better understanding of the environmental impact of vehicles and aid in the development of sustainable transportation solutions. In future work, we plan to further explore the output of the prediction to enable the predictive operation of the vehicle to minimise CO_2 emissions. Additionally, to explore further the different possible topologies for MEC applications of our CO_2 ViT model in 5G and beyond networks, distributing the physical resources for the emulation of the environments.

7.7 Limitations

While this research offers valuable findings, it is important to note some limitations. The data used, while collected carefully and based on real driving situations, is limited in its size and range. It only includes data from one type of car (Toyota Prius Plug-in Hybrid 2019) under specific conditions, which might not reflect how other cars or driving behaviors affect CO_2 emissions. To make the results more applicable, it would be beneficial to collect data from a wider variety of cars and driving situations.

Furthermore, the 5G vehicular network emulation, while providing valuable insights, does not fully replicate the complexities of real-world 5G networks. Factors such as network congestion, varying signal strengths, and interference from other devices were not explicitly modeled. Validation through testing on actual 5G networks would be beneficial to ensure the model's performance under real-world conditions.

The transformer model itself, while more efficient than LSTM models, still demands substantial computational resources. This could hinder its deployment in resource-constrained edge devices, necessitating further research into model compression techniques or optimizations to reduce complexity without compromising performance.

Additionally, this study concentrates solely on CO_2 emission prediction, excluding other pollutants and environmental factors contributing to a vehicle's overall environmental impact. A more comprehensive analysis would consider additional parameters like nitrogen oxides NO_x and Particulate Matter (PM) emissions to provide a more holistic assessment.

Finally, while the study investigates different configurations of the transformer model, the full spectrum of potential architectures remains unexplored. Further research could examine alternative transformer variants, such as those incorporating attention mechanisms like Reformer or Performer, which might yield further improvements in efficiency and performance.

In acknowledging these limitations, this study paves the way for future research to address these challenges. Overcoming these limitations will advance the development of even more accurate and efficient CO_2 emission prediction models for self-driving vehicles, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable transportation ecosystem.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter offers a comprehensive overview of the research presented in this thesis. It is structured into three distinct sections to achieve this goal. The first section revisits the initial objectives established at the outset of the project, serving as a reminder of the core research questions and motivations. The second section provides a detailed summary of the methodologies, experiments, and findings outlined in the preceding chapters, showcasing the progress made towards fulfilling the stated objectives. Lastly, a forward-looking section explores potential avenues for future research, outlining how this work can be expanded and built upon to further advance the field.

8.1 Focused key research areas

This thesis is situated at the intersection of autonomous vehicle technology, artificial intelligence, and environmental sustainability, with a specific focus on addressing the challenges of off-road scenarios. The motivation for this work stems from the growing demand for autonomous systems capable of operating in diverse and challenging environments, particularly for applications like SAR missions.

Traditional Search and Rescue (SAR) operations often rely on human-led searches or aerial vehicles equipped with cameras and object detection algorithms. While effective in many scenarios, these approaches have limitations, especially in rugged terrains or when

weather conditions hinder aerial surveillance. Ground robots and autonomous vehicles offer a promising alternative, with the potential to access remote and difficult-to-reach areas. However, the development of such systems for off-road environments requires specialized algorithms and datasets that account for the unique challenges of these settings.

Furthermore, the environmental impact of autonomous vehicles is a growing concern. As these vehicles become more prevalent, it is crucial to develop strategies to minimize their carbon footprint and optimize energy efficiency. This necessitates the development of accurate CO_2 emission prediction models and control algorithms that can adapt to varying terrain and driving conditions.

This thesis aims to address these challenges by exploring and developing novel AI-based solutions for off-road autonomous vehicle perception, teleoperation, and CO_2 emission prediction. By leveraging SotA DL techniques, multi-sensor fusion, and real-world data collection, this research seeks to advance the field of autonomous driving and contribute to the development of safer, more efficient, and environmentally responsible autonomous systems for off-road operations.

Specifically, the thesis will focus on the following key areas:

- **Environmental Awareness:** Developing robust object detection algorithms for identifying humans and other objects in off-road environments, leveraging both single-modal LiDAR-based and multi-modal LiDAR-camera fusion approaches.
- **Point Cloud Resolution Enhancement:** Investigating generative AI techniques for enhancing LiDAR point cloud resolution, improving the accuracy of object detection and scene understanding in off-road scenarios.
- **Remote Control Systems:** Designing and implementing a human-in-the-loop teleoperation system that enables remote human intervention in challenging situations, ensuring safety and expanding the operational capabilities of autonomous vehicles in off-road environments.

- **Carbon Emission Forecasting:** Developing a transformer-based AI model for accurate carbon emission forecasting in self-driving vehicles, aiming to optimize battery usage and minimize the environmental impact of autonomous driving.

By addressing these research areas, this thesis aims to contribute to the advancement of off-road autonomous vehicle technology, ultimately improving the effectiveness and sustainability of various applications, including search and rescue missions.

8.2 Achievements

This thesis successfully addressed the multifaceted challenges of off-road autonomous vehicle deployment. Objective 1 (see 1.2) was achieved by the creation and development of a novel off-road dataset, specifically designed for people detection. This dataset, encompassing diverse terrains and conditions, provides a crucial resource for training and evaluating perception systems in off-road scenarios. Additionally, the integration of LiDAR and camera data within this dataset enables the exploration of multi-modal fusion techniques, advancing the field towards more robust and comprehensive perception capabilities.

Objectives 2 and 3 (see 1.2) focused on evaluating the performance of single-modal and multi-modal AI algorithms for off-road people detection. A comprehensive analysis of various algorithms on both the KITTI and UWS Off-road datasets provided valuable insights into their strengths and weaknesses in different environments. This rigorous evaluation serves as a benchmark for future research in off-road object detection and highlights the potential of deep learning models for improving safety in challenging terrains.

To further enhance perception capabilities, Objective 4 (see 1.2) was achieved by exploring and developing point cloud upsampling techniques using generative AI. By improving the resolution and quality of LiDAR point cloud data, this work contributes to more accurate object detection and scene understanding, particularly in off-road environments where detailed information is crucial for safe navigation.

Objective 5 (see 1.2), focusing on human-in-the-loop autonomy, was realized through the design and implementation of a remote driving framework on a commercial vehicle

using a 4G network. This real-world validation demonstrates the feasibility of teleoperation as a complementary technology to autonomous driving, enabling human intervention in challenging or unexpected scenarios.

Lastly, Objective 6 (see 1.2) aimed to improve environmental awareness by developing a transformer-based model for CO_2 emission prediction. The successful implementation and evaluation of the CO_2ViT model, not only in standalone mode but also within a simulated 5G MEC environment, highlights its potential for real-time emission prediction and optimization in self-driving vehicles. This contribution not only advances the understanding of vehicle environmental impact but also showcases the feasibility of leveraging edge computing for more sustainable and efficient transportation systems.

8.3 Future Work

8.3.1 Perception

This thesis makes significant advancements in off-road human detection but also highlights several areas for future research and improvement. The UWS Off-road dataset, despite its focus on challenging terrains, is limited in size and diversity. Future work should expand this dataset to include a broader range of off-road environments, various terrains, different lighting conditions, and more object classes beyond humans, such as animals and vehicles. This expansion will improve the generalizability and practical application of detection algorithms.

Additionally, while this thesis evaluates existing state-of-the-art algorithms, there is considerable potential for developing new architectures tailored specifically for off-road human detection. Future research should incorporate domain-specific knowledge of off-road environments, develop advanced fusion algorithms to effectively use both LiDAR and camera data, and explore cutting-edge Machine Learning (ML) techniques, such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) and transformers. For instance, GNNs can model the relational structure inherent in LiDAR point clouds, representing objects and their spatial relationships more effectively. Neural graphic learning techniques, such as graph-based attention mechanisms or dynamic graph construction, could enhance the representation

of complex off-road environments by capturing dependencies among detected objects and environmental features. These approaches can be particularly beneficial for dealing with occlusions and irregular terrains.

Refining evaluation metrics is also crucial. Developing specialized metrics that address the unique challenges of off-road scenarios, such as occlusion, varying lighting, and terrain irregularities, will provide a more comprehensive assessment of algorithm performance.

Finally, addressing the real-world deployment challenges in SAR operations is a significant area for future research. This includes optimizing computational resources and power consumption, ensuring seamless integration with existing SAR infrastructure, and exploring collaboration between human operators and autonomous agents to improve detection performance in challenging off-road environments. Incorporating neural-symbolic reasoning frameworks or graph-based decision-making models into the deployment could also enable more effective coordination between autonomous agents and human operators, leveraging high-level abstractions of the environment for improved situational awareness.

8.3.2 Point Cloud Upsampling

This thesis establishes a basis for future research in improving point cloud upsampling for self-driving cars. The current tests, limited to a specific part of the KITTI dataset, highlight the need for more varied datasets that reflect real driving situations. Future work should gather data from different environments, weather conditions, and LiDAR sensor setups. Adding data from other sensors like cameras and radar could further improve the process.

While the Hausdorff distance is a useful measure, it doesn't fully assess all aspects of point cloud quality. Future studies should consider additional measures like point distribution and how well the data looks to create a more complete evaluation system. This would help guide improvements to make the upsampled point clouds more accurate and useful.

Looking beyond the PU-Net and PU-GCN models, as well as exploring different ways to measure errors during training, could lead to new and better ways to improve point cloud resolution. More in-depth studies on fine-tuning the models and using different training approaches might also help them work better in general.

Making these upsampling techniques work quickly in real-world self-driving cars is important. Future research should focus on making the models smaller and faster, without losing accuracy. This could be done by using simpler models or techniques that reduce the amount of data needed to run the model. Also, these improved point clouds need to work well with other parts of the car's perception system, like those that detect and track objects, so that they can be used in real-world self-driving situations.

By addressing these areas, this research will continue to improve point cloud upsampling, making self-driving cars safer and better at understanding their surroundings in various environments.

8.3.3 Remote Car Driving

The future of remote car driving technology holds great potential. Enhancing system robustness against network variability is a critical challenge. Future research should explore specialized teleoperation networks, adaptive streaming protocols, and predictive algorithms to reduce latency and ensure smooth, real-time control.

Security is paramount. While functionality has been demonstrated, a comprehensive security framework is essential for widespread adoption. This involves rigorous testing of security protocols, encryption algorithms, and authentication mechanisms to protect against cyberattacks and maintain system integrity.

Expanding the scope of testing is also crucial. Future work should include diverse vehicle models, various hardware configurations, and a wider range of real-world driving scenarios. This will validate the system's generalizability and provide insights into its performance in different contexts.

Understanding human factors in remote driving is equally important. Future studies should investigate the cognitive load on remote drivers, the impact of latency on decision-making, and the overall user experience. This knowledge will help design intuitive, user-friendly interfaces that prioritize driver comfort and safety.

Finally, integrating remote driving with autonomous systems is a promising research avenue. Investigating seamless transitions between autonomous and teleoperated modes,

developing collaborative decision-making algorithms, and ensuring safety in mixed-autonomy scenarios are key areas for exploration. Addressing these directions will advance remote car driving technology, contributing to a safer, more efficient, and user-centric future of mobility.

8.3.4 CO_2 Emissions Prediction

This thesis establishes a robust foundation for future advancements in CO_2 emission prediction for self-driving vehicles and outlines several promising research directions.

First, expanding and diversifying the dataset is crucial. The current dataset is limited to a single-vehicle model under specific conditions. Future work should include a wider range of vehicles, driving behaviours, and environmental conditions to enhance the CO_2 ViT model's generalizability and robustness.

Validating the model in real-world 5G networks is also essential. This involves deploying the model on edge devices within actual 5G infrastructure and conducting extensive field tests in diverse environments to assess performance under realistic conditions and address potential issues like network latency, congestion, and interference.

To manage the computational demands of the transformer model, future research could explore model compression techniques or more lightweight architectures, such as Reformer or Performer models. These approaches would facilitate deployment in resource-constrained edge devices or directly onboard vehicles, enabling real-time CO_2 emission prediction and optimization.

Expanding the model's scope to include other pollutants and environmental factors would provide a more comprehensive assessment of the vehicle's environmental impact. Incorporating measurements of nitrogen oxides, particulate matter, and other greenhouse gases would lead to a holistic approach to sustainable transportation.

Finally, future research could explore using the CO_2 ViT model's predictions to inform real-time decision-making and control algorithms in self-driving vehicles. Developing adaptive strategies that adjust the vehicle's behaviour based on predicted emissions, terrain, and traffic conditions could minimize environmental impact and maximize energy efficiency.

Pursuing these directions will refine and expand AI-powered CO_2 emission prediction models, contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly future for transportation.

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